

MASTER'S THESIS

Simulation and Visualization of Gravitational Waves
from Binary Black Holes

Author:
Philipp SCHARPF

First assessor:
Prof. Dr. Peter NIELABA

Second assessor:
Prof. Dr. Daniel WEISKOPF

June 2017

Universität
Konstanz

Universität Stuttgart

visus

Visualisierungsinstitut
der Universität Stuttgart

Summary

This thesis covers the simulation and visualization of Gravitational Waves from Binary Black Hole systems. It aims to provide an overview of theoretical Gravitational Wave science, starting with a short insight into the experimental technologies and methods whose recent success motivated a multiplicity of theoretical work in the past years. The main objective of Gravitational Wave science is to develop accurate theoretical waveform templates that can be used in Gravitational Wave Data Analysis pipelines being convoluted with the signal to minimize the detector noise and allowing for parameter estimation of the astrophysical systems that shall be detected. Approximation schemes of Newtonian and Post-Newtonian theory are introduced, followed by an elaborate treatment of the Numerical Relativity simulation theory while a comprehensive catalog from the publicly available SXS Gravitational Wave database is examined. The simulated waveform data is subsequently compared to predictions of Quasinormal Mode damped harmonic oscillations of the remnant Black Hole that are expected to be evoked by the Binary Black Hole collision. Finally, visualization techniques in the context of Gravitational Waves from Binary Black Holes and Quasinormal Modes are reviewed. Recently developed tendex-vortex tools to visualize the spacetime curvature tensors are presented, followed by visualizations of tensor spherical projections, the angular distributions of spin-weighted spherical and spheroidal harmonics that occur in the description of the Gravitational Wave ringdown and Quasinormal Modes.

Results

It will be shown that the parameterspace of Binary Black Hole coalescence Numerical Relativity simulations available today is not sufficiently covered, making analytical models indispensable for data analysis. A phenomenological model for the merger and ringdown part of the waveform is constructed, containing the constitutive quantities fitted over the whole parameterspace and all multipole modes of the examined waveforms from the available SXS simulations. The model is able to provide fast waveforms and can be used to tune the Effective One Body code that relies on ordinary differential equations (ODEs). The multimode distribution is qualitatively discussed and the frequencies and decay times are compared to the complex Quasinormal Mode (QNM) frequencies predicted by Black Hole perturbation theory. Finally, the angular distribution of the QNMs is visualized and shown to be independent of the initial data of the numerical simulation.

Zusammenfassung

Diese Arbeit beschäftigt sich mit Simulationen und Visualisierung von Gravitationswellen aus binären Schwarzen Löchern. Ziel ist es, einen Überblick zu verschaffen über die theoretische Gravitationswellenphysik, beginnend mit einem kurzen Einblick in die experimentellen Technologien und Methoden, deren kürzlicher Erfolg eine Vielzahl von theoretischen Veröffentlichungen in den letzten Jahren motivierte. Das Hauptanliegen der Gravitationswellenphysik ist die Entwicklung theoretischer Wellenformen-Vorlagen, die in der Gravitationswellen-Datenanalyse genutzt werden können, wobei die Faltung mit dem experimentellen Signal eine Minimierung des Detektorrauschens sowie Parameterabschätzungen der untersuchten astrophysikalischen Systeme ermöglicht. Näherungsschemata der Newtonschen und Post-Newtonschen Theorie werden eingeführt, gefolgt von einer ausführlichen Abhandlung der Numerischen Relativitätstheorie, wobei ein umfangreicher Katalog von Computersimulationen aus der öffentlich zugänglichen SXS-Gravitationswellen-Datenbank untersucht wird. Die simulierten Wellenform-Daten werden anschließend verglichen mit Vorhersagen von Quasinormalmoden, den gedämpften harmonischen Schwingungen des verbleibenden Schwarzen Lochs, die bei einer Kollision zweier Schwarzer Löcher erwartet werden. Ein phänomenologisches Modell des Ringabklingens wird erarbeitet und diskutiert. Schließlich werden Visualisierungstechniken im Kontext von Gravitationswellen aus binären Schwarzen Löchern und Quasinormalmoden vorgestellt, gefolgt von Visualisierungen der Tensorprojektionen auf Kugelflächen, die Winkelverteilungen der Spin-gewichteten sphärisch und sphäroidisch Harmonischen, welche auftreten in der Beschreibung des Gravitationswellen-Ringabklingens bzw. der Quasinormalmoden.

Acknowledgment

I would like to thank Peter Nielaba, Daniel Weiskopf and Sebastian Boblest for offering me the opportunity to treat this interesting topic that is highly newsworthy.

Furthermore I thank Alessandro Nagar, Domenico Giulini, Gerhard Schäfer, Kostas Kokkotas, Andrea Maselli, Greg Cook, Hans-Peter Nollert and Tim Dietrich for their suggestions.

I also thank Stefan Gerlach for technical support and Martin Pütz for valuable formal hints.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Historical Introduction	2
1.2	Gravitational Wave Science	3
1.3	Visualizations of General Relativity	3
2	Basics	5
2.1	General Relativity	6
2.2	Gravitational Waves	15
2.3	Black Holes	22
2.4	Binary Black Holes	28
3	Analysis	29
3.1	Sensitivity	30
3.2	Detectors	30
3.3	Data Analysis	34
4	Approximation	35
4.1	Newtonian Theory	36
4.2	Post-Newtonian Theory	41
5	Simulation	43
5.1	Historical evolution	44
5.2	3+1 Decomposition	45
5.3	ADM formulation	48
5.4	BSSN equations	49
5.5	Generalized Harmonic coordinates	50
5.6	Initial Data	51
5.7	Treatment of singularities	52
5.8	Numerical Methods	54
5.9	Spectral Einstein Code (SpEC)	55
5.10	SXS collaboration project	56
5.11	SXS Parameterspace (own results)	58
6	Extraction	67
6.1	Regge-Wheeler-Zerilli formalism	68
6.2	Newman-Penrose formalism	71
7	Modeling	73
7.1	Approaches	74
7.2	Analytical Relativity (AR) meets Numerical Relativity (NR)	75
7.3	Effective One Body	76
7.4	Reduced Order Modeling	80
7.5	Phenomenological Models	81
7.6	Merger and Ringdown (own results)	82
8	Perturbation	93
8.1	Quasinormal Modes	94
8.2	Numerical Calculation	98
8.3	Berti data	101
8.4	Cook data	102
8.5	Comparison (own results)	103
9	Visualization	107
9.1	Raytracing	108
9.2	Tensor Field Visualization	109
9.3	Tidal tendexes and frame-drag vortexes	110
9.4	Quasinormal Modes (own results)	124
9.5	SXS Initial Data (own results)	131

10 Summary and Outlook	133
11 Codes and Literature	135
11.1 Chapter Simulation	135
11.2 Chapter Modeling	136
11.3 Chapter Perturbation	138
11.4 Chapter Visualization	139

Notation and conventions

Vectors are printed in bold math.

\Re and \Im denote the real and imaginary part respectively of a complex function.

Geometric Units $G = c = 1$ are used (if c or G do not emerge explicitly).

mass

total mass: $M = m_1 + m_2$

chirp mass: m_{chirp}

reduced mass: $\mu = m_1 m_2 / (m_1 + m_2) = m_1 m_2 / M$

mass ratio: $q = m_1 / m_2$

symmetric reduced mass ratio: $\nu = \mu / M = m_1 m_2 / (m_1 + m_2)^2$

length

extraction radius: ρ

binary separation: R

time

coalescence time: t_{coal}

spherical coordinates

ρ, θ, φ

Abbreviations

ADM: Arnowitt-Deser-Misner
AEI: Albert Einstein Institute
AH: Apparent Horizon
BH: Black Hole
BBH: Binary Black Hole
BSSN: Baumgarte Shapiro Shibata Nakamura
CCE: Cauchy Characteristic Extraction
EEP: Einstein Equivalence Principle
EH: Event Horizon
EMRI: Extreme Mass Ratio Binary Inspiral
EOB: Effective One Body
ESA: European Space Agency
FD: Frequency (Fourier) Domain
GHC: Generalized Harmonic Coordinates
GR: General Theory of Relativity, also General Relativity
GW: Gravitational Wave
HDF: Hierarchical Data Format
ID: Initial Data
IHES: Institut des Hautes Études Scientifiques IS: Inertial System
ISCO: Innermost Stable Circular Orbit
(a)LIGO: (advanced) Laser Interferometer Gravitational-Wave Observatory
(e)LISA: (evolved) Laser Interferometer Space Antenna
LOSC: LIGO Open Science Center
LSC: LIGO Scientific Collaboration
NASA: National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NP: Newman-Penrose
NQCFp: NonQuasiCircular functioning point NR: Numerical Relativity
NINJA: Numerical INJECTION Analysis
NRAR: Numerical Relativity Analytical Relativity
NS: Neutron Star
NSF: National Science Foundation
ODE: Ordinary Differential Equation
PDE: Partial Differential Equation
PN: Post-Newtonian
PSD: Power Spectral Density
QNM: Quasinormal Modes
ROM: Reduced Order Modeling
RWZ: Regge-Wheeler-Zerilli
SpEC: Spectral Einstein Code
SNR: Signal-To-Noise Ratio
SR: Special Theory of Relativity, also Special Relativity
SWSH: Spin-Weighted Spherical Harmonics
SWSdH: Spin-Weighted Spheroidal Harmonics
SXS: Simulating eXtreme Spacetimes
TD: Time Domain
TT: Transverse-Traceless
TTML: Total Transmission Mode Left
TTMR: Total Transmission Mode Right
WKB: Wentzel Kramers Brillouin

Chapter 1

Introduction

Simulation and Visualization of Gravitational Waves from Binary Black Holes [phys, SXS, NASA2, Fal01, Zim12].

Gravitational Waves (GW) are a fascinating prediction of Einstein's Theory of General Relativity arising from perturbations of spacetime produced by accelerated mass distributions. Being dynamical solutions of the general relativistic gravitational field equations, the waves are captured by a quadrupole formula whereas lower multipole contributions vanish. However, as the radiation intensity is very weak, significant emission is only expected to be detectable observing astrophysical events where huge masses are involved.

Binary Black Holes (BBH) are among the most promising sources of Gravitational Waves. In 2015 signals of Binary Black Hole coalescence radiation were finally detected and published [Abb16] in 2016 by the LIGO collaboration. This was the triumphant result of a long theoretical and experimental journey of many scientists from several different research areas in physics, mathematics, computer science and engineering.

Data Analysis tools for the evaluation of Gravitational Wave measurements from laser interferometry detectors have been tremendously improved over the last decades along with powerful computational algorithms, data storage and transfer technologies for a worldwide collaborating community of researchers.

Approximations such as Newtonian and Post-Newtonian expansions were available long before fully-relativistic numerical simulations of three-dimensional Binary Black Hole coalescence in asymmetric nonlinear spacetimes were possible. Constantly, each time after tremendous mathematical endeavors, higher order terms were calculated, steadily allowing for more accuracy of the waveform templates. Unfortunately, the approximations fail at short distances in the strong field regime of the general relativistic Binary Black Hole problem.

Simulations of Binary Black Holes were the response to this failure. However, being a "Grand Challenge" for several decades, they were not successful until 2005. The theoretical groundwork of Numerical Relativity is a mathematical (differential geometrical) formalism that trims the general relativistic spacetime to fit a format that can be evolved as an Initial value (Cauchy) problem.

Extraction of Gravitational Waves from the simulation data is a vital step in the theoretical process. There are several formalism available, most importantly the gauge-invariant Regge-Wheeler-Zerilli (RWZ) and tetrad depending Newman-Penrose (NP) formalism.

Modeling of Gravitational Waves has been found necessary to address the issue of a parameterspace that is only scarcely filled with simulations. The two main approaches are an Effective One Body (EOB) treatment that reduces the problem to Ordinary Differential Equations (ODE), and phenomenological models that fit the numerical data.

Perturbation theory of Black Holes has been evolved since the Schwarzschild and Kerr metrics have been found. It can especially be applied to the last stage of a Binary Black Hole coalescence when the system rings down into a quiescent remnant Black Hole by Quasinormal Mode (QNM) damped harmonic oscillations that radiate away as Gravitational Waves.

Visualization of Gravitational Waves from Binary Black Hole systems is an indispensable tool for the interpretation and evaluation of simulation results. Not only large data needs to be assessed and compared - recently also a formalism has been developed to gain intuition into the physical processes taking place in nonlinear spacetimes.

1.1 Historical Introduction

Already in 1905, Henri Poincaré was suggesting that, in analogy to electromagnetic waves that are generated by accelerated charges, there should also be Gravitational Waves evoked by accelerated masses. He called for a relativistic field theory of gravity and cleared the way for Einstein's endeavor.

After Albert Einstein had published his General Theory of Relativity (GR) in 1915, he was at first skeptical since his theory was not predicting dipole radiation as in the electromagnetic case. However, shortly thereafter in 1916, he was surprised to find dynamical solutions of the field equations that were a first indication for the existence of Gravitational Waves.

It was not until 1960 when Joseph Weber started the construction of a first Gravitational Wave detector, claiming a successful direct detection in 1969 though it was not commonly accepted but regarded as a fake (erroneous measurement or fraud claim). Yet in 1974, there was indirect evidence when Russel Hulse and Joseph Taylor succeeded in measuring the energy loss of a Binary pulsar (Neutron Star system) according to the predictions of General Relativity.

In the 1980s, researchers around Kip Thorne at MIT and CIT (Caltech) set the stage for a joint Laser Interferometer Gravitational Wave Observatory (LIGO) project to experimentally search for Gravitational Waves by interferometric methods that was initiated in 1992 with the construction of the LIGO detector, while first measurements were possible since 2002. In addition, the Laser Interferometer Space Antenna (LISA) was launched as a shared project of the United States space agency National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and the European Space Agency (ESA) and will hopefully be able to perform its first measurements in space. The ground-based LIGO and space-based LISA detectors differ primarily in their sensitivity and frequency range - the latter is expected to resolve low frequency Gravitational Waves carrying less energy.

Theoretical physicists started Numerical Relativity in the 1950s when Richard Arnowitt, Stanley Deser, and Charles W. Misner developed their ADM formalism to numerically solve Einstein's field equations. This was followed by a footrace ("Binary Black Hole Grand Challenge") to solve the general relativistic two-body problem numerically. There were many issues occurring, especially due to the singularities of the Black Holes that were treated, but finally Frans Pretorius could gloriously announce his first successful Binary Black Hole coalescence simulation through all relevant stages (inspiral and plunge, merger and ringdown) in 2005.

Probably the most important milestone in the history of Gravitational Waves was recently the first direct measurement of GW150914 by LIGO that was announced in February 2016. It not only motivated this thesis, but promoted worldwide enthusiasm in theoretical and experimental research efforts.

Figure 1.1: Historical stages of Gravitational Wave science. Important people and experiments [Wiki, Phyx, APS2, PSUCI, Wiki2, EinOn, SymMag, Wiki3].

1.2 Gravitational Wave Science

In order to be able to detect Gravitational Waves it is necessary to eliminate or at least minimize the inevitable detector noise by convolution of the experimental signal with a theoretical template (matched filtering). Template waveforms are obtained numerically or analytically, using simulations and approximations. There is an increasing number of publicly available waveform databases where Gravitational Wave templates from numerical simulations are collected and systematized, one of them is the SXS waveform catalog that is a subject of this thesis.

Presumably, the source of Gravitational Waves having most promise to be directly detectable are compact Binary systems containing Black Holes (BH) or Neutron Stars (NS). Waveform predictions can approximately be constructed using Newtonian or Post-Newtonian expansions in the dimensionless velocities of the relativistic objects.

The numerical solution of Einstein's field equations requires splitting spacetime (elegantly unified by Einstein's General Relativity) again into space plus time to be able to treat the relativistic scenario as an Initial value (Cauchy) problem.

In this thesis, the chapter 3 Analysis deals with the Gravitational Wave detector and data analysis issues while the chapters 4 Approximation, 5 Simulation, 6 Extraction and 7 Modeling treat the construction of (fast and) accurate template waveforms.

Figure 1.2: Gravitational Waves Science - different research fields [SSA, SXS, NASA2, Fal01].

1.3 Visualizations of General Relativity

There are several application areas of visualizations when dealing with Gravitational Waves. Firstly, it is possible to visualize the geometrical effects of a wave that passes through matter or spacetime by using a general relativistic raytracing technique. The results can be used for teaching purposes in schools and universities or in computer animations contained within movies, planetarium shows and computer games.

Recently, a new method for visualizing the spacetime curvature has been developed by a group around Kip Thorne at Caltech. The formalism provides tidal "tendex" and frame-dragg "vortex" lines from the curvature tensors that illustrate how spacetime is deformed by static (Schwarzschild) and rotating (Kerr) Black Holes. It has been proven useful for the visualization of large simulation data of Binary Black Hole or Neutron Star mergers, providing an overview of the parameterspace and facilitating the interpretation of the physical or geometrical processes.

For example, it was not sufficiently understood why calculations of the Black Hole coalescence predicted a large kick of the remnant after merger. However, the tendex/vortex tool was able to explain the phenomenon in terms of frame-dragg effects (the whirling of spacetime). Furthermore it could be examined how Gravitational Waves propagate from the near-zone around a Black Hole source to the far-zone as well as the geometrical nature of Quasinormal Modes, the damped harmonic oscillations of the remnant emitted directly after the Black Hole collision.

In this thesis, the chapters 8 Perturbation and 9 Visualization will present the most important concepts with a focus on the merger and ringdown part of the Binary Black Hole coalescence waveform and the excited Quasinormal Modes.

Chapter 2

Basics

Gravitational Waves from Binary Black Holes [phys].

Einstein's Theory of General Relativity (GR) is the result of a long journey of numerous brilliant scientists in Mathematics and Physics. It was required by the situation that deviations from Newton's theory of gravity were observed and a new theory was needed, incorporating corrections for instance in the perihelion shift of mercury. Ten years before publishing General Relativity, Einstein had worked out Special Relativity, unifying Galilean Mechanics and Maxwell's Electrodynamics by applying a Minkowski transformation which preserves the laws of mechanics and electrodynamics using the principle of relativity. As these transformations between Inertial Systems (IS) only covered rotations and boosts with constant velocities, a more general coordinate invariance had to be found including also accelerations. Moreover, the general relativistic theory of gravity had to account for the experimentally recognized principle of equivalence, the fact that Inertial mass and Gravitational mass have the same values, just being two phenomenologically different manifestations of gravity. Einstein was able to describe both as mere results of general accelerating coordinate transformations and by applying differential geometry he claimed that gravitational forces arise from spacetime curvature.

Gravitational Waves (GW) are in this context a dynamical perturbation of spacetime curvature propagating at the speed of light, or in figurative language "ripples in the fabric of spacetime". Mathematically they can be derived from Einstein's field equations applying small perturbation around a background metric (Minkowski, Schwarzschild, Kerr). Using coordinate transformations such as the Transverse Traceless (TT) gauge and a plain wave approximation for small perturbations, the metric perturbation tensor can be reduced to just two polarization modes, each one determined by a single scalar, the respective polarization amplitude. While General Relativity proposes a plus and cross mode, alternative theories of gravity propose other. In $f(R)$ theories for example, where the action integral S contains a function of the Ricci scalar R , there is the prediction of an additional breathing and longitudinal mode [KPJ16]. Electromagnetic radiation starts with the dipole $l = 1$ contribution, yet Gravitational Waves only with the quadrupolar $l = 2$ part due to a lack of momentum conservation.

Black Holes (BH) are a physical interpretation of the mathematical singularities occurring in the solutions of Einstein's field equations for spherical and axially symmetric mass distributions. First being a mere speculation, over the past decades, observational evidence has been found. The recent discovery of Gravitational Waves that, according to the predictions of General Relativity, were produced by coalescing Binary Black Holes (BBH) increasingly encourages physicists to believe in the existence of these monstrous astrophysical objects. Nonetheless, future measurements will show whether there is indeed a singularity shielded by an event horizon (conjecture of cosmic censorship). Moreover the No-hair theorem needs verification, postulating that only mass, momentum and charge are fully determining a Black Hole. Last but not least it is quite possible that General Relativity is not the final answer and we have to correct the calculations and perhaps discover extensive phenomenological revision.

2.1 General Relativity

This chapter is providing a short introduction into the theory of (Special and) General Relativity based on the textbooks of Gönner, Fließbach and Bona [Goe04, Fli12, BPL05]. Any information that is extracted from other sources will be cited explicitly.

2.1.1 Tensors

Einstein notation In the following, we will always abbreviate summing over double indices (appearing successively as upper and lower or vice versa) from 0 to 3 (spacetime, greek letters) or 1 to 3 (space, latin letters). In case of a vector this means

$$a^\mu b_\mu := \sum_{\mu=0}^3 a^\mu b_\mu \quad (2.1.1)$$

or

$$a^i b_i := \sum_{i=1}^3 a^i b_i \quad (2.1.2)$$

respectively for matrices

$$A^{\mu\nu} B_{\mu\nu} := \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \sum_{\nu=0}^3 A^{\mu\nu} B_{\mu\nu} \quad (2.1.3)$$

or

$$A^{ij} B_{ij} := \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 A^{ij} B_{ij} \quad (2.1.4)$$

and other variations of tensors.

Tensor Mathematical objects that transform linearly homogeneously as

$$T'^{\mu\nu\dots}(x') = \frac{\partial x'^\mu}{\partial x^\kappa} \frac{\partial x'^\nu}{\partial x^\lambda} \dots T^{\kappa\lambda\dots}(x) \quad (2.1.5)$$

are called tensors. Physical equations are relations between (coordinate dependent) tensors.

Scalar Some physical quantities like the rest mass m_0 , the speed of light c and four-scalar product (2.1.1) (for example the contraction of the four-momentum $p_\mu p^\mu = m_0^2 c^2$) are invariant under Poincaré transformations

$$x'^\mu = \Lambda^\mu{}_\nu x^\nu + a^\mu \quad (2.1.6)$$

(where $\Lambda^\mu{}_\nu$ is the Lorentz transformation matrix that will be defined in section 2.1.2) and therefore named Lorentz scalars. Scalars are rank-0 (dimension = 0) tensors.

Vector Rank-1 (dimension = 1) tensors are called vectors and can be used to indicate directions and shift objects. In general they have n components and can be represented as a column or row. In the three-dimensional Eukclidean space their components (denoted by latin indices) are projections on the x,y and z direction respectively.

Four-vector Vectors with four components are referred to as four-vectors (denoted by greek indices) that are elements of the Minkowski space that is defined in the context of a indefinite (squared) interval

$$s^2 = x^\mu x_\mu = x'^\mu x'_\mu = s'^2 \quad (2.1.7)$$

that is a Lorentz scalar¹. The components of a four-vector correspond to spacetime coordinates $(x^\mu) = (ct, x, y, z)$ of a particle. There is a distinction between contravariant vectors x^μ (denoted by upper indices) and covariant vectors x_μ (denoted by lower indices)².

Contravariant and covariant vectors behave differently under the transformations that are applied in Special and General Relativity. Contravariant components of a four-vector are parallel projections on the coordinate axes while covariant components are orthogonal projections.

Contravariant four-vector A coordinate of the four-dimensional spacetime in contravariant components is given by

$$x^\mu = (x^0, x^1, x^2, x^3) = (ct, x, y, z) = (ct, \mathbf{x}). \quad (2.1.8)$$

Generally a contravariant four-vector

$$v'^\mu = \underbrace{\frac{\partial x'^\mu}{\partial x^\nu}}_{\Lambda^{\mu\nu}} v^\nu \quad (2.1.9)$$

transforms contravariantly like differentials

$$dx'^\mu = \underbrace{\frac{\partial x'^\mu}{\partial x^\nu}}_{\Lambda^{\mu\nu}} dx^\nu. \quad (2.1.10)$$

Covariant four-vector A coordinate of the four-dimensional spacetime in covariant components is given by

$$x_\mu = (x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3) = (ct, -x, -y, -z) = (ct, -\mathbf{x}). \quad (2.1.11)$$

Generally a covariant four-vector

$$v'_\mu = \underbrace{\frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial x'^\mu}}_{\Lambda_\mu{}^\nu} v_\nu \quad (2.1.12)$$

transforms covariantly like basis vectors

$$e'_\mu = \underbrace{\frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial x'^\mu}}_{\Lambda_\mu{}^\nu} e_\nu. \quad (2.1.13)$$

Covariant four-derivative The four-derivative

$$\partial_\mu = \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial(ct)}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right) \quad (2.1.14)$$

with respect to a contravariant vector x^μ transforms covariantly

$$\partial'_\mu = \frac{\partial}{\partial x'^\mu} = \frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial x'^\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\nu} = \Lambda_\mu{}^\nu \partial_\nu. \quad (2.1.15)$$

¹Also named "Lorentz covariant quantity" since it does not change when the observer is moving according to a Lorentz transformation.

²The latter is not to be confused with covariance that is invariance under a coordinate transformation.

Contravariant four-derivative The four-derivative

$$\partial^\mu = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\mu} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial(ct)}, -\frac{\partial}{\partial x}, -\frac{\partial}{\partial y}, -\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right) \quad (2.1.16)$$

with respect to a covariant vector x_μ transforms contravariantly

$$\partial'^\mu = \frac{\partial}{\partial x'_\mu} = \frac{\partial x_\nu}{\partial x'_\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\nu} = \Lambda^\mu{}_\nu \partial^\nu. \quad (2.1.17)$$

Metric Co- and contravariant vectors (or in general multi-dimensional tensors) are related by a (generally coordinate dependent) metric $g_{\mu\nu}$.

With the metric (tensor) vectors can be transformed like

$$x_\mu = g_{\mu\nu} x^\nu \quad \text{bzw.} \quad x^\mu = g^{\mu\nu} x_\nu \quad (2.1.18)$$

and in general k -rank tensors behave contravariantly like

$$T'^{\mu_1\mu_2\dots\mu_k} = \Lambda^{\mu_1}{}_{\nu_1} \Lambda^{\mu_2}{}_{\nu_2} \dots \Lambda^{\mu_k}{}_{\nu_k} T^{\nu_1\nu_2\dots\nu_k} \quad (2.1.19)$$

or covariantly like

$$T'_{\mu_1\mu_2\dots\mu_k} = \Lambda_{\mu_1}{}^{\nu_1} \Lambda_{\mu_2}{}^{\nu_2} \dots \Lambda_{\mu_k}{}^{\nu_k} T_{\nu_1\nu_2\dots\nu_k}. \quad (2.1.20)$$

2.1.2 Special Relativity

Starting from the fact that the speed of light c is the same in all physical reference systems³, meaning that

$$x = ct, \quad x' = ct' \quad (2.1.21)$$

implies for the Minkowski square

$$s^2 = (ct)^2 - x^2 = s'^2 = (ct')^2 - x'^2 \quad (2.1.22)$$

to be the same (i.e. constant) in all inertial frames⁴.

The Minkowski square can be written as a Lorenz scalar

$$s^2 = s_\mu s^\mu = (ct)^2 - \mathbf{x}^2. \quad (2.1.23)$$

For light it holds that $s^2 = 0$ (lightlike), for particles moved or signals propagated in a causally cohesive way it is $s^2 < 0$ (timelike) while superluminal velocities $s^2 > 0$ (spacelike) violate causality.

Principle of (special) relativity Einstein postulated in 1905 the result of the Michelson-Morley experiment as a principle of (special) relativity stating that the speed of light $c = 2.9979 \cdot 10^8 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$ is constant in all reference frames, not depending on the motion of the source.

³A. Michelson and E. Morley showed in 1881 / 1887 with an interferometry experiment that the speed of light in vacuum is the same alongside and perpendicular to the movement of the earth.

⁴*Inertial frames* are reference frames moving relative to each other (or a system that is defined to be at absolute rest) at a constant speed, not accelerated.

Galilei transformations The laws of classical Newtonian mechanics remain invariant when inertial frames are transformed in space \mathbf{x} and time t independently

$$\mathbf{x}' = R\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{v}t + \mathbf{x}_0, \quad t' = t + t_0, \quad (2.1.24)$$

where R is an orthogonal rotation matrix, \mathbf{v} a constant velocity vector and \mathbf{x}_0, t_0 are shifts in space and time.

The distances of two points remain unchanged when transforming

$$\Delta r = |\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2| = \Delta r' = |\mathbf{r}'_1 - \mathbf{r}'_2| \quad (2.1.25)$$

and therefore also all physical quantities that are purely depending on distances, e.g. potentials

$$V(\Delta r) = V'(\Delta r'). \quad (2.1.26)$$

Galilei invariance The laws of classical Newtonian mechanics are invariant with respect to Galileo transformations, but the laws of classical Maxwell electrodynamics are not. The wave equations in vacuum⁵

$$\square \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{E} \\ \mathbf{B} \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{0} \quad (2.1.27)$$

are form-invariant under a translation or rotation. The solution is a spherical wave defined by a wavefront where the propagation speed is depending on the propagation direction.

Lorentz invariance In order to describe mechanics and electrodynamics in a unified way, it is necessary to find a transformation that leaves the fundamental equations of both theories invariant at the same time. The Lorentz transformations presented in the next paragraph meet this requirement. Newtonian mechanics are not lorentz-invariant - becoming invalid for large velocities $v \approx c$.

Lorentz transformations Homogeneity of time and space requires that an Inertial System (IS) with coordinates x^μ is connected to another IS' with coordinates x'^μ that is moved relatively (nonaccelerated) by a linear (location-independent) transformation

$$x'^\mu = \Lambda^\mu{}_\nu x^\nu + a^\mu, \quad (2.1.28)$$

where a^μ is a spacetime translation and the (possible) rotation and movement (boost) is captured by the 4x4 matrix $\Lambda^\mu{}_\nu$.

The connection with the Minkowski metric $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ is established by the invariance condition

$$ds'^2 = \eta_{\mu\nu} dx'^\mu dx'^\nu = \eta_{\mu\nu} \Lambda^\mu{}_\kappa \Lambda^\nu{}_\lambda dx^\kappa dx^\lambda \stackrel{!}{=} \eta_{\kappa\lambda} dx^\kappa dx^\lambda \quad (2.1.29)$$

which implies that

$$\eta_{\mu\nu} \Lambda^\mu{}_\kappa \Lambda^\nu{}_\lambda \stackrel{!}{=} \eta_{\kappa\lambda} \quad \text{or} \quad \Lambda^T \eta \Lambda = \eta. \quad (2.1.30)$$

For small velocities $v \ll c$, the Lorentz transformation (2.1.28) reduces to the Galilei transformation (2.1.24) that is included as a limiting case.

Minkowski and Penrose diagrams are a tool to visualize physical processes (events and Minkowski transformations) in four-dimensional spacetime.

Examining causality, three separate regions are distinguished: "lightlike" processes (or "worldlines" along the trajectory of the moved object) are causal as the speed of light c is not exceeded ($s^2 > 0$) whereas "spacelike" processes are not causal as signals cannot propagate with superluminal velocities ($s^2 < 0$). The propagation of light itself is "lightlike" ($s^2 = 0$) and is located in the Minkowski diagram on a (light)cone that is generated by rotating the bisecting line $x = ct$ around the ct -axis.

Gravitational Waves are expected to also propagate at the speed of light c before they arrive at a very distant observer after a long (approximately infinite) time. Therefore, in Gravitational Wave simulations and modeling, it is proposed to extrapolate the waves to future null (lightlike) infinity \mathfrak{J}^+ (see figure 2.1, right).

⁵ $\square = \partial_\mu \partial^\mu = \frac{1}{c^2} \partial_t^2 - \Delta$ is called *D'Alembert operator*.

Figure 2.1: Minkowski diagram (left, self-made) and Penrose diagram (right, [Nor]).

Equivalence principle The physical basis for General Relativity is the principle of equivalence which states that gravitational forces are equivalent to inertial forces.

In Newton's law of gravity ("action principle")

$$m_{\text{inert}} \frac{d^2 x}{dt^2} = \frac{GMm_{\text{grav}}}{r^2} \quad (2.1.31)$$

the inertial mass m_{inert} (resistance against change of linear movement) is equal to the gravitational (or heavy) mass m_{grav} (measure of gravitational impact).

This is manifesting in Galilei's law of falling bodies: In vacuum, all physical bodies are falling at the same speed [Gal13].

While the "weak" principle of equivalence states the above-named equivalence of gravitational and inertial mass, the declaration of the "strong" principle of equivalence is that in a freely falling reference frame, there is no net force because for $m_{\text{inert}} = m_{\text{grav}}$ the acceleration does not depend on any mass (no matter which type).

The principle of equivalence allows to construct a relativistic law of gravitation by finding a coordinate transformation that generalizes the Lorentz transformation between Inertial Systems including arbitrary accelerations that are shown to have the same effect as the gravitational interaction potential which is inherent to heavy mass.

In the following it is demonstrated how to find the general transformations of general covariance.

Covariance The line element (2.1.23) is invariant under a special relativistic coordinate transformation, the Lorentz transformation (2.1.28).

A tensor equation in Special Relativity (SR) is called "covariant" if it is not changing its mathematical form under a Lorentz transformation Λ . A tensor equation in General Relativity (GR) is called "covariant" if a general coordinate transformation α is changing both sides equally.

In order to generalize an SR-covariant to a GR-covariant law, **Lorentz vectors** $d\xi^\alpha$ have to be transformed (or generalized) to **Riemann tensors** dx^μ via the derivative relations

$$dx^\mu = \frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial \xi^\alpha} d\xi^\alpha \quad \text{and} \quad d\xi^\alpha = \frac{\partial \xi^\alpha}{\partial x^\mu} dx^\mu. \quad (2.1.32)$$

For the line element it follows that

$$ds^2 = \eta_{\alpha\beta} d\xi^\alpha d\xi^\beta = \eta_{\alpha\beta} \frac{\partial \xi^\alpha}{\partial x^\mu} \frac{\partial \xi^\beta}{\partial x^\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu = g_{\mu\nu}(x) dx^\mu dx^\nu, \quad (2.1.33)$$

where in contrast to the SR-metric $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$, the GR-metric $g_{\mu\nu}(x)$ is in general location-dependent.

As the line element is required to be invariant, the general metric itself has to transform as a tensor

$$g_{\mu'\nu'} = g_{\mu\nu} \frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial x^{\mu'}} \frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial x^{\nu'}}, \quad (2.1.34)$$

while the freedom of coordinate choice does not affect the (mathematical) properties of the metric.

In general, four-vectors are transformed as

$$A^\mu = \frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial \xi^\alpha} A^\alpha \quad \text{or} \quad A_\mu = \frac{\partial \xi^\alpha}{\partial x^\mu} A_\alpha, \quad (2.1.35)$$

while second-rank tensors obey

$$F^{\mu\nu} = \frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial \xi^\alpha} \frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial \xi^\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \quad \text{or} \quad F_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\partial \xi^\alpha}{\partial x^\mu} \frac{\partial \xi^\beta}{\partial x^\nu} F_{\alpha\beta}. \quad (2.1.36)$$

However, a Riemann scalar is still equal to a Lorentz scalar

$$S(x^0, \dots, x^3) = S(\xi^0, \dots, \xi^3). \quad (2.1.37)$$

General (relativistic) coordinate transformations In summary, there are two different types of transformations.

In Special Relativity, the characteristic location-independent Lorentz transformations Λ were introduced as partial coordinate derivatives

$$\Lambda_\mu{}^\nu = \frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial x'^\mu} \quad \text{or} \quad \Lambda^\mu{}_\nu = \frac{\partial x_\nu}{\partial x'^\mu} \quad (2.1.38)$$

with the corresponding back transformation being

$$\bar{\Lambda}^\nu{}_\mu = \frac{\partial x'^\nu}{\partial x^\mu} \quad \text{or} \quad \bar{\Lambda}^\mu{}_\nu = \frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial x'^\nu} \quad (2.1.39)$$

In General Relativity, there is the generalization to accelerated coordinate transformations α that are possibly coordinate-dependent, formally

$$\alpha_\mu{}^\nu(x^\nu) = \frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial x'^\mu} \quad (2.1.40)$$

or as above

$$\bar{\alpha}^\nu{}_\mu(x^\nu) = \frac{\partial x'^\nu}{\partial x^\mu}. \quad (2.1.41)$$

Energy-momentum tensor In Special (and General) Relativity, the (symmetric) energy-momentum tensor describes matter and energy fields.

Einstein found an equivalence of mass m and energy E connected by the speed of light

$$E = mc^2. \quad (2.1.42)$$

In one direction it can be inferred that mass is one possible form of energy. On the other hand it means that every form of energy is acting as gravitational (heavy) mass being source for a gravitational field.

Consequently, the energy-momentum tensor includes all possible energy types

$$T^{\mu\nu} = \underbrace{M^{\mu\nu}}_{\text{mass}} + \underbrace{P^{\mu\nu}}_{\text{momentum}} + \underbrace{Q^{\mu\nu}}_{\text{electromagnetic}} + \dots \quad (2.1.43)$$

where the individual terms are given by

$$M^{\mu\nu} = \rho u^\mu u^\nu \quad (2.1.44)$$

and

$$P^{\mu\nu} = P \left(\frac{u^\mu u^\nu}{c^2} - \eta^{\mu\nu} \right) \quad (2.1.45)$$

and

$$Q^{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left(F^\mu{}_\gamma F^{\gamma\nu} + \frac{1}{4} \eta^{\mu\nu} F_{\gamma\delta} F^{\gamma\delta} \right) \quad (2.1.46)$$

Here $\rho = \frac{M}{V}$ (mass M per volume V) is the classical mass density, $P = \frac{F}{A}$ (force F per area A) the pressure, $F^{\mu\nu}$ the electromagnetic field tensor and $\eta^{\mu\nu}$ the metrical Minkowski tensor.

The **four-velocity** of the source is given by

$$u^\mu := \frac{dx^\mu}{d\tau} = \gamma \frac{dx^\mu}{dt}, \quad (u^\mu) = \gamma(c, v_x, v_y, v_z) \quad (2.1.47)$$

with its **proper time**

$$\tau = \gamma^{-1} t \quad (2.1.48)$$

and the factors

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}, \quad \beta = \frac{v}{c}. \quad (2.1.49)$$

A **four-momentum** can be defined as

$$p^\mu = m_0 u^\mu \quad (2.1.50)$$

with the rest mass m_0 .

The electromagnetic field tensor contains components of electric and magnetic fields that are possibly present, being defined as

$$(F^{\mu\nu}) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -E_x/c & -E_y/c & -E_z/c \\ E_x/c & 0 & -B_z & B_y \\ E_y/c & B_z & 0 & -B_x \\ E_z/c & -B_y & B_x & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.1.51)$$

In case of absent forces, the energy-momentum tensor obeys a general **continuity equation**

$$\partial_\nu F^{\mu\nu} = 0. \quad (2.1.52)$$

2.1.3 Spacetime geometry

Einstein's General Relativity is a theory of gravitation that connects energy sources with the geometry of the spacetime it is contained within. The mathematical groundwork is therefore differential geometry with its descriptions of differentiable manifolds. A central concept is the curvature of spacetime that distinguishes between covariant effects of the coordinate system and genuine properties of the metric that can be associated with the gravitational field of a mass.

Covariant derivative Deriving means comparing values of a tensor field at neighboring points. In general, also variations of the basis have to be included. It turns out that the partial derivative of a tensor field in the Riemannian space of General Relativity is, in general, not a tensor. Yet it is possible to contract a "covariant derivative" ∇_α that preserves the tensorial behavior. For instance, a vector can be derived according to

$$\nabla_\mu v^\nu = \partial_\mu v^\nu + \Gamma^\nu{}_{\rho\mu} v^\rho \quad (2.1.53)$$

and a matrix as

$$\nabla_\rho g_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\rho g_{\mu\nu} - \Gamma^\sigma{}_{\rho\mu} g_{\sigma\nu} - \Gamma^\sigma{}_{\rho\nu} g_{\mu\sigma} \quad (2.1.54)$$

where both derivatives are consisting of the partial derivative ∂_μ and a connection term $\Gamma_{\lambda\mu}^\kappa$. It is apparent that each derived index needs an additional connection term, called Christoffel symbol, which can be given in terms of the metric as

$$\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^\kappa = \frac{g^{\kappa\lambda}}{2} (\partial_\mu g_{\nu\lambda} + \partial_\nu g_{\mu\lambda} - \partial_\lambda g_{\nu\mu}) \quad (2.1.55)$$

In a local inertial reference system (IS), the flat space of Special Relativity, the symbols vanish, yielding the tensorial continuity equation for the metric

$$\nabla_\rho g_{\mu\nu} = 0 \quad (2.1.56)$$

implying that if a tensor is zero in the local IS, it also vanishes in all other coordinate systems.

Having defined the covariant derivative, the **total differential**

$$dA^\mu = \partial_\nu A^\mu dx^\nu \quad (2.1.57)$$

can be generalized to a **covariant differential**

$$DA^\mu = \nabla_\nu A^\mu dx^\nu. \quad (2.1.58)$$

Parallel transport The covariant differential DA^μ is connected to the total differential dA^μ via the parallel transport δA^μ according to

$$DA^\mu = dA^\mu - \delta A^\mu, \quad (2.1.59)$$

while the latter can be expressed in terms of the Christoffel symbols

$$\delta A^\mu = -\Gamma_{\kappa\nu}^\mu A^\kappa dx^\nu. \quad (2.1.60)$$

Hence, the two differentials are equal only if the Christoffel symbols vanish and the spacetime is flat (Minkowskian or Euclidean) lacking field sources.

A closed path integral over the parallel transport is given by

$$\oint \delta A^\mu = \begin{cases} = 0 & \text{in flat space} \\ \neq 0 & \text{in curved space} \end{cases} \quad (2.1.61)$$

and can thus be used as a measure of curvature.

Riemann curvature tensor In General Relativity it is important to distinguish between the intrinsic curvature of spacetime and arbitrary coordinate effects. Therefore, a curvature tensor is introduced that vanishes in flat space, irrespective of the coordinate system.

The Riemann curvature tensor mathematically describes the noncommutativity of the covariant derivative and can be expressed in terms of derivatives of the metric tensor and Christoffel symbols

$$R_{\mu\nu\kappa\lambda} = \frac{1}{2} (\partial_\nu \partial_\lambda g_{\mu\kappa} + \partial_\mu \partial_\kappa g_{\nu\lambda} - \partial_\mu \partial_\lambda g_{\nu\kappa} - \partial_\nu \partial_\kappa g_{\mu\lambda}) + g_{\rho\sigma} (\Gamma_{\kappa\mu}^\rho \Gamma_{\nu\lambda}^\sigma - \Gamma_{\lambda\mu}^\rho \Gamma_{\nu\kappa}^\sigma), \quad (2.1.62)$$

requiring that a curvature is present if the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ is coordinate-dependent (partial derivatives ∂_μ with respect to the the coordinates x^μ do not vanish).

As mentioned above, there is a relation between curvature and parallel transport

$$\oint \delta A^\mu = -\frac{1}{2} R_{\kappa}^{\mu\nu\lambda} A^\kappa df_{\nu\lambda}, \quad (2.1.63)$$

where the change of a vector δA^μ along a closed curve \oint bounded an infinitesimal area $df_{\nu\lambda}$ in four-dimensional space obviously depends on the Riemann curvature tensor $R_{\kappa}^{\mu\nu\lambda}$.

Ricci tensor and scalar The Riemann tensor can be contracted by the metric tensor in order to obtain a **Ricci tensor** (reduced by two ranks)

$$R_{\mu\nu} = R^{\kappa}{}_{\mu\kappa\nu} = g^{\kappa\lambda} R_{\kappa\mu\lambda\nu} \quad (2.1.64)$$

and with another contraction, the **Ricci scalar** (reduced by three ranks)

$$R = R^{\mu}{}_{\mu} = g^{\mu\nu} R_{\mu\nu} \quad (2.1.65)$$

that does not depend on the reference system (the choice of the four-dimensional coordinates) anymore.

The Ricci curvature scalar is furthermore useful to determine the (non-liftable) curvature singularities, where the fields are diverging causing an infinite curvature.

2.1.4 Field equations

Having discussed the energy-momentum tensor (2.1.43) as well as the curvature tensors (2.1.62), (2.1.64) and (2.1.65) it is now possible to assess how General Relativity relates energy and curvature and thereby geometrizes gravitation.

While the Newtonian theory of gravity is only valid in three-dimensional space, Einstein's theory generalizes to the four-dimensional spacetime that was first introduced in Special Relativity.

The Newtonian field equation of gravitostatics

$$\Delta\phi = 4\pi G\rho \quad (2.1.66)$$

relates the gravitational potential ϕ to the static gravitational source given by the mass density ρ , while Einstein's relativistic field equations of gravitodynamics

$$\square g_{\mu\nu} \propto GT_{\mu\nu} \quad (2.1.67)$$

connect the metric $g_{\mu\nu}$ (being a four-dimensional generalization of the potential) with the dynamic mass sources⁶ given by the energy-momentum tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$.

Conceptually, this means that energy fields are sources of spacetime curvature.

The most general form of Einstein's field equations reads

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu} \quad (2.1.68)$$

or in a more compact form

$$G_{\mu\nu} = \varkappa T_{\mu\nu} - \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} \quad (2.1.69)$$

with the symmetric, divergence-free **Einstein tensor**

$$G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu} \quad (2.1.70)$$

that includes the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$, the Ricci scalar R and the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$.

The proportional factor is depending on the natural constants

$$\varkappa = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}, \quad (2.1.71)$$

the Newtonian constant of gravity G and the speed of light c .

The Lambda term, depending on the **Cosmological constant** Λ , is negligible on non-cosmological distances

$$\Lambda \approx 0, \quad (2.1.72)$$

leading to the very simple form

$$G_{\mu\nu} = \varkappa T_{\mu\nu}. \quad (2.1.73)$$

⁶While locally curving the spacetime metric, the sources are embedded in asymptotic flat space.

Structure The field equations form a system of nonlinear Partial Differential Equations (PDE) in the metric $g_{\mu\nu}$ that provides a description of the gravitational interaction in four-dimensional spacetime. However, only 10 of the 16 coefficients of the 4×4 matrix $g_{\mu\nu}$ are independent. The Riemann curvature tensor (2.1.62) has up to $4^4 = 256$ components that are reduced by symmetries captured in the **Bianchi identities**

$$\nabla_\lambda R^\mu_{\nu\rho\sigma} + \nabla_\rho R^\mu_{\nu\sigma\lambda} + \nabla_\sigma R^\mu_{\nu\lambda\rho} = 0 \quad (2.1.74)$$

or a conservation law for the Einstein tensor

$$\nabla_\mu G_{\mu\nu} = 0 \quad (2.1.75)$$

that enable the contractions to the Ricci tensor (2.1.64) and Ricci scalar (2.1.65).

Numerical solutions Numerical Relativity (NR) aims at computing the evolution of the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ for a given mass-energy source $T_{\mu\nu}$. If composite solutions are wanted where different regions of a spacetime are included with several sources, the metric is required to be differentiable (smooth) at the boundaries. Formally, the field equations are equilibrium conditions for matter and energy with terms for transport and sources. Apart from vacuum solutions (e.g. Black Holes), it is also possible to model hydrodynamic matter (e.g. Neutron Stars) where methods of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) can be applied. In Numerical Relativity, approximations are not based on physical parameters, but discretizations of continuous functions $f(t) \rightarrow f^{(n)}$, $n = 1, \dots, N$ are made to enable numerical integration. A comprehensive treatment of Numerical Relativity will be presented in chapter 5 Simulation.

2.2 Gravitational Waves

Dynamical solutions of Einstein's field equations are physically interpreted as Gravitational Waves, figuratively spoken "ripples in the fabric of spacetime". There are two transverse degrees of freedom or polarization states, a plus and a cross mode. Gravitational radiation is caused by accelerated masses and propagates with the speed of light, in this case called "speed of gravity".

2.2.1 Expansion around flat space

Einstein's field equations of General Relativity

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R = 8\pi T_{\mu\nu} \quad (2.2.1)$$

allow for seeking a metric solution $g_{\mu\nu}$ given an energy-mass distribution $T_{\mu\nu}$.

The general metric can be written in terms of the flat (Minkowski) metric⁷ $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ and a (small) perturbation $h_{\mu\nu}$, meaning an expansion around flat space

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \eta_{\mu\nu} + h_{\mu\nu}, \quad |h_{\mu\nu}| \ll 1 \quad (2.2.2)$$

If we exploit the coordinate gauge freedom

$$x^\mu \rightarrow x'^\mu = x^\mu + \xi^\mu(x) \quad (2.2.3)$$

and define the "trace-reversed" metric as

$$\bar{h}_{\mu\nu} = h_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}\eta_{\mu\nu}h, \quad h = \eta^{\mu\nu}h_{\mu\nu} \quad (2.2.4)$$

a "Lorentz gauge"

$$\partial^\nu \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} = 0 \quad (2.2.5)$$

⁷Or another background like a Black Hole metric.

can be used to find "Lorentz gauged" field equations

$$\square \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} = -16\pi T_{\mu\nu} \quad (2.2.6)$$

for the (trace-reversed) metric perturbation $h_{\mu\nu}$ that reduce the four terms contained within the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ given by equation (2.1.64) to a single term while the D'Alembert operator

$$\square = \partial_\mu \partial^\mu = \frac{1}{c^2} \partial_t^2 - \Delta \quad (2.2.7)$$

is applied to the perturbation.

2.2.2 Polarization modes

The Lorentz gauged field equations in vacuum ($T_{\mu\nu} = 0$) further reduce to

$$\square h_{\mu\nu} = 0 \quad (2.2.8)$$

with the solutions being plane waves

$$h_{\mu\nu} = A_{\mu\nu} \exp(ik_\alpha x^\alpha) \quad (2.2.9)$$

that are transverse

$$A_{\mu\nu} k^\mu = 0 \quad (2.2.10)$$

and propagating along light rays

$$k_\alpha k^\alpha = 0 \quad (2.2.11)$$

where k_α determines the propagation direction.

The amplitude can be decomposed into two (linear) polarization modes

$$A_{\mu\nu} = h_+ e_+^{\mu\nu} + h_\times e_\times^{\mu\nu} \quad (2.2.12)$$

whose directions (amplitudes h_+ and h_\times) are depicted in figure 2.2 while their effect on matter is described in the next section.

The transverse-traceless (TT) gauge

$$h^{0\mu} = 0, \quad h^\mu{}_\mu = 0, \quad \partial^\nu h_{\mu\nu} = 0 \quad (2.2.13)$$

has reduced the field equations' 10 degrees of freedom (d.o.f.) by 8 (one condition is redundant) to the remaining 2 that are captured by the two polarization states.

More precisely we have 10 d.o.f. (field equations) $\xrightarrow{\text{Lorentz gauge}}$ 6 d.o.f. $\xrightarrow{\text{TT gauge}}$ 2 d.o.f (polarization).

Finally, the perturbation in TT-gauge can be written in terms of the plus and cross polarization amplitudes h_+ and h_\times

$$h_{\mu\nu}^{\text{TT}}(t, z) = \begin{pmatrix} h_+ & h_\times & 0 \\ h_\times & -h_+ & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}_{\mu\nu} \cos[\omega(t - z)], \quad (2.2.14)$$

while the Gravitational Wave is propagating in z -direction with a frequency ω .

For a plane wave solution $h_{\mu\nu}$ propagating in the direction $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ one can define a TT-gauge "Lambda tensor"

$$\Lambda_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma}(\hat{\mathbf{n}}) = \delta_{\mu\rho}\delta_{\nu\sigma} - \frac{1}{2}\delta_{\mu\nu}\delta_{\rho\sigma} - n_\nu n_\sigma \delta_{\mu\rho} - n_\mu n_\rho \delta_{\nu\sigma} + \frac{1}{2}n_\rho n_\sigma \delta_{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{2}n_\mu n_\nu \delta_{\rho\sigma} + \frac{1}{2}n_\mu n_\nu n_\rho n_\sigma \quad (2.2.15)$$

that is representing the gauge transformation of the perturbation

Figure 2.2: Gravitational Wave polarization modes h_+ and h_\times propagating in z -direction [CB10].

$$h_{\mu\nu}^{\text{TT}} = \Lambda_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} h_{\rho\sigma} \quad (2.2.16)$$

Furthermore, in TT gauge, the Riemann tensor can be expressed as

$$R_{\mu 0 \nu 0}^{\text{TT}} = \frac{1}{2} \ddot{h}_{\mu\nu}^{\text{TT}}, \quad (2.2.17)$$

meaning that a Gravitational Wave $h_{\mu\nu}$ is a propagating curvature perturbation $R_{\mu 0 \nu 0}$.

In the Newtonian limit, where a component of the metric tensor

$$g_{00} \approx 1 + 2\Phi \quad (2.2.18)$$

can be identified with the classical potential Φ , the Riemann tensor can directly be derived as

$$R_{\mu 0 \nu 0}^{\text{TT}} = \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x^\mu \partial x^\nu}. \quad (2.2.19)$$

Further reading: [Mag07, BS10].

2.2.3 Interaction of Gravitational Waves with test masses

The geodesic equation in terms of the covariant derivative D by proper time τ can be written as

$$\frac{D^2 x^\mu}{D\tau^2} = -R^\mu{}_{\nu\rho\sigma} x^\rho u^\nu u^\sigma \quad (2.2.20)$$

with the geodesic deviation x^μ caused by the curvature $R^\mu{}_{\nu\rho\sigma}$.

In the weak-field TT-gauge and in the proper detector frame, the geodesic deviation x^μ can be related to the polarization amplitude or perturbation $h_{\mu\nu}$

$$\ddot{x}^\mu = \frac{1}{2} \ddot{h}_{\mu\nu}^{\text{TT}} x^\nu, \quad (2.2.21)$$

meaning that as

$$\delta x/x \sim h \quad (2.2.22)$$

the wave amplitude h measures the relative strain $\delta\xi/\xi$ between two particles in the spacetime that is stretched or squeezed by the Gravitational Wave.

With the line element

$$ds^2 = (\eta_{\mu\nu} + h_{\mu\nu}) dx^\mu dx^\nu \quad (2.2.23)$$

capturing a perturbation of flat space, the geodesic equation solved for modeling a particle that is initially at rest

$$\frac{dx^\mu}{d\tau}\Big|_{\tau=0} = \frac{d^2x^\mu}{d\tau^2}\Big|_{\tau=0} = 0 \quad (2.2.24)$$

yields

$$x^\mu(\tau) = \text{const.} \quad (2.2.25)$$

Figure 2.3 shows the elongation of free mass points on a circle by a linearly polarized plan Gravitational Wave passing in x^3 -direction. The spacial coordinates

$$x_P^1 = L \cos \varphi \text{ und } x_P^2 = L \sin \varphi \quad (2.2.26)$$

are constant, but their relative distances can change. The physical distance ρ of a selected particle in point P oscillates according to

$$\rho^2 = L^2 \cdot \begin{cases} [1 - 2h \cos(2\varphi) \cos(\omega t)] & (e_{11} = h, e_{12} = 0) \\ [1 - 2h \cos(2\varphi) \cos(\omega t)] & (e_{12} = h, e_{11} = 0) \end{cases}, \quad (2.2.27)$$

where the two possible linear polarizations are distinguished. Note that the two independent polarization directions are not perpendicular, as in the case of electromagnetic waves, but form an angle of $\pi/4$.

Further reading: [Fli12].

Figure 2.3: Free mass points on a circle $(x^1)^2 + (x^2)^2 = L^2$ (above). If a linearly polarized plan Gravitational Wave passes traveling in x^3 -direction, there are two possible elliptic elongation possibilities (plus and cross mode) depending on the direction of the polarization (below left or right) [Fli12].

The energy of Gravitational Waves

The energy flux of a Gravitational Wave with polarization amplitude h_{ij} is given by the time average

$$\frac{dE}{dAdt} = \frac{1}{32\pi} \langle \dot{h}_{\mu\nu}^{\text{TT}} \dot{h}_{\mu\nu}^{\text{TT}} \rangle \quad (2.2.28)$$

while the energy spectrum can be expressed as an integration over the angular space (with solid angle Ω)

$$\frac{dE}{df} = \frac{\pi}{2} f^2 r^2 \int d\Omega \left(|\tilde{h}_+(f)|^2 + |\tilde{h}_\times(f)|^2 \right) \quad (2.2.29)$$

in terms of the frequency domain (Fourier transformed) waveforms $\tilde{h}_+(f)$ and $\tilde{h}_\times(f)$.

Geometric optics in curved space

Gravitons are the postulated mediator particles of gravitational information and thus the particle model or image of Gravitational Waves. If they indeed propagate at the speed of light / gravity along null-geodesics, they should exhibit the same behavior as photons in the electromagnetic case suffering from deflection or redshift when passing massive bodies.

It can be shown that the "Einstein angle" (deflection) is the same for lensing of photons and gravitons

$$\theta_E^2 = \frac{2R_S d_{SL}}{d_{OL}(d_{SL} + d_{OL})} \quad (2.2.30)$$

with a geometry as shown in figure 2.4 below.

Figure 2.4: Gravitational (Wave) lensing geometry [Mag07].

Absorption and scattering of GWs

Finally, gravitons or Gravitational Waves are comparatively insensitive to absorption and scattering on their way from astrophysical sources to an observer - the gravitational cross-section is very small.

Significant absorption can only occur if the Gravitational Wave impinges on a Black Hole, where the capture cross-section of relativistic particles by a Black Hole with Schwarzschild radius R_s (see section Black Holes) is given by

$$\sigma = (27/4)\pi R_s^2. \quad (2.2.31)$$

2.2.4 Mass quadrupole radiation

For both electromagnetic and gravitational radiation, the amplitude decreases with $1/r$ and the propagation is at the speed of light / gravity c . However there are differences, as shown in the table below.

multipole moment l	monopole ($l=0$)	dipole ($l=1$)	quadrupole ($l=2$)
EM	✗charge conservation	✓	✓
GW	✗mass conservation	✗momentum conservation	✓

Allowed ✓ and forbidden ✗ (due to) multipole modes for electromagnetic (EM) and gravitational (GW) radiation.

In the weak far-field approximation where the wavelength λ of the Gravitational Wave is much smaller than the size of the source, the (TT-gauged) polarization amplitude

$$h_{\mu\nu}^{\text{TT}}(t, \mathbf{x}) \sim \Lambda_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma}(\hat{\mathbf{n}}) \int d^3x' \frac{T_{\rho\sigma}(t_{\text{ret}}, \mathbf{x}')}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|} \quad (2.2.32)$$

is given in terms of the energy-momentum tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ that is evaluated at the retarded time $t_{\text{ret}} = t - r$.

If we define a mass moment

$$M^{\mu\nu} = \int d^3x T^{00} x^\mu x^\nu \quad (2.2.33)$$

from the energy-momentum tensor $T^{\mu\nu}$, the quadrupole moment can be computed as

$$Q^{\mu\nu} = M^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{3}\delta^{\mu\nu} M_{\lambda\lambda} = \int d^3x \rho(t, \mathbf{x}) (x^\mu x^\nu - \frac{1}{3}r^2 \delta^{\mu\nu}) \quad (2.2.34)$$

where $\rho(t, \mathbf{x})$ is the mass density.

In TT-gauge, the polarization tensor is then related to the second time derivative of the quadrupole moment by Einstein's quadrupole formula

$$h_{\mu\nu}^{\text{TT}}(t, \mathbf{x}) = \frac{2}{r} \ddot{Q}_{\mu\nu}^{\text{TT}}(t_{\text{ret}}), \quad (2.2.35)$$

meaning that Gravitational Waves are time changes of the quadrupolar mass distribution.

The energy spectrum of the quadrupole radiation can be derived, given by the Fourier transformed quadrupole moment $\tilde{Q}_{\mu\nu}$

$$\frac{dE}{d\omega} = \frac{1}{5\pi} \omega^6 \tilde{Q}_{\mu\nu}(\omega) \tilde{Q}_{\mu\nu}^*(\omega) \quad (2.2.36)$$

while the angular momentum carried away by Gravitational Waves (per unit time) is

$$\frac{dJ^\mu}{dt} = \frac{2}{5} \epsilon^{\mu\rho\sigma} \langle \ddot{Q}_{\rho\lambda}(t) \ddot{Q}_{\sigma\lambda}(t) \rangle \quad (2.2.37)$$

and the radiation reaction force (per unit volume)

$$\frac{dF_\mu}{dV} = -\frac{2}{5} \rho(t, \mathbf{x}) x_\nu \frac{d^5 Q_{\mu\nu}}{dt^5}(t). \quad (2.2.38)$$

Angular distribution of the quadrupole radiation

Having defined the mass moment $M_{\mu\nu}$ it is possible to compute a general expression for the polarization amplitudes

$$h_+(t, r, \theta, \varphi) = \frac{1}{r} [\ddot{M}_{11}(\cos^2 \varphi - \sin^2 \varphi \cos^2 \theta) + \ddot{M}_{22}(\sin^2 \varphi - \cos^2 \varphi \cos^2 \theta) - \ddot{M}_{33} \sin^2 \theta - \ddot{M}_{12} \sin 2\varphi(1 + \cos^2 \theta) + \ddot{M}_{13} \sin \varphi \sin^2 2\theta + \ddot{M}_{23} \cos \varphi \sin^2 2\theta] \quad (2.2.39)$$

and

$$h_\times(t, r, \theta, \varphi) = \frac{1}{r} \left((\ddot{M}_{11} - \ddot{M}_{22}) \sin 2\varphi \cos \theta + 2\ddot{M}_{12} \cos 2\varphi \cos \theta - 2\ddot{M}_{13} \sin \varphi \sin \theta + 2\ddot{M}_{23} \right) \quad (2.2.40)$$

that depend on time t , radius r and the angles θ, φ .

Quadrupole radiation from an oscillating mass

If we consider harmonic oscillations of reduced mass μ along the z -axis

$$z_0(t) = a \cos \omega_s t \quad (2.2.41)$$

with source frequency ω_s and amplitude a , the polarization amplitudes can be computed as

$$h_+(t, r, \theta, \varphi) \sim \frac{\mu a^2 \omega_s^2}{r} \sin^2 \theta \cos(2\omega_s t_{\text{ret}}) \quad (2.2.42)$$

and

$$h_\times(t, r, \theta, \varphi) = 0. \quad (2.2.43)$$

Quadrupole radiation from a mass in circular orbit

A circular mass trajectory of radius R in the (x, y) plane with orbital coordinates given by

$$x_0(t) = R \cos(\omega_s t_{\text{ret}} + \frac{\pi}{2}), \quad (2.2.44)$$

$$y_0(t) = R \sin(\omega_s t_{\text{ret}} + \frac{\pi}{2}), \quad (2.2.45)$$

$$z_0(t) = 0 \quad (2.2.46)$$

yields the polarization amplitudes

$$h_+(t, r, \theta, \varphi) \sim \frac{1}{r} \mu \omega_s R^2 (1 + \cos^2 \iota) \cos(2\omega_s t_{\text{ret}}) \quad (2.2.47)$$

and

$$h_\times(t, r, \theta, \varphi) \sim \frac{1}{r} \mu \omega_s R^2 \cos \iota \sin(2\omega_s t_{\text{ret}}), \quad (2.2.48)$$

where ι is the inclination angle of the plane, as shown in figure 2.5, while the possible resulting polarization modes are given in the table below.

Further reading: [Mag07].

Figure 2.5: Orbit inclination [Mag07].

inclination angle ι	polarization mode
$\pi/2$	linear
0	circular
intermediate	elliptic

Possible polarization modes depending on inclination angle.

2.3 Black Holes

Black Holes are astrophysical objects that are extremely dense (high mass and small volume). They are expected to form when a central gravitational collapse cannot be impeded by other forces such as gas radiation and degeneracy pressure in a star. Mass aggregations feature a region where the escape velocity (the kinetic energy of a test particle just exceeds the gravitational binding energy) is equal to the speed of light. Because this region will be causally disconnected from the exterior it is called the "event horizon". For a spherically symmetric mass distribution, the boundary is called "Schwarzschild radius" given by

$$r_s = 2GM. \quad (2.3.1)$$

It can easily be understood that astrophysically small objects below the scale of stars like our planet Earth have their event horizons lying within their physical surfaces. The Schwarzschild radius of the earth is roughly $r_s = 2GM_E c^2 \approx 8.8$ mm while that of a proton⁸ is $r_s = 2GM_p \approx 2.410 \cdot 10^{-54}$ m and even our sun has $r_s = 2GM_\odot \approx 2952$ m, still way too small to contain all the mass inside and lie in free space in order to be approachable. However, when a star has consumed all its fuel (elements whose cores can be fused in order to release energy) and ceases to emit radiation, the final collapse can lead to a Black Hole if the mass exceeds the "Tolman-Oppenheimer-Volkoff limit" that is currently estimated to be between 1.5 and 3 solar masses. In this case the event horizon lies outside the mass distribution and forms the boundary where not even light can escape (the fact that motivated the term "Black Hole", coined by [SA] Wheeler⁹ starting in 1967).

Further reading: [Fli12, Rin01].

Types and detection Apart from "stellar" Black Holes ($M/M_\odot \approx \mathcal{O}(10^0 - 10^1)$) there "intermediate-mass" mass Black Holes ($M/M_\odot \approx \mathcal{O}(10^3)$) that are believed to be produced by collisions of stars and "supermassive" Black Holes ($M/M_\odot \approx \mathcal{O}(10^5 - 10^{10})$) observed in the center of galaxies. Experimental detection can be done by *kinematic evidence* (impact on orbiting stars including Doppler shift), *eruptive proof* (tidal effects on stars near to the Black Hole that can be disrupted while characteristic x-rays are emitted), *aberrative verification* (deflection of light), *obscurative* (black border caused by red shift), *temporal* (time dilatation near the Black Hole) and *spectro-relativistic methods* (change in spectra of stars surrounding the Black Hole).

Further reading: [Mue].

No-Hair theorem Recall that Black Holes are characterized by their capacity to "suck in" the surrounding matter while there is nothing that can prevent the permanent gravitational collapse due to the diverging gravitational pressure. It can be shown that the field outside the event horizon is solely determined by the total mass M of the Black Hole even if the mass distribution was initially inhomogeneous. It was conjectured by Wheeler in 1965 that the conserved quantities mass M , angular momentum L and electromagnetic charge Q are uniquely determining the Black Hole and all possible "hairs", i.e. structures such as inhomogeneities and multipole moments are radiated away by Gravitational Waves. While being an open question awaiting evidence, the No-hair theorem gives rise to the Information paradox that asks: "what happens to the information that described the matter before it collapsed to form a Black Hole". In case it is destroyed, the unitarity of time evolution would be violated. One possible solution was proposed by t'Hooft, that is to say the information is not lost but instead projected on the surface of the Black Hole with the entropy being proportional to the area of the event horizon. Measuring Gravitational Waves from Binary Black Holes and examining Black Hole perturbations (oscillations) is expected to not only be a instrumental test of General Relativity but also an important step towards an examination of the No-hair theorem (see section Perturbations). Having agreed on the statement of the No-hair theorem, that there is only mass, momentum and charge determining a Black Hole, there are several Black Hole spacetimes that were discovered as solutions of Einstein's field equations of General Relativity. The most general metric of a stationary Black Hole is the Kerr-Newman solution for a spinning, charged Black Hole with parameters $\{M, L, Q\}$. If besides the mass M that should always be present there is only charge and no momentum $\{M, Q\}$, the solution is called Reissner-Nordström metric. When dealing with Gravitational Waves from Black Holes however, the electromagnetic charge Q is not part of the investigation, so that the parameters left are mass and spin $\{M, L\}$. Thus there are only two Black Hole solutions left: the general case of a spinning Kerr metric and the nonspinning Schwarzschild solution that is the limit of Kerr when the spin goes to zero. Both solutions are presented in the following.

Further reading: [Fli12, BS10].

⁸Because $r_s \ll r_p \approx 10^{-15}$ m the event horizon of the proton lies inside the spatial uncertainty of its quantum wave function.

⁹In fact it is reported that the expression was suggested by a student of him in a lecture on the topic [SA].

Figure 2.6: No-hair theorem and implied possible sets of the parameters $\{M, L, Q\}$ that are expected to uniquely describe a Black Hole [Mue2].

2.3.1 Schwarzschild metric

The Schwarzschild metric describes an uncharged nonrotating spherical symmetric point mass and can be applied to stars and Black Holes.

After Einstein had published General Relativity in November 1915 he was surprised when the German astrophysicist Schwarzschild found a first solution [Sch16] of the nonlinear coupled partial differential field equations already in January 1916. The first solution found by Schwarzschild is valid in the exterior while there is a second interior solution that was discovered barely one month later¹⁰. The interior solution assumes an incompressible fluid where pressure vanishes on its surface (approximately valid for stars). Due to Birkhoff's theorem which says that a spherical symmetric vacuum solution of the field equations is static, the Schwarzschild metric is stable confronting small nonsymmetric perturbations. However if the Black Hole is spinning (the Kerr metric) the asymmetry due to the ellipsoid of revolution leads to instabilities that can radiate as Quasinormal Modes (see chapter 8 Perturbations) or enable a Penrose process in which rotational energy can be extracted from the Black Hole within an area called "ergosphere" (see section Kerr metric).

Inner and outer solution The general solution in Schwarzschild coordinates $\{t \in \mathbb{R}, r \in \mathbb{R}^+, \theta \in (0, \pi), \varphi \in [0, 2\pi)\}$ is given by

$$ds^2 = -A(r)dt^2 + B(r)dr^2 + r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2). \quad (2.3.2)$$

For the vacuum exterior of the Black Hole, the coefficients are simply

$$B(r) = 1 - \frac{r_s}{r} \quad (2.3.3)$$

and

$$A(r) = B(r)^{-1} = \frac{1}{1 - r_s/r}. \quad (2.3.4)$$

The interior solution is more complicated because the energy momentum tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ does not vanish¹¹ and one has to take into account the inner mass distribution of the Black Hole

$$\mathcal{M}(r) = 4\pi \int_0^r dr' r'^2 \rho(r') \quad (2.3.5)$$

¹⁰ A few months later, Schwarzschild died tragically after returning from World War I.

¹¹ However it can be diagonalized.

to find

$$A(r) = \left[1 - \frac{2GM(r)}{r} \right]^{-1} \quad (2.3.6)$$

and

$$B(r) = \exp \left(-2G \int_r^\infty \frac{dr'}{r'^2} \frac{\mathcal{M}(r') + 4\pi r'^3 P(r')}{A(r')} \right) \quad (2.3.7)$$

with the pressure $P(r)$ coming from the equation of Tolman, Oppenheimer and Volkoff (TOV)

$$\frac{dP}{dr} = -\frac{GM\rho}{r^2} (1 + P/\rho) \left(1 + \frac{4\pi r^3 P}{\mathcal{M}} \right) A(r). \quad (2.3.8)$$

The exterior solution has a real physical singularity in the origin $r = 0$ as well as a liftable coordinate singularity at the Schwarzschild radius $r_s = 2GM$. Two singularity avoiding coordinates are presented below. The interior solution however is free from singularities.

Further reading: [Fli12].

Eddington-Finkelstein coordinates One possible choice of coordinates to eliminate the singularity at $r_s = 2M$ can be made by introducing a new radial "tortoise" coordinate

$$r^* = r + r_s \ln |r - r_s| \quad (2.3.9)$$

that goes to minus infinity $r^* \rightarrow -\infty$ when approaching¹² the event horizon $r \rightarrow r_s$.

Now there are two possible time coordinates, both leading to elimination of the singularity at $r = r_s$. The first one is called "ingoing" or "advanced" with

$$v = t + r^* = t + r + r_s \ln |r - r_s|, \quad (2.3.10)$$

while the second, "outgoing" or "retarded" coordinate is set by

$$u = t - r^* = t - r - r_s \ln |r - r_s| \quad (2.3.11)$$

The first is leading to advanced Eddington-Finkelstein coordinates (v, r, θ, φ) with the metric

$$ds^2 = - \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} \right) dv^2 + 2dvdr + r^2 d\Omega^2, \quad (2.3.12)$$

while the second implies the set (u, r, θ, φ) with

$$ds^2 = - \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} \right) du^2 - 2dvdr + r^2 d\Omega^2 \quad (2.3.13)$$

where in both cases the differential angular element is given by

$$d\Omega^2 = d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2. \quad (2.3.14)$$

Note the cross-terms occurring in the line elements, mixing time and radial coordinates. This obviously means that the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ contains two off-diagonal elements.

In mathematical terms, these coordinate transformations are analytic continuations of the classical Schwarzschild metric which is diverging at $r = r_s$ for nonrotating Black Holes. Both solve the problem that the event horizon can theoretically only be reached in infinite coordinate time by an observer very far away whose proper time is very

¹²The reason why it is called "tortoise" referring to Zeno of Elea's paradox "Achilles and a tortoise" where the "swift-footed" Achilles is in an imaginary footrace with a tortoise that he can never overtake (assumption) due to an infinite number of points he has to reach.

large. As it is assumed that instead, practically, an incident body reaches the event horizon in finite time, the above transformations are reasonable.

As a consequence of the two possible time transformations, the symmetry is broken and, as introduced before, one has to distinguish "retarded" from "advanced" solutions that can be interpreted as two possible situations of a semipermeable membrane enclosing the event horizon that lets particles pass only outwardly (retarded solution) or inwardly (advanced solution). For an observer bound to causality (retarded solution) thus the inside of a Black Hole remains hidden.

Further reading: [CoS, Spek].

Kruskal coordinates There is another commonly used way to eliminate the singularity at $r = r_s$. Instead of distinguishing retarded and advanced solutions by two separate parameters u and v , there is the possibility of using both simultaneously to find a metric depending on $(u, v, r, \theta, \varphi)$

$$ds^2 = \frac{4r_s^3}{r} e^{-r/r_s} (-dv^2 + du^2) + r^2 d\Omega^2 \quad (2.3.15)$$

and distinguishing the solutions by the signs \pm occurring in the definitions

$$u = \pm \sqrt{1 - \frac{r}{r_s}} e^{r/(2r_s)} \sinh \frac{t}{2r_s} \quad v = \sqrt{1 - \frac{r}{r_s}} e^{r/(2r_s)} \cosh \frac{t}{2r_s} \quad 0 < r < r_s \quad (2.3.16)$$

$$u = \pm \sqrt{\frac{r}{r_s} - 1} e^{r/(2r_s)} \cosh \frac{t}{2r_s} \quad v = \sqrt{\frac{r}{r_s} - 1} e^{r/(2r_s)} \sinh \frac{t}{2r_s} \quad r \geq r_s \quad (2.3.17)$$

where + corresponds to the retarded and - to the advanced solution.

The Kruskal solution is known to be the "maximal analytic continuation" of the Schwarzschild coordinate singularity. Incoming (retarded) or outgoing (advanced) Eddington-Finkelstein coordinates are transformed into lines that can reach from an arbitrary point in spacetime into either infinity or the physical singularity in the origin $r = 0$.

Wormholes Kruskal coordinates enable so called "Wormholes" as solutions of the field equations. If time is running ahead, the retarded solution can describe Black Holes whose event horizon is only traversable from the outside. If time is running reverse, the advanced solution can describe "White Holes" whose event horizon is only traversable from the inside. The connection of both a Black Hole and a White Hole at their singularities in the origin can be interpreted as a Wormhole (also called "Einstein-Rosen bridge") that is supposed to enable traveling in space or time by taking the shortcut which avoids the long way on the spacetime hypersurface (see figure 2.7). Morris and Thorne proposed [MT88] in 1988 that this could be a feasibility for time traveling and / or interstellar trips that are otherwise (at present) suspected to be impossible regarding currently imaginable spacecraft propulsion methods.

Further reading: [CoS, Spek].

Figure 2.7: A "wormhole" is a possible solution that combines a Black Hole (retarded solution) with a "White Hole" (advanced solution). It was conjectured [MT88] by Morris and Thorne that this a wormhole would allow traveling in space and time by taking a shortcut [Quora].

2.3.2 Kerr metric

The Kerr metric describes an uncharged rotating axially symmetric point mass and can be used to describe the vacuum exterior of a spinning Black Hole that is expected to form when a rotating star collapses or as remnant of a Binary Black Hole inspiral (see next section Binary Black Holes). The solution was found [Ker63] by Kerr in 1963.

Boyer-Lindquist coordinates While Kerr originally discovered the metric in Cartesian coordinates, the expressions are much simpler and more practicable for axially symmetric objects leading to Boyer-Lindquist coordinates (t, r, θ, φ) given by

$$ds^2 = - \left(1 - \frac{r_s r}{\Sigma}\right) dt^2 - \frac{2r_s a r \sin^2 \theta}{\Sigma} dt d\varphi + \frac{\Sigma}{\Delta} dr^2 + \Sigma d\theta^2 + \left(r^2 + a^2 + \frac{r_s a^2 r \sin^2 \theta}{\Sigma}\right) \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2 \quad (2.3.18)$$

with $\Sigma = r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta$, $\Delta = r^2 - r_s r + a^2$ and $r_s = 2GM/c^2$.

The dimensionless spin parameter $a = J/M$ cannot exceed $a = 1 \Rightarrow J = M$ due to causality. Moreover, Thorne found [Tho74] in 1974 that there is a critical maximum already at $a = 0.998$. In the nonspinning limit $a \rightarrow 0$ the Kerr metric reduces to the Schwarzschild metric. As for the Eddington-Finkelstein coordinates, there are cross-terms mixing time dt and azimuthal angle $d\varphi$. There are even pseudospherical Kerr-Schild coordinates which feature three cross-terms. However they can be convenient in numerical simulations as initial conditions are implemented more easily.

Asymptotic flatness and stability Both the Schwarzschild and Kerr metric are asymptotically flat meaning that as $r \rightarrow \infty$, the spacetime approaches the Minkowski metric.

It is the consequence of the Robinson theorem that rotating Black Holes with mass M and angular momentum J will necessarily be captured by Kerr's solution. The Robinson uniqueness theorem is valid for stationary axially symmetric spacetimes. Under the conditions of axis symmetry, asymptotic flatness, convex smooth event horizons and regularity outside of the event horizon, it implies that the spacetime is solely determined by the two parameters M and J which constitute the Kerr solution.

While the Schwarzschild metric is stable even with respect to nonsymmetric perturbations, Kerr's solution can only resist axially symmetric disturbances. As already mentioned in the previous section (Schwarzschild metric), it is possible to extract the rotational energy of the Black Hole using the frame-dragging. This Penrose effect can even lead to a complete loss of the angular momentum J such that the Kerr metric transcends to the nonrotating Schwarzschild case. In this sense, the Kerr solution is much less stable. Besides, the interior region of the solution appears to be unstable. It has not been fully approved to be discovered although recent development [HH17] looks promising.

Event horizon and ergosphere In the Kerr metric, the event horizon of a Black Hole is given by

$$r_+ = \frac{r_s}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{r_s^2}{4} - a^2}, \quad (2.3.19)$$

whereas the boundary of the ergosphere is

$$r_0 = \frac{r_s}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{r_s^2}{4} - a^2 \cos^2 \theta}. \quad (2.3.20)$$

As stated before, the ergosphere is a zone where an object is forced to corotate due to the whirling of spacetime - an effect called frame-dragging.

Cosmic censorship For smaller values of L both the Kerr and Schwarzschild metric provide a closed surface as event horizon of the Black Hole. This boundary shields the singularity (inevitably implied by the Field equations) from the exterior. Penrose postulated in 1969 a theorem of "cosmic censorship" saying that there should not be "naked singularities" without an event horizon. It is still open to be inspected whether the initial conditions of a gravitational collapse only lead to shielded singularities exhibiting an event horizon.

Further reading: [BMW, BS10, Fli12, Spek]

Figure 2.8: Event horizon r_+ and ergosphere r_0 of a rotating Kerr Black Hole [CoS].

Figure 2.9: Schwarzschild and Kerr geometry. In both cases, a singularity (point or ring) is shielded by an event horizon. The Kerr metric has an additional ergosphere where an observer inevitably corotates [Mue2].

2.4 Binary Black Holes

Binary Black Holes (BBH) are expected to be an important source of Gravitational Waves as their coalescence is accompanied by the emission of radiation. A compact binary can also involve Neutron Stars (NS) where relativistic hydrodynamics has to be applied.

2.4.1 Stages of the coalescence of compact binaries

This section will give a short overview on Binary Black Hole coalescence. The details are gradually revealed throughout the next chapters.

Figure 2.10: Stages of the coalescence of two Black Holes sketched together with the theoretically predicted waveform signal and the analysis technique that has to be used to describe the particular regime [BS10].

Inspiral

The first stage of the coalescence of two Black Holes is by far the longest period. The approximation of Gravitational Waves as small perturbations of flat space is valid only if the Black Hole separation is much smaller than their total mass. Gravitational Wave radiation constantly reduces the eccentricity of the orbit that is circularized. In the late period we simply have a quasi-circular orbit with decreasing radius. The Gravitational Wave amplitude and frequency are continuously increasing during inspiral ("chirp" signal) together with the speed of both Black Holes.

Plunge und Merger

After an Innermost Stable Circular Orbit (ISCO) has been reached, the Black Holes begin to plunge and merge. For equal mass binaries, the transition is continuous because deviations from circularity are already large when approaching the ISCO. Plunge and merger take place at an orbital timescale while the Gravitational Wave amplitude has its maximum at merger. As this stage is highly nonlinear being in the strong-field regime, Numerical Relativity simulations are indispensable.

Ringdown

After the two Black Holes have merged, a remnant is produced that exponentially rings down its deviations from spherical (nonrotating) or axial (rotating) symmetry. The oscillations (called "Quasinormal Modes") are damped by Gravitational Wave emission being predictions of Black Hole perturbation theory (see chapter 8 Perturbation). An important question to ask is which modes (directions, overtones) are excited after merger depending on initial parameters.

Chapter 3

Analysis

Ground-based LIGO and space-based LISA Gravitational Wave detectors [LE, UB].

Measuring Gravitational Waves is definitely not an easy task, often referred to as "finding a needle in a haystack". One has to detect a strain of spacetime in the order of $h \sim 10^{-20}$ or several magnitudes less. Even for large monitored distances of a few kilometers (arm length for the largest ground-based detectors), this leads to the necessity of detecting distortions around the size of an atom's nucleus (often even a small fraction thereof).

There are mainly two different detector types. Resonance detectors measure quadrupolar oscillations in a solid caused by Gravitational Waves. Often a metal rod or sphere (cooled down) is excited while resonance provides an amplification that leads to detectability. The first detector, constructed by Weber since 1960 and used for measurements since 1969 was of that type. Although Weber's result were not acknowledged, he at least made Gravitational Wave research popular motivating later the construction of further interferometric detectors. Those are based on a different principle, optical interferometry that has a long history - including the well-known Michelson interferometer, back then (1887) falsifying the ether theory of a medium for light in outer space. (Laser) beams are running through two orthogonal arms while runtime differences are interferometrically detected. The setup will be described in more detail in this chapter.

Besides the two famous LIGO detectors in Hanford (Washington, USA) and Livingston (Louisiana, USA), there are smaller detectors: VIRGO in Cascina near Pisa, Italy (an Italian/French collaboration) and GEO600 near Hannover, Germany (a German/English collaboration). Furthermore, there is TAMA300 in Tokyo, Japan and ACIGO in Perth, Australia. All these ground based-detectors are measuring only the high-frequency range of the Gravitational Wave spectrum. For lower frequencies (or energies), space-based detectors are needed such as the LISA telescopes. DECIGO in Japan is bridging the gap between both frequency ranges.

Data Analysis of Gravitational Waves heavily relies on the technique of Matched-filtering where the noisy signal is convoluted with a theoretically constructed template. There are pipelines where numerous templates corresponding to different sources and parameters are available online. The LIGO Open Science Center (LOSC) [LOSC] not only provides the experimental data from actual detection events, but also several software packages - Python, MATLAB and C scripts to use in waveform analysis. The LSC Algorithm Library Suite (LALSuite) for example is a comprehensive collection of routines written in C. Moreover, there is Einstein@Home, a distributed computing project by LIGO Scientific Collaboration (LSC) and the Max Planck Society where volunteers can share and supply their computational resources to help finding Gravitational Wave signals in measurements of LIGO and GEO600.

Further reading: [BS10, Fli12].

3.1 Sensitivity

There are many different sources of Gravitational Waves and several detector types available or in construction today. An important question to ask is then which detector can detect what sources. Therefore it is possible to construct sensitivity curves where different quantities representing detectability are plotted against the Gravitational Wave frequency. Mainly there is the characteristic strain (or polarization amplitude) h measuring the relative change in length of the spacetime background, the Power Spectral Density (PSD) and Amplitude Spectral Density (ASD) that is the square root of the former.

Figure 3.1 shows a Gravitational Wave sensitivity curve¹ with respect to characteristic strain. The sensitivities of three detectors (IPTA, eLISA, aLIGO) are marked as black curves while the different sources form colored beams with flat or inclined tops. If there is a cross section above a curve, the specific detector is in principle able to detect the source while the area over the curve makes a prediction on the signal's strengths.

Figure 3.1: Gravitational Wave sensitivity curve with respect to characteristic strain. The area between the detector's curve (black line) and the top of the colored boxes quantify how strong the signal would be [MCB14].

The detectors that are included in figure 3.1 are the International Pulsar Timing Array (IPTA) in the low frequency range, the Evolved Laser Interferometer Space Antenna (eLISA) in the intermediate and the Advanced Laser Interferometer Gravitational-Wave Observatory (aLIGO) in the high frequency range. The last two are the current versions of LIGO and LISA and will be described in the next sections.

The International Pulsar Timing Array (IPTA) comprises several pulsar timing array experiments all over the world. Pulsars (pulsating source of radio emission) are magnetized, rotating Neutron Stars (NS) or White Dwarfs (WD) that emit electromagnetic synchrotron radiation that oscillate in their intensity. As the variations themselves are characteristic for the source and almost constant over time, a pulsar can be used as a "cosmic clock". Gravitational Waves however are expected to have a measurable impact on the pulsar timing.

Further reading: [MCB14].

3.2 Detectors

Observing electromagnetic radiation can roughly be compared to "seeing" as the wavelength is often much smaller than the objects that are examined. Gravitational Wave detection can instead rather be compared to "hearing" as the wavelengths are larger and the frequency lies in the "audible" range. Apart from this qualitative difference there is also a quantitative one. If we double the sensitivity of a Gravitational Wave detector, the observable distance doubles too and with an eight-fold volume the event rate is eight times larger. This is only possible because we can directly measure amplitudes that fall off with one over the distance as opposed to the electromagnetic case where one measures intensity that falls off with one over the distance squared. The detectable event rate of an electromagnetic detector with twice the sensitivity is only amplified by a factor of $\sqrt{2}^3$.

Further reading: [BS10].

¹An interactive plot can be found on <http://rhcole.com/apps/GWplotter/> where plot type, detectors and sources can be chosen by the user.

Figure 3.2: Pulsar - a magnetized rotating neutron star emitting electromagnetic radiation [OTTE].

3.2.1 Laser Interferometer Gravitation Wave Observatory (LIGO)

The LIGO Scientific Collaboration (LSC) of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) and the California Institute of Technology (CIT or Caltech) runs two "L-shaped" Laser Interferometer detectors at a distance of around 3000 km across the United States (10 ms light or Gravitational Wave travel time), one in Hanford (Washington) and the other in Livingston (Louisiana). Up to now there were two phases of operation, an initial (iLIGO) an advanced (aLIGO) that differed in sensitivity. The first detectors (iLIGO) had been finished in 1999 with detection beginning in 2002. As by the year 2010 still no Gravitational Waves were found, the setup was rebuild in order to increase the sensitivity by a factor of ten. Following the argumentation in the beginning of this section, this means enlarging the distance of detection also by the full factor of ten and the detectable volume or event rate even by a factor of 1000. The second phase (aLIGO) began in September, 2015 and within days the advanced detectors could accomplish what the initial were not capable of in 8 years of operation. A signal of Gravitational Waves from a Binary Black Hole convalescence could be measured from a source that was estimated to be around 1.3 Billion light years away from earth.

Further reading: [LE].

Figure 3.3: LIGO Laser Interferometer set up [LIGO].

Setup

Figure 3.3 is a sketch of the experimental setup of LIGO's Laser Interferometers. A highly coherent laser beam runs simultaneously in two orthogonal 4 km long vacuum tubes after being split while changes in the distances of test masses are measured as shifts in the interferometric patterns captured by a photodetector. Encapsulating approximately $10,000 \text{ m}^3$, the light storage arms consist of the world's second-largest vacuum chambers - surpassed only by CERN's Large Hadron Collider in Switzerland. An ultra-high vacuum with an interior pressure one-trillionth of an atmosphere at sea level ($10^{-18} \cdot 1013 \text{ hPa} \approx 10^{-15} \text{ Pa}$) enable the precise measurements. It took 40 days (1100 hours) to remove all the air and residual gases contained within the steel tubes that now bear up against 155 Million kg, surprisingly being only 3 mm thick.

Results

Up to now LIGO has detected two events. The first one is GW150914 detected on 14 September 2015 and published on 11 February 2016, the second one is GW151226 detected on 26 December 2015 and published on 15 June 2016.

The first observation of Gravitational Waves (GW150914) matched General Relativity's predictions of a Binary Black Hole coalescence with a chirp mass around 30 solar masses large. The individual masses were estimated to be approximately 36 and 29 solar masses. This yields a total of 65 solar masses while the remnant only had 62 meaning that 3 were lost radiated away as Gravitational Waves. The second observation of Gravitational Waves (GW151226) matched General Relativity's predictions of a Binary Black Hole coalescence with a chirp mass around 9 solar masses large. The individual masses were estimated to be approximately 14 and 8 solar masses. This yields a total of 22 solar masses while the remnant only had 21 meaning that 1 was lost radiated away as Gravitational Waves. In both cases the ratio of the mass loss is about 5 percent.

Figure 3.4 illustrates where the two LIGO detectors are positioned in the United States together with their observed signals of the event GW150914, published by the LIGO Science collaboration (LSC) in the LIGO Open Science Center (LOSC) that will be described later on. The signal was convoluted by a Binary Black Hole waveform template produced by the SXS simulation SXS:BBH:0305 [Mro13] (see chapter 5 Simulation) in order to actually claim a detection and estimate the parameters.

Further reading: [LOSC, Abb16].

Figure 3.4: LIGO detector's positions (above) and LOSC results of the event GW150914 (below) [LOSC].

3.2.2 Laser Interferometer Space Antenna (LISA)

While ground-based detectors like LIGO probe the high-frequency part (1 Hz - 10 kHz) of the Gravitational Wave spectrum, the space-based LISA project is supposed to be concerned with the low-frequency range (0.1 mHz - 1 Hz) - as shown in figure 3.1. LISA was originally a joint venture of the United States Space Agency (NASA) and the European Space Agency (ESA). However in 2011, NASA stepped out to rather support the Jupiter Icy Moon Explorer (JUICE) mission. Nonetheless, ESA continued the LISA project now under the name of evolved LISA (eLISA) or New Gravitational wave Observatory (NGO). Planned to be started in 2034, "LISA will be the largest man-made structure ever build - a giant laser observatory in space to probe the Dark Side of the Universe"[LISA]. As mentioned before, up to now we can only observe ("see") the visible universe by examining electromagnetic sources. With Gravitational Wave astronomy it will be possible to also observe ("hear") the invisible universe. This will hopefully help to answer key questions in astrophysics concerned with galaxies, Black Holes and the early universe.

Setup

LISA is designed as a giant triangle of three spacecraft satellites that will follow the Earth's orbit around the sun being connected by very powerful and precise laser arms more than one million kilometers long. Once brought into space to the specified positions by rockets, the setup will only slowly drift away from Earth without using additional fuel. Meanwhile, the high-precision Laser Interferometer will monitor changes in distance between free falling test masses. As illustrated in figure 3.5, the triangle will rotate to be sufficiently close for communication purposes.

Figure 3.5: LISA's stages on Earth's orbit [eLISA, BS10].

During the year 2016, a test run named LISA Pathfinder (LPF) was performed, bringing two test masses to a very quiet place around 1.5 million kilometers from Earth towards the Sun. Measurements of their relative motion by inertial sensors and an optical system started on in March with first results presented in June exceeding accuracy expectations by a factor of five. The experiment showed that General Relativity's principle of equivalence actually holds up to a relative acceleration of the test bodies lower than one part in ten Millionths of a Billionth (10^{-16}) of Earth's gravitational acceleration.

Further reading: [LISA].

3.2.3 Detector noise

LIGO and LISA measurements both suffer from different disturbing sources. The strongest interference can occur through seismic waves that are an important issue for ground-based detectors. Besides there is thermal ("white") noise that has to be minimized by low-temperature vacuum (see the LIGO section above). In space, in regions devoid of dust, we are still left with shot noise produced by the detector's photons, a random or stochastic process which cannot even in principle be eliminated, being an inherent property associated with the particle nature of light.

3.3 Data Analysis

Signals from Gravitational Wave detectors are only feasible after they underwent certain data analysis procedures to identify actual astrophysical encounters and estimate their parameters. Therefore several data analysis pipelines are available worldwide with lots of templates the signal can be compared with using matched-filtering convolutions.

3.3.1 Matched-filtering

A measure of overlap or match between a physical signal $h_1(t)$ and filtering template waveform $h_2(t)$ can be their frequency space inner product $\langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle$ given by

$$\langle h_1 | h_2 \rangle \equiv 2 \int_0^\infty \frac{\tilde{h}_1(f)\tilde{h}_2(f)^* + \tilde{h}_1(f)^*\tilde{h}_2(f)}{S_n(f)} df, \quad (3.3.1)$$

where $\tilde{h}(f)$ is the polarization amplitude in the frequency domain and a star * denotes complex conjugation.

The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is then

$$\left(\frac{S}{N} \right) = 4 \int_0^\infty df \frac{|\tilde{h}(f)|^2}{S_n(f)} \quad (3.3.2)$$

with the one-sided noise Power Spectral Density (PSD) of the detector

$$S_n(f) \sim \Delta f \quad (3.3.3)$$

being connected to the frequency resolution Δf .

For parameter estimation the template has to be set as a function of the parameters of the astrophysical system or source that is expected. For Binary Black Hole coalescence the combination of possible source and detector configurations implies an at least 17-dimensional parameterspace. Each Black Hole a priori obtains 10 degrees of freedom - 1 for its mass, 3 for position, 3 for angular momentum and 3 for the spin. Of the total 20 there are 3 related to the joint center-of-mass movement that presumably cannot be measured properly by Gravitational Waves as the sources are too far away.

The remaining 17 parameters can be either associated with intrinsic properties of the source or relations between source and detector. Among the first are the total mass $M = m_1 + m_2$, mass-ratio η , individual spins $\mathbf{S}_{1,2}$ of the Black Holes, time to coalescence t_c and the eccentricity e . As the orbit is gradually circularized by the emission of Gravitational Waves and supposed to be vanished when entering the detector's window, the last two can usually be neglected. Of the latter type are the distance between source and detector D that is equal to the extraction radius of the radiation ρ , the inclination angle ι , orbital phase ϕ , waveform polarization ψ and position of the binary on the detector's sky $\{\Theta, \Phi\}$.

Further reading: [CB10].

3.3.2 LIGO Open Science Center (LOSC)

LIGO operates a publicly available database website, supported by the U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF). First of all there are data releases from the two acknowledged events GW150914 and GW151226 plus a candidate event LVT151012 that can be analyzed using libraries in many software languages (C, C++, MATLAB, etc.). Apart from the specific events, also bulk data can be downloaded. Furthermore, tutorials on matched-filtering and signal processing are provided, mostly using the programming language Python². Different software packages are disposable. Pycbc is a "package to analyze gravitational-wave data, find signals, and study their parameters"³. The LSC Algorithm Library Suite (LALSuite)⁴ comprises "various gravitational wave data analysis routines written in C". Finally, some data analysis projects with LOSC data are presented.

Further reading: [LOSC].

²<https://www.python.org/>

³<https://github.com/ligo-cbc/pycbc>

⁴<https://wiki.ligo.org/DASWG/LALSuite>

Chapter 4

Approximation

From Newton's theory of gravity to Einstein's General Theory of Relativity.[RLC]

The full general relativistic two-body problem of two coalescing Black Holes cannot be solved analytically. Long before Numerical Relativity simulations were available, approximations had to be used to obtain waveforms of the signal that is expected to be emitted. In Newtonian theory the classical problem can still be solved analytically with the Keplerian solution. This is only possible due to the fact that no radiation loss of the orbital energy is included. The Gravitational Wave emission leading to shrinking orbits is a prediction of General Relativity and Einstein's quadrupole formulae (presented in chapter 2 Basics) that link Gravitational Wave strain and energy with time derivatives of the mass distributions's quadrupole moments. However one can combine Newtonian dynamics with Einstein's quadrupole formula (2.2.35) to obtain a first approximation for the Gravitational Wave signal, called Newtonian theory.

To achieve more accuracy it is yet necessary to use a (Parametrized) Post-Newtonian (PN) expansion to express Einstein's equations in terms of deviations from Newton's gravity where some parameters can be adjusted to account for possible amendments of General Relativity that await detection. The expansion is valid for sufficiently small fields or forces (weak-field approximation). The Gravitational Wave expressions are evolved in terms of a small parameter that is the velocity of the bodies divided by the speed of light. The Post-Newtonian formalism can be applied to all metric theories that incorporate the Einstein equivalence principle (EEP).

Higher-order terms can be added until a certain point where the field becomes too strong and a full numerical solution has to be found. Part of recent research was to find out where this happens. How late can we thrust Post-Newtonian theory and how early do we need Numerical Relativity near the merger in a Binary Black Hole coalescence waveform? This is a very important question since simulations require a lot of computational resources, not to mention they have to be successful for a certain set of parameters in the first place. Once that particular instant of time is found by minimizing the phase difference, both parts (PN and NR) can be brought together (see chapter 7 Modeling).

Even in the age where Numerical Relativity simulations can effectively be performed, Post-Newtonian theory is still needed to extent the inspiral part of the numerical waveform that would otherwise be too short because each Gravitational Wave cycle takes a lot of time to be computed. This chapter introduces basic concepts for obtaining both Newtonian and Post-Newtonian waveforms of Binary Black Hole coalescence.

Further reading: [Mag07, Hug09].

4.1 Newtonian Theory

This section is a sketch of the most important Gravitational Wave expressions in Newtonian Theory. More details can be found in the textbook by Maggiore [Mag07].

4.1.1 Inspiral of compact binaries in Newtonian approximation

Consider a compact binary made of two point-like masses m_1 and m_2 at positions \mathbf{r}_1 and \mathbf{r}_2 . In the Newtonian approximation and in the center-of-mass (CoM) frame, one can split the CoM motion with total mass

$$M = m_1 + m_2 \quad (4.1.1)$$

and CoM (barycentric) coordinate

$$\mathbf{r}_{\text{CoM}} = (m_1 \mathbf{r}_1 + m_2 \mathbf{r}_2) / M \quad (4.1.2)$$

from the relative motion with reduced mass

$$\mu = (m_1 m_2) / M \quad (4.1.3)$$

and relative coordinate

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1. \quad (4.1.4)$$

This leads to the relative equation of motion

$$\ddot{\mathbf{R}} = -(M/R^3)\mathbf{R} \quad (4.1.5)$$

while the source frequency can be derived from Kepler's law, increasing with shrinking radius

$$\omega_s^2 = \frac{M}{R^3}. \quad (4.1.6)$$

The Gravitational Wave frequency is found to be twice the source frequency

$$\omega = 2\omega_s = 2\pi f \quad (4.1.7)$$

and the polarization amplitudes (2.2.47) and (2.2.48) become

$$h_+(t, r, \varphi, \theta) \sim \frac{1}{r} m_{\text{chirp}}^{5/3} \omega^{2/3} \frac{1 + \cos^2 \theta}{2} \cos(\omega t_{\text{ret}} + 2\varphi), \quad (4.1.8)$$

$$h_\times(t, r, \varphi, \theta) \sim \frac{1}{r} m_{\text{chirp}}^{5/3} \omega^{2/3} \cos \theta \sin(\omega t_{\text{ret}} + 2\varphi),$$

where the chirp mass

$$m_{\text{chirp}} = \mu^{3/5} M^{2/5} = \frac{(m_1 m_2)^{3/5}}{(m_1 + m_2)^{1/5}} \quad (4.1.9)$$

is a characteristic of the binary system that can directly be determined from the waveform.

As the two bodies circle around each other (inspiral), the orbit decays due to the energy loss caused by emission of Gravitational Waves. This evokes an increase in both amplitude and frequency within the waveform, comparable to that occurring in an acoustic signal of a bird's "chirp".

The number of cycles, a binary completes depends on both the chirp mass and the frequency

$$\mathcal{N}(f) = \frac{1}{32\pi^{8/3}} m_{\text{chirp}}^{-5/3} f^{-5/3}. \quad (4.1.10)$$

Introducing a new time variable

$$\tau = t_{\text{coal}} - t, \quad (4.1.11)$$

where t_{coal} is the binary's time to coalescence, the frequency increase (chirp) until coalescence can be written as

$$f \sim m_{\text{chirp}}^{-5/8} \tau^{-3/8}, \quad (4.1.12)$$

while the increasing amplitude (chirp) until coalescence is given by

$$h_+, h_\times \sim m_{\text{chirp}}^{5/3} \tau^{-1/4} \quad (4.1.13)$$

and for the phase evolution holds

$$\phi \sim m_{\text{chirp}}^{-5/8} \tau^{5/8}. \quad (4.1.14)$$

The orbital radius (quasi-circular orbit in Newtonian approximation where $\dot{\omega}_s \ll \omega_s^2$) decreases according to

$$R(\tau) = R_0 \left(\frac{t_{\text{coal}} - t}{t_{\text{coal}} - t_0} \right)^{1/4} \quad (4.1.15)$$

with

$$\tau_0 \sim \frac{R_0^4}{M^2 \mu} \quad (4.1.16)$$

It has been estimated that only binary systems with initial orbital periods of less than about a day can have coalesced emitting Gravitational Waves within the present age of our galaxy - this is expected to constrain the observation of binary coalescence events.

Finally, the total radiated power increases with

$$P \sim (m_{\text{chirp}} \omega)^{10/3} \quad (4.1.17)$$

Further reading: [Mag07].

Plots of Newtonian waveform, frequency, phase and orbit

Figure 4.1 shows the Newtonian waveform given by equation (4.1.8) in Geometric Units and SI-Units that are related by the conversion factors for

- time:

$$G/c^3 M_\odot \approx 4.91 \cdot 10^{-6}$$

- strain:

$$(GM_\odot/c^2)^{5/3} (GM_\odot/c^3)^{-5/12} c^{-2/3} \approx 69.44$$

Figure 4.2 shows the Newtonian frequency given by equation (4.1.12) in Geometric Units and SI-Units that are related by the conversion factors for

- time:

$$G/c^3 M_\odot \approx 4.91 \cdot 10^{-6}$$

- frequency:

$$c^3/(GM_\odot) \approx 2.03 \cdot 10^5$$

Figure 4.3 shows the Newtonian phase given by equation (4.1.14).

Figure 4.4 shows the Newtonian orbit given by equation (4.1.15).

Figure 4.1: Newtonian waveform for an equal-mass ($m_1 = m_2 = 0.5$) Binary Black Hole with initial separation $R_0 = 18$ in Geometric Units (above) and SI-Units (below). The conversion factor for time is $G/c^3 M_\odot \approx 4.91 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and for the strain $(GM_\odot/c^2)^{5/3} (GM_\odot/c^3)^{-5/12} c^{-2/3} \approx 69.44$. The strain signal is further divided by the total mass M and multiplied by the extraction radius ρ , as it decaying like $1/\rho$.

Figure 4.2: Newtonian frequency for an equal-mass ($m_1 = m_2 = 0.5$) Binary Black Hole with initial separation $R_0 = 18$ in Geometric Units (above) and SI-Units (below). The conversion factor for time is $G/c^3 M_\odot \approx 4.91 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and for the frequency $c^3/(GM_\odot) \approx 2.03 \cdot 10^5$. The frequency is further multiplied by the total mass M .

Figure 4.3: Phase evolution of an equal-mass ($m_1 = m_2 = 0.5$) Binary Black Hole in Geometric Units, with initial separation $R_0 = 18$ and increasing until its coalescence time $t_{\text{coal}} \approx 8200$.

Figure 4.4: Radial decay $R(t)$ of the Newtonian orbit in Geometric Units, starting from the initial radius R_0 and decreasing until its coalescence time t_{coal} .

4.2 Post-Newtonian Theory

This section is a sketch of the most important Gravitational Wave expressions in Post-Newtonian Theory. More details can be found in the textbook by Baumgarte and Shapiro[BS10].

4.2.1 Inspiral of compact binaries in Post-Newtonian approximation

In order to perform a Post-Newtonian expansion of the physical quantities connected to the radiation of a compact binary, it is instrumental to introduce the symmetric reduced mass ratio

$$\nu = \mu/M = m_1 m_2 / (m_1 + m_2)^2 \quad (4.2.1)$$

and a dimensionless Post-Newtonian parameter in the velocity or binary separation

$$\gamma = M/R \sim \frac{v^2}{c^2}. \quad (4.2.2)$$

The orbital frequency can then be found as an extension of Kepler's law (4.1.6)

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_s^2 = \frac{m}{R^3} & \left\{ 1 + ((-3 + \nu)\gamma + \left(6 + \frac{41}{4}\nu + \nu^2\right)\gamma^2 \right. \\ & \left. + \left(-10 + \left(-\frac{75707}{840} + \frac{41}{64}\pi^2 + 22 \ln\left(\frac{R}{R_0}\right)\right)\nu + \frac{19}{2}\nu^2 + \nu^3\right)\gamma^3 \right\} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{c^8}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (4.2.3)$$

Furthermore, a dimensionless time variable can be defined

$$\Theta = \frac{\nu}{5M}(t_{\text{coal}} - t) \quad (4.2.4)$$

together with a dimensionless frequency variable

$$x = (m\omega_s)^{2/3} \quad (4.2.5)$$

that is found to be connected to the former via the expansion

$$x = \frac{1}{4}\Theta^{-1/4} \left\{ 1 + \left(\frac{743}{4032} + \frac{11}{48}\nu\right)\Theta^{-1/4} \pm \dots \right\}. \quad (4.2.6)$$

The phase can then be computed in terms of Θ as

$$\phi(t) = -\frac{1}{\nu}\Theta^{5/8} \left\{ 1 + \left(\frac{3715}{8064} + \frac{55}{96}\nu\right)\Theta^{-1/4} \pm \dots \right\} \quad (4.2.7)$$

or in terms of x

$$\phi(t) = -\frac{1}{32\nu}x^{-5/2} \left\{ 1 + \left(\frac{3715}{1008} + \frac{55}{12}\nu\right)x \pm \dots \right\}. \quad (4.2.8)$$

Finally, the polarization amplitudes can be expanded using x

$$h_{+, \times} = \frac{2\mu x}{R} H_{+, \times} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{R^2}\right) \quad (4.2.9)$$

with

$$H_{+, \times} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} x^{n/2} H_{+, \times}^{(n/2)}, \quad (4.2.10)$$

where the expansion coefficients $H_{+, \times}^{(n/2)}$ include numerous terms and can be found in [BS10].

Instead of using a polynomial Taylor expansion that converges well only if no poles are present, one can use a Padé approximant that in some cases converges faster for small binary separations (large expansion parameters). The resummation has led to another approach, the Effective One Body (EOB) model that will be discussed in chapter 7 Modeling.

Further reading: [BS10].

Chapter 5

Simulation

SXS simulation performed by the Spectral Einstein Code (SpEC) [SXS], visualized with ParaView.

With the advent of the age of ground- and space-based gravitational wave detectors such as LIGO and LISA (described in the previous chapter Analysis) there is an increasing need for accurate waveform templates to use in matched-filtering in order to tackle the low signal-to-noise-ratio. Since the birth of General Relativity in 1915 many people tried to solve Einstein's equations for different scenarios and it is undoubtedly a huge achievement that analytic solutions such as the Schwarzschild and Kerr spacetimes for static and rotating Black Holes have been discovered. Nonetheless these solutions are special cases of high symmetry and are not able to describe dynamical astrophysical processes like the collision of Black Holes in stages where weak-field approximations fail and the full nonlinear equations have to be solved. Numerical Relativity has been developed to fill the gaps around analytic solutions obtained by symmetry (e.g. Schwarzschild, Kerr) or perturbative approximations (e.g. Post-Newtonian expansions, Black Hole perturbation theory). It is a powerful tool to explore the physics of events taking place in nonlinear spacetimes with objects (e.g. compact binaries consisting of Black Holes or Neutron Stars) moving at highly relativistic speeds and approaching each other to strong-field distances. Assisted by the advance in supercomputer technologies, computational resources, numerical methods and algorithms, the new field has become increasingly mature over the last decades. After tremendous efforts of many physicists, mathematicians and computer scientists it is finally possible to simulate the dynamics of Binary Black Hole inspirals and extract the gravitational wave signal emitted. Many cycles, high mass ratios and spins have been achieved by continuously improving the techniques and jointly tackling all the countless problems occurring. Einstein's field equations are multidimensional, nonlinear, coupled partial differential equations in space and time and share many problems with other areas of computational physics (e.g. hydrodynamics). Additionally they introduce complications related to the choice of the arbitrary spacetime coordinates. Singularities appearing in the numerical equations due to an unfavorable gauge condition cause overflows in the computer calculations that lead to premature termination of the simulation. Thus the art and science has been to intelligently get around computationally encountering these singularities. Besides singularity avoiding coordinates that mostly require some symmetry, there is a possibility to simply "excise" the singularity containing region dynamically. The first successful Binary Black Hole merger simulation has however been achieved by "moving punctures" where the singularity is absorbed in analytic terms such that only the regular part is tackled numerically. Moreover, by introducing additional auxiliary variables, the numerical formulation of the field equations is improved. Last but not least, there is the difficulty to adequately extract the gravitational wave content from the simulation, bridging the probed near-field merger zone with the far-field detection zone. If not cited explicitly, this chapter follows the textbook of Baumgarte and Shapiro [BS10].

Further reading: [BS10, CB10, Hug09].

5.1 Historical evolution

After in 1959 Arnowitt, Deser and Misner had published their ADM formalism (Arnowitt et al. 1959) to numerically solve Einstein's field equations (by slicing spacetime into spacial foliations that evolve in space and time, see next sections), there was still a lot to do until the first successful simulation of a Binary Black Hole merger by Pretorius in 2005. In 1964, Hahn and Lindquist were the first to try a simulation of a head-on collision of two equal mass Black Holes on a computer in 2D exploiting axisymmetry. The simulation could compute 50 time steps to a duration of $\sim 1.8M$ until they stopped the code because it was no longer accurate enough for further evolution. Smarr and Eppley managed in the mid-1970s to successfully evolve the collision in the ADM formalism and extract gravitational wave information. They were using the most powerful computers available at that time. The more realistic scenario of an inspiral collision with 3D orbits could still not be implemented because of unresolved questions about the instabilities and insufficient computer power, so the Binary Black Hole merger problem had to wait for more than a decade.

As in the 1990s the LIGO project made progress, the need for gravitational wave templates to use in data analysis pipelines motivated people to return to the problem. The National Science Foundation was willing to fund a Computational Grand Challenge grant for a joint multi-institutional effort to tackle the Binary Black Hole coalescence in 3D including the extraction of the gravitational wave signal. Numerical relativists were surprised to discover that the merger problem in 3D was far more difficult than expected. In order to produce a waveform that could be used as a template for the detector data analysis required at least a few 100 M of simulated time covering the important stages of inspiral, plunge, merger and ringdown. Still there were many instabilities causing the code to crash without having any substantial portion of an orbit simulated. Starting 1994 Cook, Baumgarte and Pfeiffer provided initial data for a Binary Black Hole starting near the Innermost Stable Circular Orbit (ISCO). Supported by the tools to deal with the singularities, namely excision by Seidel in 1992 and punctures by Brandt and Brügmann in 1997, the problem was almost ready to be mastered. Starting 1992, Bona and Massó were the first to stress the importance of hyperbolicity in formulating the Einstein equations for numerical solution.

The ADM evolution equations were reformulated by Baumgarte and Shapiro in 1998 resurrecting an approach already published by Shibata and Nakamura in 1995. The BSSN formalism enabled the simulation of boosted Black Holes (Cook et al., 1998), head-on collisions (Sperhake et al. 2005) and grazing collisions (Brügmann, 1999). Another milestone in the evolution of Binary Black Hole simulations was the emerging Cactus computational framework¹ that enabled sharing numerical-relativity codes and analysis tools among many research groups. Modern techniques such as Adaptive Mesh Refinement (Carpet driver²) Finite Difference (Brügmann 1999), the parallel adaptive mesh refinement community toolkit Paramesh³ (MacNeice et al. 2000) and Multidomain Spectral methods (Pfeiffer et al. 2003) further enhanced the computational infrastructure for Binary Black Hole applications. New slicing and shift conditions continuously increased the duration of the simulations up to $\sim 30M$ which was still not enough for obtaining a waveform through all the important stages of inspiral, plunge, merger and ringdown.

The Lazarus project was an approach to combine the simulations with results from Black Hole perturbation theory to produce a hybrid model for the merger (Baker et al. 2000). Brügmann et al. managed for the first time in late 2003 to simulate a complete orbit of $\sim 100M$. But unfortunately they were not able to extract gravitational waves. So by 2004 there was much disappointment and frustration, which was about to change in a decisive way in early 2005 when Pretorius presented the first successful simulation through all stages. Baker and Campanelli discovered the new method of Moving Punctures and continued the achievements in 2006, a year in which a lot of things happened for the first time. The first simulations of unequal-mass Black Holes including the recoil of the remnant Black Hole, the first coalescence of spinning Black Holes, the first long waveforms around 7 orbits (Baker et al. 2007), the first comparison of Numerical Relativity simulations with Post-Newtonian approximations (Buonanno et al. 2007) and the first discovery of "superkicks" (recoil velocities of more than 1000 km/s) by Gonzales et al. Already in 2008, mass ratios up to 10 were accomplished and by 2009 precession was included. Spectral Numerical methods began to emerge, in particular the Spectral Einstein Code (SpEC) was developed, solving hyperbolic and elliptic Partial Differential Equations (PDEs) on multiple domains.

Further reading: [CB10].

¹<http://www.cactuscode.org> (23.2.2017)

²<http://www.carpetcode.org> (23.2.2017)

³<https://sourceforge.net/projects/paramesh> (23.2.2017)

5.2 3+1 Decomposition

Einstein's achievement of his elegant theory of General Relativity was to merge space and time into a four-dimensional spacetime. Unfortunately it is not only our intuition struggling with this unification. When one wants to model dynamical physical processes of gravitational interactions such as Binary Black Hole coalescence, an initial value (Cauchy) problem needs to be solved. This requires the reverse decomposition of the four-dimensional spacetime into slices of three-dimensional space that evolve (along a normal vector) in one-dimensional time. The 3+1 decomposition (or "foliation") of spacetime is the only way that Einstein's field equations can be numerically tackled by computers. It is the result of profound groundwork in numerics and differential geometry and (as described in the previous section) it took a long time until convergence and stability was achieved to a gradually satisfying extent. Mainly three steps are necessary for a successful simulation. Firstly, a formulation in terms of constraint and evolution equations has to be elaborated, secondly appropriate gauge (or slicing) conditions have to be found and last but not least, the art and science of constructing appropriate Initial Data is an important issue. In the next sections, following the textbook of Baumgarte and Shapiro [BS10], the fundamental aspects of these steps are reviewed.

5.2.1 Maxwell's equations

There is a fruitful analogy between electromagnetism (Special Relativity) and gravity (General Relativity) that can be exploited to gain intuition into the idea of the decomposition. Maxwell's equation can be grouped into two categories: i) constraint equations that have to be satisfied not only initially but at each instant of time ii) equations that describe the evolution of the electromagnetic fields in time and preserve the constraints.

The constraints can be formulated covariantly⁴

$$\mathcal{C}_E = \partial_i E^i - 4\pi\rho = 0, \quad (5.2.1)$$

$$\mathcal{C}_B = \partial_i B^i = 0, \quad (5.2.2)$$

where E^i and B^i are the three spatial components of the electric and magnetic field and ρ is the static charge density.

The evolution is governed by

$$\partial_t E_i = \epsilon_{ijk} \partial^j B^k - 4\pi j_i, \quad (5.2.3)$$

$$\partial_t B_i = -\epsilon_{ijk} \partial^j E^k, \quad (5.2.4)$$

depending on the dynamic current density j^i .

By using the four-potential $A^\mu = (\phi, A^i)$ and with

$$B_i = \epsilon_{ijk} \partial^j A^k, \quad (5.2.5)$$

the evolution equations can be rewritten in a form that is closer to the form that will be derived later for the decomposition of Einstein's field equations

$$\partial_t A_i = -E_i - \partial_i \phi, \quad (5.2.6)$$

$$\partial_t E_i = \partial_i \partial^j A_j - \partial^j \partial_j A_i - 4\pi j_i. \quad (5.2.7)$$

The constraints, if initially satisfied, are preserved by the evolution

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathcal{C}_E = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathcal{C}_B = 0 \quad (5.2.8)$$

and the initial value problem in electrodynamics can now be solved by evolving initial data (A_i, E_i) according to the sources (ρ, j^i) . Still there is the necessity of choosing an appropriate gauge condition for the potentials, eliminating the gauge freedom

$$\tilde{\phi} = \phi - \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial t}, \quad (5.2.9)$$

$$\tilde{A}_i = A_i + \partial_i \Lambda. \quad (5.2.10)$$

⁴It turns out that the partial derivative ∂_i can even be generalized to the covariant derivative D_i .

The transverse radiation (Coulomb) gauge chooses the divergence (or longitudinal part) of A_i to vanish

$$\partial_i A^i = 0, \quad (5.2.11)$$

leading to a simple inhomogeneous wave equation

$$\square A_i = -\partial_t^2 A_i + \partial^j \partial_j A_i = -4\pi j_i + \partial_i(\partial_t \phi). \quad (5.2.12)$$

The gravitational case (the decomposition of Einstein's equations) shares many features with the electromagnetic one (the decomposition of Maxwell's equations): constraint and evolution equations, gauge conditions and wave equations that will be introduced below.

5.2.2 Foliations of spacetime

The 10 independent components of Einstein's field equations can be split into 4 constraint equations

$$G^{a0} = 8\pi T^{a0} \quad (5.2.13)$$

and 6 evolution equations

$$G^{ij} = 8\pi T^{ij} \quad (5.2.14)$$

As before, the constraints, if initially satisfied, are preserved by the evolution. For the general relativistic Cauchy problem, one now needs to construct the spacial metric describing the gravitational field at a particular moment of time and the extrinsic curvature describing its time evolution.

Figure 5.1: Foliations Σ of the spacetime M along the normal vector n^a that is orthogonal to the spatial hypersurfaces of constant time [BS10].

5.2.3 Spacial metric and extrinsic curvature

Having the constraint equations (5.2.13) and evolution equations (5.2.14) at hand, the problem can be solved by computing the spacial metric (first fundamental form)

$$\gamma_{ab} = g_{ab} + n_a n_b \quad (5.2.15)$$

and the extrinsic curvature (second fundamental form)

$$K_{ab} = -\gamma_a^c \gamma_b^d \nabla_c n_d = -\frac{1}{2} \mathcal{L}_n \gamma_{ab} \quad (5.2.16)$$

where \mathcal{L}_n is the Lie derivative⁵ along n^a .

The extrinsic curvature describes how the spacial metric changes along the normal vector directing the time evolution.

⁵Recall that the Lie derivative of a tensor field measures the difference of change along a vector field compared to a mere coordinate transformation.

Figure 5.2: The extrinsic curvature K^{ab} of the spatial metric hypersurface measuring the change in time as it warps in the embedding space along the normal vector n^a [BS10].

Extrinsic vs. intrinsic curvature

The geometric interpretation of the spatial metric and extrinsic curvature can be illustrated reducing by one dimension. Imagine a flat piece of paper (2D) representing the spatial metric with a triangle drawn on it. As a texture, it can be projected on the surface of a (3D) cylinder or sphere (see figure 5.3). The texture itself is flat having neither intrinsic nor extrinsic curvature. Covering the cylinder, the angles within the triangle still sum up to 180 degrees, there is still no intrinsic curvature. On the surface of the sphere however, the angles within the triangle exceed 180 degrees, the texture has gained intrinsic curvature. Without intrinsic curvature, parallel lines would stay parallel on the hypersurface (the texture) embedded in (3D) space, as opposed to on the sphere where they would converge and meet each other at some point. Anyhow, in both cases, on the (2D) surface of the cylinder and the sphere, the texture has acquired extrinsic curvature being curved in the embedding (3D) space. Like the (2D) texture can be curved in (3D) space transcending into the next dimension, the (3D) spatial metric solution of Einstein's field equations can be curved in (4D) spacetime.

Further reading: [Mas14].

Figure 5.3: A triangle texture projected on a cylinder or sphere.

5.2.4 Lapse and Shift

The freedom to choose coordinates manifests itself in two parameters that enter proper distances on the spatial metric hypersurfaces: the lapse scalar and shift vector. Evolving along the normal vector, proper time changes scaled by the lapse α

$$\delta\tau = \alpha\delta t \quad (5.2.17)$$

and the congruence along the time evolution is given in terms of the shift β

$$t^a = \alpha n^a + \beta^a \quad (5.2.18)$$

yielding the line element

$$ds^2 = -\alpha^2 dt^2 + \gamma_{ij}(dx^i + \beta^i dt)(dx^j + \beta^j dt). \quad (5.2.19)$$

Figure 5.4: Lapse scalar α and shift vector β describing how time t and space x^i is evolved along the normal vector \mathbf{n} [Hug09].

5.3 ADM formulation

Having introduced the 3+1 decomposition of spacetime captured by the constraint and evolution equations, the spatial metric g_{ab} , extrinsic curvature K_{ab} , the lapse α and the shift β , solving the Cauchy problem of general relativity still requires one last step: computing the time derivatives $\partial_t \gamma_{ij}$ and $\partial_t K_{ij}$ that can then be numerically integrated.

The trace of extrinsic curvature, often called mean curvature, is given by

$$K = g^{ab} K_{ab} = \gamma^{ab} K_{ab} \quad (5.3.1)$$

measuring the spatial expansion of normal observers as they move in time.

The constraint equations (5.2.13) can now be rewritten in terms of the extrinsic curvature K_{ij} and mean curvature K , split into an Hamiltonian (energy) constraint

$$R + K^2 - K_{ij} K^{ij} = 16\pi\rho \quad (5.3.2)$$

and momentum constraint

$$D_j(K^{ij} - \gamma^{ij} K) = 8\pi S^i. \quad (5.3.3)$$

where D_j is the covariant derivative⁶, ρ is the matter density and S^i the momentum density.

Finally the evolution equation for the spacial metric can be evaluated using the shift vector β_i arising from the Lie derivative

$$\partial_t \gamma_{ij} = -2\alpha K_{ij} + D_i \beta_j + D_j \beta_i \quad (5.3.4)$$

and the evolution equation for extrinsic curvature

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t K_{ij} = & -D_i D_j \alpha + \alpha (R_{ij} - 2K_{ik} K^k_j + K K_{ij}) \\ & - 8\pi \alpha (S_{ij} - \frac{1}{2} \gamma_{ij} (S - \rho)) \\ & + \beta^k D_k K_{ij} + K_{ik} D_j \beta^k + K_{kj} D_i \beta^k \end{aligned} \quad (5.3.5)$$

contains both the lapse scalar α and the shift vector β_i along with the matter source terms

$$\rho = n_a n_b T^{ab}, \quad (5.3.6)$$

$$S = \gamma^{ij} S_{ij}. \quad (5.3.7)$$

⁶Recall that the covariant derivative of an arbitrary tensor is still a tensor and it measures the change of the tensor with respect to parallel transport.

The constraint and evolution equations are still equivalent to Einstein's field equations and the previously presented "Standard 3+1 Decomposition" is also referred to as ADM formalism being (in a slightly different form) the historically first decomposition found [ADM59] by Arnowitt, Deser and Misner in 1959. Comparing with the decomposition of Maxwell's equations, one can identify the shift vector with the scalar potential ϕ , the spatial metric g_{ab} with the vector potential A^i , the extrinsic curvature K_{ab} with the electric field E^i and the matter source terms ρ, S^i with the charge source terms ρ, j^i . Nonetheless there is an important difference between the two theories: Maxwell's electromagnetic equations are linear vector equations (vector field theory) whereas Einstein's gravitational equations are nonlinear tensor equations (tensor field theory).

Using the ADM formulation, even simple astrophysical applications like the propagation of linear Gravitational Waves in vacuum lead to growing instabilities causing the code to crash early. This can be traced back to mathematical properties of the evolution equations that suffer from the same problems as ungauged Maxwell electromagnetic evolution equations. Lacking hyperbolicity, the solutions can grow out of bounds. The problem is defined to be "well-posed" if the solutions cannot increase faster than exponentially which is still not desirable. It turns out that well-posedness is a necessary but not a sufficient condition for a stable numerical treatment. In a symmetric hyperbolic form, the evolution equations are automatically strongly hyperbolic and thereby well-posed. Weak hyperbolicity (with the matrices not having a complete set of eigenvectors) implies ill-posedness. To achieve hyperbolicity, the equations have to be reduced to first-order by introducing special gauge choices leading to wave equations or auxiliary variables that in turn contain first derivatives of the original variables.

5.4 BSSN equations

The BSSN formulation is widely used today. It was introduced first [SN95] in 1995 by Shibata and Nakamura and recast [BS98] by Baumgarte and Shapiro in 1998 fixing the ADM equations with respect to stability (hyperbolicity). By constructing auxiliary variables to reduce the evolution equations to containing only first-order derivatives one obtains wave-equations that are proven not only to be hyperbolic but with existing and unique solutions [RZ13]. With suitable boundary conditions the waves can "propagate the errors away".

Considering again, as an illustrative example, Maxwell's evolution equations

$$\partial_t A_i = -E_i - \partial_i \phi, \quad (5.4.1)$$

$$\partial_t E_i = \partial_i \partial^j A_j - \partial^j \partial_j A_i - 4\pi j_i \quad (5.4.2)$$

with the constraint equations

$$\mathcal{C}_E = \partial_i E^i - 4\pi \rho = 0, \quad (5.4.3)$$

$$\mathcal{C}_B = \partial_i B^i = 0 \quad (5.4.4)$$

that are preserved, i.e. $\partial_t \mathcal{C} = 0$. If one introduces, as new auxiliary variable, the divergence of the potential

$$\Gamma = \partial_i A^i \quad (5.4.5)$$

and computes its evolution equation by inserting the former evolution equations

$$\partial_t \Gamma = \partial_t \partial^i A_i = \partial^i \partial_t A_i = -\partial^i E_i - \partial_i \partial^i \Phi = -\partial_i \partial^i \Phi - 4\pi \rho \quad (5.4.6)$$

the constraints are no longer preserved, instead the constraint violations satisfy the wave equation

$$\square \mathcal{C} = (-\partial_t^2 + \partial^i \partial_i) \mathcal{C} = 0, \quad (5.4.7)$$

leading to stability (wavelike constraint violation / error propagation).

Returning to General Relativity and Einstein's equations and applying a conformal⁷ transformation to the spacial metric

⁷A conformal mapping preserves the angles locally.

$$\bar{\gamma}_{ij} = e^{-4\Phi} \gamma_{ij} \quad (5.4.8)$$

the auxiliary variable Γ can play the role of a "conformal connection function"

$$\bar{\Gamma}^i = -\partial_j \bar{\gamma}^{ij} \quad (5.4.9)$$

that absorbs second time derivatives in its first derivatives.

The extrinsic curvature is then decomposed into its trace and traceless parts that are conformally transformed along with the spacial metric

$$K_{ij} = e^{4\phi} \tilde{A}_{ij} + \frac{1}{3} \gamma_{ij} K. \quad (5.4.10)$$

This way the Hamiltonian and momentum constraint particularly become functions of the conformal factor ϕ and the sources ρ and S^i

$$0 = \mathcal{H} = \bar{\gamma}^{ij} \bar{D}_i \bar{D}_j e^\phi - \frac{e^\phi}{8} \bar{R} + \frac{e^{5\phi}}{8} \tilde{A}_{ij} \tilde{A}^{ij} - \frac{e^{5\phi}}{12} K^2 + 2\pi e^{5\phi} \rho \quad (5.4.11)$$

$$0 = \mathcal{M}^i = \bar{D}_j (e^{6\phi} \tilde{A}^{ij}) - \frac{2}{3} e^{6\phi} \bar{D}^i K - 8\pi e^{6\phi} S^i \quad (5.4.12)$$

The evolution equation for the spacial metric splits into

$$\partial_t \phi = -\frac{1}{6} \alpha K + \beta^i \partial_i \phi + \frac{1}{6} \partial_i \beta^i \quad (5.4.13)$$

$$\partial_t \bar{\gamma}_{ij} = -2\alpha \tilde{A}_{ij} + \beta^k \partial_k \bar{\gamma}_{ij} + \bar{\gamma}_{ik} \partial_j \beta^k + \bar{\gamma}_{kj} \partial_i \beta^k - \frac{2}{3} \bar{\gamma}_{ij} \partial_k \beta^k \quad (5.4.14)$$

and the evolution equation for the extrinsic curvature separates as

$$\partial_t K = -\gamma^{ij} D_j D_i \alpha + \alpha (\tilde{A}_{ij} \tilde{A}^{ij} + \frac{1}{3} K^2) + 4\pi \alpha (\rho + S) + \beta^i \partial_i K \quad (5.4.15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t \tilde{A}_{ij} &= e^{-4\phi} \left(-(D_i D_j \alpha)^{TF} + \alpha (R_{ij}^{TF} - 8\pi S_{ij}^{TF}) \right) \\ &\quad + \alpha (K \tilde{A}_{ij} - 2 \tilde{A}_{il} \tilde{A}^l{}_j) \\ &\quad + \beta^k \partial_k \tilde{A}_{ij} + \tilde{A}_{ik} \partial_j \beta^k + \tilde{A}_{kj} \partial_i \beta^k - \frac{2}{3} \tilde{A}_{ij} \partial_k \beta^k \end{aligned} \quad (5.4.16)$$

where the superscript TF means taking only the trace-free part of the tensors.

The BSSN formulation is also called "conformal traceless". It is strongly hyperbolic and the problem is thereby "well-posed" leading in many cases to a stable numerical integration.

5.5 Generalized Harmonic coordinates

The first successful simulation of a Binary Black Hole merger through all stages by Pretorius [Pre05a] used another approach to gain code stability. In the Generalized Harmonic formulation, Einstein's field equations are brought into the form

$$\begin{aligned} g^{\delta\gamma} g_{\alpha\beta, \gamma\delta} + g^{\gamma\delta}{}_{, \beta} g_{\alpha\delta, \gamma} + g^{\gamma\delta}{}_{, \alpha} g_{\beta\delta, \gamma} + 2H_{(\alpha, \beta)} \\ - 2H_\delta \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\delta + 2\Gamma_{\delta\beta}^\gamma \Gamma_{\gamma\alpha}^\delta = -8\pi (2T_{\alpha\beta} - g_{\alpha\beta} T) \end{aligned} \quad (5.5.1)$$

where new gauge source functions

$$\Gamma^a = H^a(t, x^i) \quad (5.5.2)$$

are introduced. Note that the gauge Γ^a is not to be confused with the Christoffel symbols $\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\delta$ that describe the gravitational fields in General Relativity. The lapse α and shift β^i are this way replaced by Γ^a for the choice of coordinates.

The source functions can then be generalized in four dimensions to [Pre05b]

$$H^\mu \equiv \square x^\mu = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}} \partial_\alpha (\sqrt{-g} g^{\alpha\mu}) \quad (5.5.3)$$

with g being the trace of the four dimensional metric $g_{\mu\nu}$.

5.6 Initial Data

Representing Black Holes in numerical spacetimes is a difficult task and has been elaborated for many years, discussing whether a specific approximation is appropriate or not. The essential challenge in numerical simulations is the fact that besides numerical errors (that occur also e.g. in the computation of π), there are phenomenological ones caused by a particular choice of the initial data. Recall that the Cauchy problem of General Relativity consists of evolving some initially constraint spacial slices in time. Besides the requirement that the evolution equations have to preserve the constraints, this means that, like for example in thermodynamics, there has to be some kind of stationary equilibrium [RZ13] at each instant of time governed by the Hamiltonian (energy) constraint

$$R + K^2 - K_{ij}K^{ij} = 16\pi\rho \quad (5.6.1)$$

and momentum constraint

$$D_j(K^{ij} - \gamma^{ij}K) = 8\pi S^i \quad (5.6.2)$$

for the spatial metric γ_{ij} and extrinsic curvature K_{ij} . These are only four conditions and cannot specify all the 12 independent components of γ_{ij} and K_{ij} (symmetric 3×3 matrices). Four of the remaining equations are due to and determined by the coordinate choice, leaving still four that can be associated with gravitational wave degrees of freedom, two for each element of the conjugate pair (g_{ij}, K_{ij}) - the two transverse polarization states h_+ and h_\times . It is intuitively clear that these dynamical degrees of freedom cannot be determined by the static constraints. Waves are described by hyperbolic equations - they constitute the "longitudinal" parts of the gravitational field. Complementarily the "transverse" parts are the gravitational waves that are freely specifiable.

Finding suitable Initial Data for Black Holes is not an easy task and has been subject of frequent discussion and improvement over the last decades. One has to find initial values for the spacial metric γ_{ij} and extrinsic curvature K_{ij} that not only satisfy the constraint equations but notably describe the astrophysical situation in a realistic way and to a high degree of accuracy. In the 1970s, York expanded the early work of Lichnerowicz (1944) in order to find a general procedure for finding solutions of the constraint equations that can serve as Initial Data for the General Relativistic Cauchy problem. The procedure requires solving a coupled elliptic system of four nonlinear field equations. As this is a very difficult challenge, some simplifying assumptions are necessary that, as they reduce generality, have to make sure that the evolution produced is sufficiently insensitive to the particular choice of initial data. To decouple the Hamiltonian from the momentum constraint and solve them individually, the trace of the extrinsic curvature $K = \text{tr}(K_{ij}) = \gamma^{ij}K^{ij}$ can be set to zero

$$K = 0. \quad (5.6.3)$$

The next step on the way of finding solutions that capture multiple Black Holes is the assumption of a "conformally flat" initial slice

$$\gamma_{ij} = \psi^4 \delta_{ij} \quad (5.6.4)$$

where ψ is the conformal factor (chosen to be at a convenient, but arbitrary power) and δ_{ij} is a flat metric. What is then left is to solve a (in most cases nonlinear) equation for the scalar field ψ .

A simple solution for N Black Holes momentarily at rest was found by Brill and Lindquist (1963)

$$\psi = 1 + \sum_i^N \frac{m_i}{2r_i} \quad (5.6.5)$$

where m_i are the individual masses (in the limit of large separation) with their coordinate centers r_i .

The above solution was a first important step, but it still lacks the inclusion of linear and angular momentum of the Black Holes described. So the next step was done by Bowen and York in 1980 by providing initial data for boosted (linear momentum) and spinning (angular momentum) Black Holes.

Further reading: [CB10].

In the case of boosted Black Holes, the conformal factor can be given in terms of the linear momentum p

$$\psi = 1 + \frac{m}{2r} + \frac{p^2}{m^4} \psi^{(2)} + \mathcal{O}(p^4) \quad (5.6.6)$$

with $\psi^{(2)}$ being the second order perturbation of the conformal factor.

In the case of spinning Black Holes, ψ can be given by the angular momentum j

$$\psi = 1 + \frac{m}{2r} + \frac{j^2}{m^4} \psi^{(2)} + \mathcal{O}(j^4) \quad (5.6.7)$$

It turns out that the Bowen-York solution is considered to be not identical to the known Kerr solutions⁸ because it describes initial data only and the initial slices are not likely to correspond to slices of constant time t in Boyer-Lindquist coordinates.

With the evolution formalism and initial data at hand there are still two major problems to tackle in order to manage a successful Binary Black Hole simulation: the treatment of Black Hole singularities and the numerical treatment of the functions (mainly the spatial metric and extrinsic curvature).

5.7 Treatment of singularities

Binary Black hole simulations suffer from the fact that one has to deal with singularities that are causing overflows crashing the code (premature termination). Mainly there are three methods to numerically avoid these singularities. They are presented and discussed in the following.

5.7.1 Singularity avoiding coordinates

The first intuitive strategy would be to use singularity avoiding coordinates. While they may be useful in some special cases of spherical symmetry, they suffer from a lot of problems. Firstly, they are generally not easy to find and in many cases do not bear up the dynamical evolution of the Black Hole spacetime. The second issue is the occurring "grid stretching" that develops along the Black Hole throats still leading to a premature truncation of the simulation. Besides, as the advance of proper time in areas close to the singularity is slowed down, increasingly more time steps have to be computed covering increasingly less space. This may cause an inefficient use of the computational resources. The more realistic the problem becomes (in particular three dimensional Binary Black Hole coalescence with initial eccentricity and extremal mass ratio and spins), the harder it is to find successful singularity avoiding coordinates that enable a long-term stable evolution. Consequently, better strategies have been elaborated for tackling the spacetime singularities.

5.7.2 (Moving) Punctures

A very clever method to avoid encountering the singularities numerically is to first use a conformal transformation of the spacial metric

$$\gamma_{ij} = \psi^4 \bar{\gamma}_{ij} \quad (5.7.1)$$

⁸At least up to now it is difficult and not expected to find a coordinate transformation relating the two [BS10].

and then decompose the conformal factor ψ as a sum or product of a singular analytic and regular numerical term

$$\psi = 1 + \frac{1}{\alpha} + u \quad (5.7.2)$$

in order to absorb the singularities in analytic terms. This way, the singularities remain at fixed coordinate locations, given by the "punctures" in the analytic part. During the simulations, one numerically evolves only the regular part without encountering the singularities. The coordinate pathologies (most importantly the "grid stretching" mentioned above) of the singularity avoiding coordinates are successfully eliminated.

Figure 5.5: Moving puncture treatment of Black Hole singularities. For a single nonspinning Black Hole, the numerical result rapidly asymptotes to an exact form of the Schwarzschild solution called a "trumpet" with a flat end at $r = \infty$ and an infinitely long cylinder of areal radius $r = M/2$ when approaching $r = 0$ [BS10].

5.7.3 Excision

The next, very plausible approach is to simply excise the Black Hole singularity dynamically as the evolution proceeds. The hypothesis of "cosmic censorship", first formulated by Penrose in 1969, states that no "naked" singularities without an event horizon exist. As no information can leave the Black Hole event horizon, one can try to simulate only the exterior and excise the discarded interior. It is usually not possible to locate the event horizon (EH), but only the "apparent" horizon (AH). The latter (AH) forms the boundary of a Black Hole for light at a particular instant of time while the former (EH) is known to be the boundary of a Black Hole for light in the future (depending on slicing). While AHs depend on the slicing, the particular choice of coordinates, EHs are invariant with respect to the gauge.

Figure 5.6: Event horizon ellipsoid (grey) covering the individual apparent horizon spheres (red) contained within the common apparent horizon ellipsoid (green) [Sch13].

Due to a theorem which states that, if an AH exists, it cannot be outside an EH, one can just excise the region inside the AH (sphere or ellipsoid) as shown in figure 5.6. This is important since it is usually not possible to track the EH, but instead to locate the AH. While gridpoints inside the AH can this way simply be ignored in the numerical evolution, many finite differencing schemes cause problems on the boundary, on the AH surface. It may then be more convenient to use spectral methods, described in the next section.

Figure 5.7: Excision method. Black Hole singularities are dynamically removed from the numerical grid [Sch13].

5.8 Numerical Methods

Numerical approximations are very important to deal with astrophysical situations and processes that are far from symmetries simplifying the equations. They also enable a discrete treatment in computer algorithms which is essential for most of the very complex problems that arise in General Relativity applications.

Function Discretization The fundamental approach in numerical methods is to perform a discretization of a continuous set of arbitrary functions, replacing them by a finite set of values

$$f(t) \rightarrow \{f^{(n)}\}, n = 1, \dots, N$$

introducing an adimensional parameter n that is independent of the physical variables or dimensions. This allows for the numerical methods to be used in physical simulations without restricting the treatment to a particular regime.

Finite Elements One possible tool to discretize a function can be implemented by constructing a set of finite domains with volume V_n

$$f^{(n)} = \int_{V_n} f dV$$

and then evaluating the parts of the function as integrals over the individual domains. This is a special case of the Spectral Methods approach presented below.

Finite Differences Another method that is commonly used is to discretize the continuous space or spacetime by a lattice of points (the numerical grid). The values of the functions are then taken on this discrete set of independent variables, for example the time dependence can be expressed as

$$f^{(n)}(t) = f(t_n)$$

The approximation scheme can be regarded as a limiting case of the Finite Elements method with vanishing volumes $V_n \rightarrow 0$ while the set of basis functions $\{f^{(n)}\}$ tend to a set of Dirac delta functions δ_n .

Finite differences are often used in combination with Adaptive Mesh Refinement where the grid resolution is dynamically adopted to the particular need of details. In Binary Black Hole coalescence, for example, the regions around the Black Holes are furnished with a much finer grid.

Spectral Decomposition A very powerful tool that is competing with Finite Differences builds on decomposing the function into a complete set of basis (Eigen) functions and then formulating the series representation

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=1}^N f^{(n)} \phi^{(n)}(x)$$

where the discrete coefficients $f^{(n)}$ do not depend anymore on the independent variable x . Exploiting this useful property one can now compute partial derivatives analytically in terms of the derivatives of the known basis functions $\phi^{(n)}(x)$ as

$$\partial_x f(x) = \sum_{n=1}^N f^{(n)} \partial_x \phi^{(n)}(x) \tag{5.8.1}$$

instead of deriving the function $f(x)$ directly which is often only possible numerically. In Numerical Relativity, calculations of the spatial metric g_{ij} and intrinsic curvature K_{ij} are then much easier to compute because the occurring partial derivatives are this way available analytically.

The crucial advantage of the Spectral Decomposition over Finite Differences is the observation that the numerical error using the former often falls off exponentially with n such that terms of higher order can soon be neglected. In contrast to the latter approach, the numerical error typically decreases only with a small power of the number of gridpoints n .

Further reading: [BPL05].

5.9 Spectral Einstein Code (SpEC)

In the previous sections, two formulations of Einstein’s field equations (ADM, BSSN) were presented along with two types of singularity treatments (Moving Punctures, Excision) and (among others) two important and commonly employed numerical methods (Finite Differences, Spectral Decomposition). All these different approaches still coexist⁹ and it is not just a matter of choosing the best and discarding the others. Different research groups made their individual choices to pursue a track they consider most useful or adequate to the astrophysical problems they try to solve numerically. Nonetheless, comparing the different codes building on different pieces is essential to improve the confidence in the results obtained by the simulations.

Figure 5.8: NR codes. The particular choice of the Spectral Einstein Code (SpEC) is enclosed by the blue line [Sch13].

This work focuses on Binary Black Hole simulations from the Spectral Einstein Code (SpEC) that is using the Generalized Harmonic formulation along with Excision of the singularities and Spectral Decomposition of the functions. This code, while developed to treat Einstein’s field equations, is also applicable to a variety of hyperbolic and elliptic partial differential equations. The code uses parallel linear and nonlinear equation solvers, spherical harmonic transforms, Fast Fourier transforms and the GNU Scientific Library containing mathematical routines for scientific applications. Since 2000, when Kidder et al. introduced the concept of Black Hole evolution by Spectral Methods, more than 100 articles have been published that make use of or improving the SpEC. Apart from Kidder, Scheel and Pfeiffer who remain the principal maintainers of the code, numerous persons and institutes are involved working together in the Simulating eXtreme Spactimes (SXS) collaboration (see next section).

5.9.1 Historical evolution of the SpEC

In 2001, Kidder et al. managed to extend the lifetime of 3D Black Hole Simulations, four years before Pretorius was successfully extracting a Gravitational waveform caused by a Binary Black Hole coalescence through all important stages in 2005. Pfeiffer et al. figured out appropriate Initial Data sets in 2002, followed by dynamical gauge conditions for the Einstein evolution equations found by Lindblom and Scheel in 2003. Excision boundary conditions for the Initial Data were evolved by Cook and Pfeiffer in 2004, before the Generalized Harmonic formulation of the code was done by Lindblom et al. in 2006. Attempts to reduce orbital eccentricity (Pfeiffer et al.) as well as high-accuracy comparisons of the numerical relativity simulations with post-Newtonian expansions (Boyle et al.) were published in 2007. Initial data for Neutron Stars and binaries with extremal spins was evolved comparing pseudospectral and finite difference methods in 2008. The first nonspinning Effective One Body waveforms (see chapter 7 Modeling) were calibrated to the simulations in 2009 by Buonanno et al. This was extended to spinning Binaries in 2010. Precessing Black Holes were the next step to fill the parameterspace with more realistic scenarios (Buonanno et al. in 2011). Unequal-mass binaries with mass ratios up to 6 were simulated by Buchman et al. in 2012. A catalog of 174 Binary Black Hole simulations for Gravitational Wave Astronomy was presented by Mroué et al. in 2013 followed by Inspiral-merger-ringdown waveforms of spinning, precessing black-hole binaries in the effective-one-body formalism (Pan et al. in 2014). In the following year, 2015, a compact binary simulation spanning 350 Gravitational-Wave cycles was accomplished by Szilágyi, approaching the Post-Newtonian regime with Numerical Relativity which was important for the comparisons. Finally, 2016 was the year of the first observation of Gravitational Waves from a Binary Black Hole Merger (GW150914) by the LIGO collaboration where the Spectral Einstein Code (SpEC) was involved.

Further reading: [SpEC].

⁹Although the first historically important ADM formulation is presumably not used anymore in practice.

5.10 SXS collaboration project

Around 60 researchers (Buonanno, Kidder, Pfeiffer, Scheel, Teukolsky, Thorne et al.) from 7 institutions (Caltech, Cornell, Fullerton, CITA, AEI, Oberlin College and Washington State University) have joined a collaboration that is funded by the National Science Foundation (NSF) and the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA). The major aim is to publicly provide a catalog of gravitational waveform templates that can be used in data-analysis and for the construction of reduced or analytic models (see chapter 7 Modeling).

SXS Gravitational Waveform Database

Completed Simulations

[Important Information](#)

[Latest News and Updates](#)

[Help and Documentation](#)

Click to [subscribe](#) (or [unsubscribe](#)) to the waveform announcement mailing list.
 For general questions about the Catalog, please send an email to questions@black-holes.org.
 For questions about a specific simulation, please click the email icon in the table below.

Filters
Filter Value Delete

--Choose a field--
Add column

Last updated: 2016-12-26 Per Page: 25

Id	Data	m ₁ /m ₂	X ₁	X ₂	X _{1X}	X _{1Y}	X _{1Z}	X _{2X}	X _{2Y}	X _{2Z}	Ecc	Mω _{orb}	Orbits	Email
SXS:BBH:0001														
SXS:BBH:0002														
SXS:BBH:0003														

Figure 5.9: SXS Gravitational Waveform Database <https://www.black-holes.org/waveforms/catalog.php> supplemented with the participating institutions and funding organizations [SXS].

5.10.1 SXS Waveform catalog

While the initial release was published [Mro13] in October 2013 comprising 174 waveforms, up to date there are 314 simulations available that can be downloaded via `wget`¹⁰ or directly within the webbrowser. In the last case, one can directly use filters constraining the parameters (mass ratio, spins, eccentricity, orbits etc.). The waveforms are disposable at several resolutions (varying with the individual simulation number) and different extrapolation orders. While all waveforms are extracted at certain fixed extraction radii, they are extrapolated to future null infinity (see figure 2.1) with different extrapolation orders N . The resolution labels Lev1, Lev2, ... are just a relative quantity within one individual simulation and not comparable among simulations with different parameters. The numerical accuracy depends on the resolution (not being affected by precession, but mass ratio and spin magnitudes) whereas the accuracy of extrapolation (to future null infinity) can be evaluated by the comparison of different extrapolation orders. Higher orders tend to yield better results in the inspiral, but worse in the ringdown part of the waveform. Within each simulation at a particular resolution and extrapolation order, the waveform is decomposed into spin-2-weighted spherical harmonics (see chapter 6 Extraction) of multipole indexes l running from 2 to 8 and m between $+l$ and $-l$ including 0. There are huge differences up to a factor of 10^{-7} between certain modes and the dominant $(l, m) = (2, 2)$ mode. If the factor exceeds 10^{-5} , the maintainers of the waveform catalog recommend not to trust the accuracy of the specific mode because it could be just numerical noise.

Apart from a metadata file that contains all the important parameters and descriptions of the simulation, there are 8 files available, explained below.

Further reading: [SXS].

¹⁰<https://www.gnu.org/software/wget/> (24.2.2017)

5.10.2 Data files

From the 8 files that are provided (excluding the metadata), 6 contain actual waveform data while 2 describe the evolution of the orbits, spins and other geometric quantities such as the spacetime curvature along with the tidal and frame-drag field at the Black Hole horizons (treatment in chapter 9 Visualization). With the exception of the metadata.txt, the files are in the Hierarchical Data Format (HDF5) [HDF] with the file extension .h5 and zipped inside.

Metadata.txt

Besides the keywords and papers that describe the particular simulation as well as the email addresses of the researchers involved, in this global file (corresponding to a simulation being valid for all associated files and waveforms in all available resolutions and extrapolation orders) the Initial Data is listed along with some brief results of the characterized simulation in form of relaxed quantities and remnant properties. The reference section is divided into "papers describing the particular run (if any)", "papers describing the evolution code", "papers describing the initial data" and "papers describing eccentricity reduction" - a key topic in gravitational wave modeling. Input Parameters for Initial Data include the initial separation, orbital frequency and acceleration as well as the binary type (BH = Black Hole, NS = Neutron Star), the initial positions and, most importantly, the individual initial masses and spins (in components). The relaxed quantities¹¹ comprise masses, spins, Black Hole centers and orbital frequency at the relaxation time. The relaxed eccentricity is usually very small, meaning that the initial eccentricity has "radiated away" by Gravitational Waves that have "circularized" the orbit. The last group of information in this file belongs to the final Black Hole remnant (in general a rotating Kerr Black Hole) whose mass (scalar), spin and velocity (vector) is stated. The information is important to the treatment of Quasinormal Modes that is elaborated in the second half of this work.

rhOverM_Asymptotic_GeometricUnits.h5

rMPsi4_Asymptotic_GeometricUnits.h5

These two files contain the spin-weighted spherical harmonic components of either the Regge-Wheeler-Zerilli (RWZ) quantity h or the Newman-Penrose (NP) quantity Ψ_4 describing outgoing gravitational radiation. While the first is gauge-invariant (the Gravitational Wave strain or polarization amplitude), the latter depends on the specific tetrad chosen in the NP formalism. The methods for obtaining both are described in the chapter 6 Extraction. The coefficients are given in terms of extrapolated proper time the data file is split into different h5-groups "Extrapolated_Nx.dir" where "x" is the order of the extrapolating polynomial used. Note that the normalization is done multiplying h while dividing Ψ_4 by the total mass M . However both quantities are multiplied by the extraction radius in order to eliminate the radial $1/r$ decrease of the waveform.

rhOverM_Asymptotic_GeometricUnits_CoM.h5

rMPsi4_Asymptotic_GeometricUnits_CoM.h5

Here the suffix "_CoM" is added to account for the fact that the Center of Mass (CoM) has been corrected by a method described in [arxiv:1509.00862]. Apart from this correction, the files formally contain the same spin-weighted spherical-harmonic coefficients and all facts stated for the previous two are still valid.

rh_FiniteRadii_CodeUnits.h5

rPsi4_FiniteRadii_CodeUnits.h5

These two files contain raw output from SpEC simulations in which the quantities h and Ψ_4 are extracted at various finite radii with h5-groups labeled "Rxxxx.dir", where "xxxx" is the coordinate radius rounded to the nearest integer. The functions are given in code units instead of retarded time per total mass t/M .

Horizons.h5

HorizonsDump.h5

The last two files do not deal with the waveforms, but include information on the Black Holes's Apparent Horizons (AH) in hdf-groups denoted as AhA.dir and AhB.dir where each dataset roughly contains the center of mass and spin of the individual Black Hole (in code units). The latter file includes the Ricci scalar as well as the Horizon tendicity and vorticity (described in chapter 9 Visualization).

Further reading: [SXS].

¹¹Relaxation means as usual that the system has reached an equilibrium state in which, in this case, the initial data has relaxed to a stable state after a certain amount of "junk radiation" has been released (see chapter 6 Extraction).

5.11 SXS Parameterspace (own results)

In the following, the parameterspace of the SXS waveform catalog is explored. It spans the set of all possible combinations of all the different (Initial Data) parameters and can be represented as a multidimensional continuous space that can be plotted in a coordinate system with the axes scaling the parameter variables. In this case, the SXS parameterspace is 7 dimensional if the mass ratio $q = m_1/m_2$ and the 6 components $\{\chi_{1x}, \chi_{1y}, \chi_{1z}, \chi_{2x}, \chi_{2y}, \chi_{2z}\}$ of the two spin vectors χ_1 and χ_2 of the individual Black Holes. In the broader sense, eccentricity e , orbital frequency $M\omega_{\text{orb}}$ and the number of orbits simulated N_{orb} can be added. However, as eccentricity is radiated away by Gravitational Waves and the orbital frequency is determined by the initial data and included in the waveform being half the Gravitational Wave frequency, they are no real additional independent parameters that enter the waveform formula. The number of orbits simulated simply sets up the range (length) of the waveform. The more cycles one can manage to compute before merger, the better it can be matched to the Post-Newtonian waveform expressions.

5.11.1 Initial Data

The first subject that will be investigated here, is the parameterspace reduced to 3 and 2 dimensions by including just the magnitudes of the spin vectors $\chi_1 = |\chi_1|$ and $\chi_2 = |\chi_2|$ and the mass ratio $q = m_1/m_2$. Figure 5.10 shows the 3D parameterspace above with the mass ratio q represented by the z -axis and the spin magnitudes χ_1 and χ_2 scaling the x and y -axis. There is a number of 65 nonspinning simulations with $\chi_1 = \chi_2 = 0$ that can be identified as the high pile in front of the plot. The rest of the data points, each representing a particular simulation included in the waveform catalog, are distributed in a sparse manner. It seems to be somehow chaotic, but instead the particular parameterpoints available are motivated by the feasibility of the simulation's Initial Data and certain requests by the research community that aims at building analytical models fitted to or tuned by the numerical data (see chapter 7 Modeling). The fact that the population of the parameterspace is not only discrete, but even meager, is the main driving force for building surrogate analytical models. Looking on the 2D projection of the 3D parameterspace in figure 5.10 below where the mass ratio q is faded out, one finds the pile of the nonspinning simulations being one single data point at the origin where $\chi_1 = \chi_2 = 0$. There are some points on the x - and y -axis that represent simulations where only one of the individual Black Hole spins χ_i is zero and the bisecting line which shows parameter points where the situation is symmetric, meaning that both Black Holes have the same spin $\chi_1 = \chi_2$. Recall that the dimensionless spin magnitudes χ vary only between 0 and 1, being normalized to the total mass that cannot be exceeded due to causality considerations (see chapter 2 Basics).

5.11.2 Frequency and Orbits

The next quantities to examine when exploring the SXS parameterspace are the orbital frequency and the number of orbits simulated. Figure 5.11 shows bar charts of the orbital frequency and the number of orbits simulated plotted over the simulation number $BBHnr$. The orbital frequency $M\omega_{\text{orb}}$ varies between 0.01 and 0.03 constraining the Gravitational Wave frequency to twice these values. On the right edge of the plot, one can see a void between the $BBHnr$ 309 and 316 which is due to unavailability of these simulations at the time of this investigation. The number of orbits simulated $\#orbits$ varies between 6.5 and 88.4 showing that also fractions are possible. It is plausible that with the number of orbits simulated, the simulation is consuming more time and computational resources, so that very long simulations including more than 30 orbits are not performed a lot. With increasing mass ratio q , the Binary Black Hole inspiral takes longer thus a high number of orbits is needed especially for Extreme Mass Ratio Binary Inspirals (EMRIs) that will be characterized in chapter 7 Modeling.

5.11.3 Eccentricity and Precession

Figure 5.12 above shows bar charts of the initial eccentricity e of the SXS simulations. The major part, 243 of the 314 available simulations, starts with eccentricities below 0.001. The total range of the eccentricity is bounded by the minimum of 10^{-5} and the maximum of 10^3 . The more eccentric the Initial Data of the simulation, the more difficult it is to construct an analytical model due to a lack of phase accuracy. Besides eccentricity, most of the astrophysically realistic and relevant Binary Black Hole systems are expected to exhibit spin precession that astonishingly already can be included in the simulations. The parameterspace consisting of the 314 disposable simulations is thus divided into 141 nonprecessing and the major part of 173 precessing simulations (figure 5.12 below). The spin precession, including nutation effects and the resulting modulation on the waveform will be examined at the end of this chapter.

Figure 5.10: SXS parameterspace: Initial Data in 3D (above) including mass ratio ν and 2D (below) with just the individual spins χ_1 and χ_2 .

Figure 5.11: SXS parameterspace: Orbital frequency (left) and number of orbits simulated (right).

Figure 5.12: SXS parameterspace: Initial eccentricity (left) fraction of simulations with precessing Binaries (right).

5.11.4 Waveforms

Having discussed the Initial Data parameterspace of the SXS simulations, this section will deal with the waveforms extracted from these simulations, expected to be produced by the Binary Black Hole coalescence. As stated above, the waveforms are extracted at certain fixed extraction radii r and extrapolated to future null infinity (with different extrapolation orders N). The data is available in the form of either the Regge-Wheeler-Zerilli (RWZ) quantity h or the Newman-Penrose (NP) quantity Ψ_4 (see chapter 6 Extraction) and can be downloaded as the datasets `rhOverM_Asymptotic_GeometricUnits.h5`, `rMPsi4_Asymptotic_GeometricUnits.h5`, `rhOverM_Asymptotic_GeometricUnits_CoM.h5`, `rMPsi4_Asymptotic_GeometricUnits_CoM.h5`, `rh_FiniteRadii_CodeUnits.h5` and `rPsi4_FiniteRadii_CodeUnits.h5` that are explained in section 5.10.

Figure 5.13: The first release of 174 SXS waveforms [Mro13]. This is an overview showing some of the most prominent waveforms where precession is already included in 92 simulations e.g. BBH 50 (5th row middle, marked red). On the y -axis the Gravitational Wave strain is plotted in Geometric Units while the time axis is scaled by a multiple of the Binary total mass $1000M$ ($= 0.1s$ for $M = 20M_{\odot}$).

Figure 5.13 shows an overview of some of the most important waveforms of the first release of the SXS waveform catalog, published in [Mro13]. The waveforms were predestined to serve as templates in Gravitational Wave Data Analysis pipelines that led to the first direct discovery of Gravitational Waves from Binary Black Hole systems by LIGO in 2016 [cite]. The waveform templates are especially utile and necessary for parameter estimation using Markov Chain Monte Carlo algorithms. Prior to the SXS catalog, other world-wide projects such as the Numerical INjection Analysis (NINJA) [Aji12] and Numerical Relativity Analytical Relativity (NRAR) [Hin13] collaboration had been established. Purpose of the former (NINJA) was to "study the sensitivity of existing gravitational-wave search and parameter-estimation algorithms using numerically generated waveforms" while intensifying the cooperation between the numerical-relativity and data-analysis communities. Concentrating on only the dominant $(l, m) = (2, 2)$ mode, real detector data was compared (convolution) to "hybrid" templates that combined early Post-Newtonian inspiral with late inspiral, merger and ringdown waveforms matching the two parts minimizing their phase difference. The latter (NRAR) was a "joint effort between members of the numerical relativity, analytical relativity and gravitational-wave data analysis communities" with the aim of using numerical relativity simulations to construct increasingly accurate analytical waveform expressions for the LIGO/Virgo collaboration. Though this attempt was restricted to nonprecessing Binary Black Hole systems, it was an important step towards Gravitational Wave modeling (see section Modeling). The analytical waveforms were calibrated to some of the simulations and then checked with others in order to find very good overlaps above 99 % (for mass ratios below 6 even beyond 99.7 %). Nonetheless, the NINJA collaboration handled only 40 waveforms with an average length of about 9 orbits while the NRAR collaboration published 25 waveforms at an average already around 13 orbits being more accurate than the NINJA templates. The tremendous advance of the SXS catalog [Mro13] was to extent both the length of the waveforms up to 35 and the parameterspace coverage up to 174 (in the first release). Moreover, the eccentricity could be reduced to less than 10^{-5} . As stated above, the first SXS release already included 92 precessing simulations. Post-Newtonian (PN) theory is able to make predictions on the precession of the spin and orbital angular momenta that can be compared to the numerical results. Therefore it is important to have long waveforms covering a large scope of the parameterspace enabling a comprehensive comparison.

5.11.5 Orbits

The files `Horizons.h5` included in each simulation data of the SXS catalog contain information on the center of mass and spin of the individual Black Holes (data groups `AhA.dir` and `AhB.dir`) as well as those of a common Apparent Horizon (data groups `AhC.dir`). The orbital trajectories are saved in the dataset `CoordCenterInertial.dat` in the format $(t, x(t), y(t), z(t))$ and can be investigated together with the waveforms.

Figure 5.14: Orbital evolution of the individual Black Holes (red and blue) of the simulation BBH1 extracted from the datasets `AhA.dir` and `AhB.dir` of the file `Horizon.h5` available in the SXS catalog [SXS]. During the inspiral the trajectories almost perfectly lie in the $x - y$ plane, apart from tiny oscillations with a modulation due to non negligible precession effects, see plot on the right. After the merger there is a slight kick causing the Black Holes to leave the plane.

Figure 5.15: Orbital decay of BBH1. The orbit is highly circular such that the decay in x and y (blue oscillation) is just phase shifted by $\pi/2$ while the magnitude of both decays as $(t_{\text{coal}} - t)^{1/4}$ (red envelope).

Kicks

The orbital decay apparent in figure 5.15 is caused by the loss of energy and angular momentum carried away by the Gravitational Waves emitted from the Binary Black Hole coalescence. It turns out that also linear momentum can be radiated. Studies have shown that this can lead to a recoil or "kick" due to the asymmetry between the $(l = 2, m = +2)$ and $(l = 2, m = -2)$ of the waveform (Ψ_4 or h) increasing with the spin of the Black Holes. Since Campanelli et al. (2007), numerous simulations showed that there can be "superkicks" for extremal spin configurations with recoil speeds up to

$$v_{\text{kick}} = \mathcal{O}(1000)\text{km/s} \quad (5.11.1)$$

that are expected to be able to eject the remnant Black Hole out of the host galaxy. Owen et al. were later able to provide an geometric interpretation of the process by associating it with effects of whirling spacetime [Owe11] (see section Visualization).

Further reading: [Hug09, CB10].

5.11.6 Spin

Apart from the orbital trajectories saved in `CoordCenterInertial.dat`, the data groups `AhA.dir`, `AhB.dir` and `AhC.dir` in the `Horizons.h5` file also include information on the Black Hole spins $\chi_{A,B,C} = S_{A,B,C}/M^2$, saved in the dataset `chiInertial.dat`. The data is provided in the format $(t, \chi_x, \chi_y, \chi_z)$ with the Cartesian components $S_{x,y,z}$ of the spin angular momentum measured in the inertial frame. Figure 5.16 shows the time evolution of the orbits (left) of the two Black Holes (red and blue) in the simulation BBH1 together with the corresponding spins (right). Figure 5.17 illustrates the effects of precession (left) and nutation (right) on the spin trajectories that will be discussed again in the next section together with the resulting modulation in the waveform.

Figure 5.16: SXS horizon data: Time evolution of the orbits of two Black Holes (red and blue) for an equal-mass non-spinning Binary (left) and the corresponding spins (right) including numerical artifacts at the end.

Figure 5.17: SXS horizon data: Increasing precession (left) and nutation (right) of a spinning Black Hole Binary.

Spin flips

A coalescence of initially nonspinning Black Holes produces a spinning remnant (Kerr Black Hole) whose spin direction \mathbf{S} is aligned with the orbital angular momentum \mathbf{L} of the binary. However if the individual Black Holes are spinning the directions may differ significantly. This effect, the "spin flip", already occurs when the Black Hole spins are at first antialigned with \mathbf{L} and can be even amplified in generic spin configurations. Figure 5.18 illustrates the phenomenon for the precessing binary BBH165.

[CB10]

Figure 5.18: SXS orbit and spin of the precessing system BBH165. The spin flips its direction completely during the time evolution causing the remnant spin \mathbf{S} to be inclined with respect to the total orbital angular momentum \mathbf{L} .

5.11.7 Precession

Apart from the spin flip, precession of the individual Black Holes may have other observable effects. Precession was first proposed [Apo94] by Apostolatos, Cutler, Sussman, and Thorne in 1994 and has ever since been successfully included in numerical and analytical models (see section Modeling).

Figure 5.19 shows the configurations of a binary system that is in general precession. This is the case when the orbital angular momentum (blue vector) is not parallel to the total angular momentum (gray vector) of the system that is usually perpendicular to a fixed plane in the coordinate system (gray grid). As it is well known, precession means that the tip of the orbital angular momentum moves on the surface of a cone. Furthermore, the individual spins can precess with respect to the orbital plane.

Nutation is a phenomenon that appears as oscillation of the tip of the (orbital or spin) angular momentum around the surface of the cone (described above). In the SXS Binary Black Hole simulations it can also be observed when examining the `chiInertial.dat` dataset in the `Ah(A,B,C).dir` data group of the `Horizon.h5` file. In figure 5.20 one can see the time evolution of the spin components χ_x , χ_y and χ_z of one of the individual Black Holes which are oscillating around the orbital plane ($\chi = 0$). The nutation is here visible as tiny fluctuations superposed on the curves (trembling).

Most importantly, precession can be observed as amplitude modulation of the Gravitational Wave signal as shown in figure 5.20. This was already proposed by Apostolatos et al. in their groundbreaking paper [Apo94] published in 1994, see figure 5.21.

Figure 5.19: Precessing Binary Black Hole system with the orbital plane (turquoise) perpendicular to the orbital angular momentum (blue vector) not lying in the plane (grey grid) perpendicular to the total angular momentum (gray vector). The spin angular momentum (red vectors) of the individual Black Holes (black spheres) can also precess with respect to the direction perpendicular to the orbital plane [ctc].

Figure 5.20: SXS horizon and waveform data: Precession and nutation (left) and the resulting modulation on the waveform (right).

Figure 5.21: Amplitude modulation of the waveform first proposed by Apostolatos et al. in 1994 [Apo94] (figure simplified).

Chapter 6

Extraction

Tullio Regge, John Wheeler and Frank Zerilli who piecewise discovered a waveform decomposition formalism [Alc, SH, MP].

Having discussed Numerical Relativity and the simulation of Binary Black Hole coalescence, it is now due to deal with a topic that is most important at the interface of Numerical Relativity and Gravitational Waves Data Analysis. The extraction of waveforms from the simulations is a vital and crucial step in the theoretical process. As predicting the Gravitational Wave strain signal is one of the major motivations behind the Binary Black Hole simulations, the accurate calculation of the waveforms is essential and needs closer attention.

Gravitational Waves connect the near-zone of the Black Holes with the asymptotic far-zone through spacetime. The difficulty arises due to the fact that while the waves are strong and nonlinear in the near-zone where they are extracted, an extrapolation has to be done in order to find the asymptotic signal that is expected to be measured by the detector far away from the source. Since Gravitational Waves travel at the speed of light, they must be extracted at future null infinity, the asymptotic causally connected lightlike spacetime-region (see figure 2.1). In the far-zone, the Gravitational Wave perturbation of the spacetime is weak and can be linearly approximated expressing the wave information in terms of the two polarization amplitudes in the transverse-traceless (TT) gauge. However, in the strong-field near-zone it is necessary to model the waves as spacetime perturbations of a background metric that, in the case of Black Holes, can either be Schwarzschild or Kerr. The question is now how to get the gauge-invariant polarization amplitudes from the coordinate dependent spacial metric that is evolved in a simulation.

In this chapter, two main approaches are presented. The gauge-invariant Regge-Wheeler-Zerilli [RW57, Zer70] (or Moncrief) formalism relies on decomposing the spacial metric into (spin-weighted) spherical harmonics while the Newman-Penrose [NP62] formalism employs projections of the Weyl tensor onto null tetrads in order to compute Weyl scalars that are directly related to the waveform (second time derivatives of the polarization amplitudes). Most of the concepts introduced will be picked up in the chapters 8 Perturbation and 9 Visualization where the connection of Gravitational Waves and Quasinormal Modes is investigated.

The whole chapter is based on the textbook of Baumgarte and Shapiro [BS10].

6.1 Regge-Wheeler-Zerilli formalism

The Moncrief (RWZ) formalism is most commonly used when dealing with Gravitational Wave simulations. It is based on a perturbative decomposition of the numerically available spacial metric g_{ab} into the background part g_{ab}^{bg} and a perturbation h_{ab}^{pt}

$$g_{ab} = g_{ab}^{\text{bg}} + h_{ab}^{\text{pt}} \quad (6.1.1)$$

The perturbation can then further be decomposed into even and odd parity contributions

$$h_{ab} = \sum_{l=2}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-l}^l {}^e h_{ab}^{lm} + {}^o h_{ab}^{lm} \quad (6.1.2)$$

where the summation starts with the quadrupolar $l = 2$ contribution.

The parity of the perturbation or waveform refers to the behavior under space inversion where the sign can change or remain depending on the indexes l and m . The concept of parity and the resulting decomposition will be explained in more detail in chapter 8 Perturbation.

At this point it is just important to note that the Gravitational Wave polarizations h_+ and h_\times can be split into

$$h_+(t, r, \theta, \varphi) = {}^e h_+ + {}^o h_+, \quad (6.1.3)$$

$$h_\times(t, r, \theta, \varphi) = {}^e h_\times + {}^o h_\times. \quad (6.1.4)$$

The even-parity (polar or electric) part is then given by

$${}^e h_+ - i {}^e h_\times = \frac{1}{r} \sum_{l=2}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-l}^l \sqrt{\frac{(l+2)!}{(l-2)!}} R_{lm}(t, r) {}_{-2}Y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi) \quad (6.1.5)$$

where the time and radial dependence goes into $R_{lm}(t, r)$ while the angular dependence separates into the spin-weighted spherical harmonics ${}_{-2}Y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi)$ (see chapter 8 Perturbation for an explanation of the spin-weight s). As the angular functions are known universally, one is then left to study the time dependent coefficients that are solutions of the (vacuum) Zerilli equation

$$\partial_t^2 R_{lm} - \partial_{r^*}^2 R_{lm} + {}^e V_l R_{lm} = 0 \quad (6.1.6)$$

The odd-parity (axial or magnetic) part is given by

$${}^o h_+ - i {}^o h_\times = -\frac{i}{r} \sum_{l=2}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-l}^l \sqrt{\frac{(l+2)!}{(l-2)!}} q_{lm}(t, r) {}_{-2}Y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi) \quad (6.1.7)$$

where the coefficients $q_{lm}(t, r)$ containing the time and radial dependence follow from an integration

$$q_{lm} = \int_{-\infty}^t Q_{lm}(t', r) dt' \quad (6.1.8)$$

of the quantity Q_{lm} that is analogously determined by the (vacuum) Regge-Wheeler equation

$$\partial_t^2 Q_{lm} - \partial_{r^*}^2 Q_{lm} + {}^o V_l Q_{lm} = 0 \quad (6.1.9)$$

In both the Regge-Wheeler and Zerilli equation the radial coordinate r is replaced by the tortoise coordinate

$$dr_* = \frac{dr}{\alpha^2} \quad r_* = r + 2M \ln(\alpha^2 r / 2M) \quad (6.1.10)$$

that was explained together with the Eddington-Finkelstein coordinates of the Schwarzschild metric in section Black Holes of chapter 2 Basics.

6.1.1 Energy and angular momentum

It is now possible to compute the change in energy and angular momentum of a source due to gravitational radiation as

$$dE/dt = -\frac{i}{r} \sum_{l=2}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-l}^l \sqrt{\frac{(l+2)!}{(l-2)!}} (|Q_{lm}|^2 + |\dot{R}_{lm}|^2) \quad (6.1.11)$$

and

$$dJ_z/dt = -\frac{i}{16\pi} \sum_{l=2}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-l}^l \sqrt{\frac{(l+2)!}{(l-2)!}} (q_{lm}^* Q_{lm} + R_{lm}^* \dot{R}_{lm}). \quad (6.1.12)$$

6.1.2 Surface projection

Having revealed the time and radial dependence (R_{lm} or Q_{lm}) of the polarization expansion, one is now left with the calculation of the angular part - the spin-weighted spherical harmonics $_{-2}Y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi)$. Gravitational Waves are spherical waves that are most generally described by the Riemann tensor. So in order to obtain full information about the wave in time, radius and angles, the tensor has to be projected onto a sphere to capture the angular dependence or distribution. Projecting a scalar on the surface of a sphere is simple and is for instance applied in Quantum Mechanics when dealing with the hydrogen atom. If vectors have to be projected, already a two dimensional vector basis is needed while the tensor spherical harmonics use basis tensors. All spherical projections of higher rank tensors involve angular derivatives of the scalar spherical harmonics and the two dimensional metric σ_{ab} on the unit sphere S^2

$$\sigma_{ab} dx^a dx^b = d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2 \quad (6.1.13)$$

In the following the spin-weight $s = 0$ scalar, $s = 1$ vector and $s = 2$ tensor spherical harmonics are presented. Higher ranks $s > 2$ are self-evidently possible but not needed in this analysis.

6.1.3 Scalar spherical harmonics

The $s = 0$ scalar spherical harmonics satisfy the equations

$$\sigma_{ab} \nabla_a \nabla_b Y_{lm} = -l(l+1) Y_{lm} \quad (6.1.14)$$

and

$$\partial_\varphi Y_{lm} = im Y_{lm} \quad (6.1.15)$$

and can explicitly be given by

$$Y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi) = \sqrt{\frac{(2l+1)(l-m)!}{4\pi(l+m)!}} P_l^m(\cos \theta) e^{im\varphi} \quad -l \leq m \leq l \quad (6.1.16)$$

Substituting $x = \cos \theta$, the associated Legendre polynomials are given by

$$P_l^m(x) = \frac{(-1)^m}{2^l l!} (1-x^2)^{m/2} \frac{d^{l+m}}{dx^{l+m}} (x^2-1)^l \quad (6.1.17)$$

being a solution of the differential equation

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left[(1-x^2) \frac{d}{dx} P_l^m(x) \right] + \left[l(l+1) - \frac{m^2}{1-x^2} \right] P_l^m(x) = 0 \quad (6.1.18)$$

and obeying the parity relation

$$P_l^m(-x) = (-1)^{l+m} P_l^m(x). \quad (6.1.19)$$

This leads to the parity relation

$$Y_{lm}(\pi - \theta, \pi + \varphi) = (-1)^l Y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi) \quad (6.1.20)$$

and the symmetry¹

$$Y_{l-m}(\theta, \varphi) = (-1)^m Y_{lm}^*(\theta, \varphi) \quad (6.1.21)$$

of the scalar spherical harmonics that are the starting point for the calculation of higher-rank vector or tensor spherical harmonics.

6.1.4 Vector spherical harmonics

The vector spherical harmonics are needed to represent vectors projected onto a sphere where the two basis vectors² are the "electric"

$$E_a^{(lm)} = \nabla_a Y^{(lm)} \quad (6.1.22)$$

with even or polar parity under space inversion and the "magnetic"

$$M_a^{(lm)} = \epsilon_a^b \nabla_b Y^{(lm)} \quad (6.1.23)$$

with odd or axial parity.

Here ϵ_{ab} is the Levi-Civita tensor on S^2 whose only nonvanishing components are

$$\epsilon_{\theta\varphi} = -\epsilon_{\varphi\theta} = \sin\vartheta \quad (6.1.24)$$

The spherical harmonic basis vectors obey the orthogonality relations

$$\int (E_a^{lm}) E_a^{l'm'} d\Omega = l(l+1) \delta_{ll'} \delta_{mm'} \quad (6.1.25)$$

and

$$\int (M_a^{lm}) M_a^{l'm'} d\Omega = l(l+1) \delta_{ll'} \delta_{mm'} \quad (6.1.26)$$

when integrated over the whole 4π space of the solid angle Ω .

6.1.5 Tensor spherical harmonics

While the vector spherical harmonics involved first partial derivatives, the (rank-two) tensor spherical harmonics contain second partial derivatives.

The even, polar or electric part of the basis is given by

$$Z_{ab}^{(lm)} = \nabla_a \nabla_b Y_{lm} \frac{l(l+1)}{2} \sigma_{ab} Y^{(lm)} \quad (6.1.27)$$

whereas the odd, axial or magnetic part can be computed as

¹The operator * denotes the complex conjugate of the function.

²Note that the multipole indexes (lm) are not tensorial indexes.

$$S_{ab}^{lm} = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla_a S_b^{lm} + \nabla_b S_a^{lm}) \quad (6.1.28)$$

In the gravitational case the spin weight $s = -2$ is requested for the description of outgoing radiation (see also chapter Perturbations). This yields

$${}_{-2}Y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi) = \sqrt{\frac{(l-2)!}{(l+2)!}} (W_{lm} - iX_{lm}/\sin\theta) \quad (6.1.29)$$

where

$$X_{lm} = 2\partial_\varphi(\partial_\theta - \cot\theta)Y_{lm} \quad (6.1.30)$$

and

$$W_{lm} = \left(\partial_\theta^2 - \cot\theta\partial_\theta - \frac{1}{\sin^2\theta}\partial_\varphi^2 \right) Y_{lm} \quad (6.1.31)$$

play the role of the basis parts Z_{ab}^{lm} and S_{ab}^{lm} . Another form that is easier to compute

$$X_{lm} = 2im(\partial_\theta Y_{lm} - \cot\theta Y_{lm}) \quad (6.1.32)$$

and

$$W_{lm} = -l(l+1)Y_{lm} - 2\cot\theta\partial_\theta Y_{lm} + 2m^2/\sin^2\theta Y_{lm} \quad (6.1.33)$$

only uses the scalar (spin-weight $s = 0$) spherical harmonics Y_{lm} and their derivative

$$\partial_\theta Y_{lm} = -\sqrt{\frac{2l+1}{4\pi}} \sqrt{\frac{(l-m)!}{(l+m)!}} \left((l+m)(l-m+1)P_l^{m-1}(\cos\theta) + m\cot\theta P_l^m(\cos\theta) \right) \exp(im\phi), \quad (6.1.34)$$

which is also given in terms of the Associated Legendre polynomials $P_l^m(\cos\theta)$. Thus, the spin-weighted spherical harmonics can be computed analytically. However this is not the case for the spin-weighted spheroidal harmonics that are introduced in chapter 8 Perturbation.

Further reading: [BS10].

6.2 Newman-Penrose formalism

Another approach to extract the Gravitational Wave content from the Riemann curvature or spacial metric is a formalism that relies on contracting the Weyl tensor (see also chapter 9 Visualization) with complex null tetrads. The resulting five "Weyl scalars" can then be interpreted as quantities measuring ingoing and outgoing gravitational radiation. Unfortunately there is no unique way to construct these quantities because different choices of the tetrads affect their mathematical values and physical interpretation accounting for the coordinate freedom. So one of the topics arising in the Newman-Penrose formalism is the identification of a suitable null tetrad. In the so-called "quasi-Kinnersley frames", two of the scalars vanish leaving three able to quantify longitudinal and transverse Gravitational Waves. Choosing a spherical coordinate system (t, r, θ, φ) , the complex null tetrads can be constructed in terms of the basis unit vectors $e_{\hat{t}}^a, e_{\hat{r}}^a, e_{\hat{\theta}}^a, e_{\hat{\varphi}}^a$ as

$$\begin{aligned} l^a &= \frac{1}{2}(e_{\hat{t}}^a + e_{\hat{r}}^a), \\ n^a &= \frac{1}{2}(e_{\hat{t}}^a - e_{\hat{r}}^a), \\ m^a &= \frac{1}{2}(e_{\hat{\theta}}^a + ie_{\hat{\varphi}}^a), \\ \bar{m}^a &= \frac{1}{2}(e_{\hat{\theta}}^a - ie_{\hat{\varphi}}^a) \end{aligned} \quad (6.2.1)$$

and the Weyl scalars are calculated as contractions of the Weyl tensor

$$\begin{aligned}
\Psi_0 &= C_{abcd} l^a m^b l^c m^d, \\
\Psi_1 &= C_{abcd} l^a n^b l^c m^d, \\
\Psi_2 &= C_{abcd} l^a m^b m^{*c} n^d, \\
\Psi_3 &= C_{abcd} l^a n^b m^{*c} n^d, \\
\Psi_4 &= C_{abcd} n^a m^{*b} n^c m^{*d}.
\end{aligned} \tag{6.2.2}$$

In the transverse quasi-Kinnersley frames, the odd scalars Ψ_1 and Ψ_3 vanish - leaving the scalars Ψ_0 and Ψ_4 as measures of the ingoing and outgoing gravitational radiation whereas Ψ_2 represents the longitudinal (or "Coulomb") part of the gravitational field. When constructing Gravitational Wave templates one is especially interested in the outgoing radiation, thus the examination of

$$\Psi_4 = C_{abcd} n^a m^{*b} n^c m^{*d} \tag{6.2.3}$$

that includes both Regge-Wheeler-Zerilli polarization states h_+ and h_\times according to

$$\Psi_4 = \ddot{h}_+ - i\ddot{h}_\times \tag{6.2.4}$$

The Weyl scalar Ψ_4 can also be directly computed from the Riemann tensor

$$\Psi_4 = -\frac{1}{4} \left(R_{i\hat{\theta}i\hat{\theta}} - 2iR_{i\hat{\theta}i\hat{\varphi}} - 2R_{i\hat{\theta}\hat{r}\hat{\theta}} + 2iR_{i\hat{\varphi}\hat{r}\hat{\theta}} - R_{i\hat{\varphi}\hat{t}\hat{\varphi}} + R_{\hat{r}\hat{\theta}\hat{r}\hat{\theta}} + 2iR_{i\hat{\theta}\hat{r}\hat{\varphi}} + 2R_{i\hat{\varphi}\hat{r}\hat{\varphi}} - 2iR_{\hat{r}\hat{\varphi}\hat{r}\hat{\theta}} - R_{\hat{r}\hat{\varphi}\hat{r}\hat{\varphi}} \right) \tag{6.2.5}$$

where the contractions are done with respect to the subscript basis vectors $\hat{t}, \hat{r}, \hat{\theta}, \hat{\varphi}$.

Furthermore, there is a series expansion similarly to the Regge-Wheeler-Zerilli case

$$\Psi_4(t, r, \theta, \varphi) = \sum_{l=2}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-l}^l \Psi_4^{lm}(t, r) {}_{-2}Y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi) \tag{6.2.6}$$

while the expansion coefficients can be determined in terms of the RWZ quantities R_{lm} and Q_{lm} as

$$\Psi_4^{lm} = \frac{1}{r} \sqrt{\frac{(l+2)!}{(l-2)!}} (\ddot{R}_{lm} - i\dot{Q}_{lm}) \tag{6.2.7}$$

and using the orthogonality relations of the spherical harmonics Y_{lm} yields the completeness

$$\Psi_4^{lm} = \int d\Omega {}_{-2}Y_{lm}^* \Psi_4 \tag{6.2.8}$$

Further reading: [BS10].

Chapter 7

Modeling

Extreme Mass Ratio Inspiral [NASA2].

While simulations typically make as few approximations as possible, modeling means building predictions using approximations and phenomenological assumptions. As opposed to simulations they depend on many parameters that have to be tuned to Numerical Relativity results. The huge advantage over simulations is that modeling is computationally inexpensive and typically involves only Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs) instead of the Partial Differential Equations (PDEs) arising from a full numerical solution of General Relativity.

Starting from the discovery that Numerical Relativity is way too expensive for low mass ratio and spin, there is a need to find other approaches. The inspiral part of a Binary Black Hole coalescence can be described by Post-Newtonian theory (see chapter 4 Approximation) while the ringdown is expected to be captured by Black Hole perturbation theory (see chapter 8 Perturbation). The prediction of the plunge and merger part of the waveform however is only possible through Numerical Relativity simulations as they reside in the highly nonlinear strong-field regime.

One is now left with the issue of how to combine the three scopes of application. Hybrid models simply adhere the Post-Newtonian inspiral to the Numerical Relativity plunge, merger and ringdown, minimizing their phase differences, without involving Black Hole perturbation theory. Phenomenological models also use the Post-Newtonian inspiral but instead of rawly using the simulation data, fits are done supposing a form expected from Black Hole perturbation theory for the ringdown.

A powerful alternative that has been increasingly successful recently is the Effective One Body (EOB) model that includes all parts of the waveform without always involving Numerical Relativity (although a one-time tuning to simulation data is important). In Post-Newtonian theory, the conservative dynamics and Gravitational Wave emission is computed as a Taylor expansion which is here "resummed" into an appropriate form to separate the conservative from the radiation-reaction part of the dynamics. Incorporating Post-Newtonian theory, the test-mass limit, Extreme Mass Ratio limit and results from Black Hole perturbation theory as well as Numerical Relativity, the Effective One Body description is a comprehensive model that is, in contrast to the simulations, extremely fast in performance and astonishingly accurate.

Yet the Effective One Body model is still numerical, involving Ordinary Differential Equations. For data analysis purposes, an analytical description is desirable as it is again much faster. There are mainly two ways to obtain analytic waveforms - Phenomenological models (Phenom) and Reduced Order Modeling (ROM) surrogates. As stated above, the former approach means fitting the Numerical Relativity simulation data. The latter however takes Effective One Body results that can be generated fine-meshed over the parameterspace in order to fit these at certain points (parameters) and check with other points or simulations. Both fitting techniques can be performed in either the time domain (TD) or frequency domain (FD) while the last one is especially important to make predictions for higher modes giving information about the geometry of the source that has to be captured by the detector.

Further reading: [Hug09, Dam08, Bla15].

7.1 Approaches

Starting from the fact that Numerical Relativity is far too expensive for binaries with small initial separation and low mass ratio and spins, systems to produce a complete waveform including many inspiral cycles, there are several ways to combine Numerical Relativity (NR) with Post-Newtonian (PN) theory in order to make a "complete" waveform model.

Figure 7.1: Modeling approaches to obtain a waveform faster.

The three main approaches are

- **Hybrid:** Early PN inspiral and NR late inspiral, merger and ringdown are "glued" together at a matching point where the phase difference is minimized.
- **Phenomenological:** PN is used for inspiral while for the merger and ringdown functions with unknown coefficients are determined from fits to NR simulations.
- **Effective One Body:** A full inspiral-merger-ringdown model from ODEs is build on PN inspiral expansions, corrections from NR for the merger and Black Hole perturbation theory (see chapter 8 Perturbation) Quasinormal Mode predictions for the ringdown.

Numerical Relativity simulations are essential for all three techniques because they are irreplaceably providing information on the nonlinear strong-field waveform part around the merger.

An alternative to the phenomenological models that yield an analytical waveform is a surrogate obtained by

- **Reduced Order Modeling:** NR and EOB data is produced fine-meshed over the parameterspace in order to fit the unknown parameters.

The difference is that while the phenomenological model can only rely on a relatively small number of NR simulations, the surrogate (ROM) model is able to include data from a lot more points in the parameterspace, theoretically only limited by how many are previously generated, though one has to be careful estimating the number of support points that are effectively needed.

In the following, the above approaches are presented and explained in more detail after a brief description of the general idea and error estimation strategy.

7.2 Analytical Relativity (AR) meets Numerical Relativity (NR)

In the last chapters, analytical approximation schemes and numerical simulations (together with waveform extraction methods) have been introduced. Unfortunately, all these techniques have their limitations with respect to the scope of validity. Post-Newtonian theory provides faithful and accurate predictions in the early inspiral phase by simple differential equations or even in closed form. However, the approximations become increasingly inaccurate when the system approaches the plunge. The loss of energy caused by Gravitational Wave emission causes shrinking orbits of the binary and increasing velocities of the Black Holes. At a certain point in the late inspiral close to the plunge, Numerical Relativity resumes the description including the nonlinearities of the field equations. But, as the simulations are expensive, challenging and time consuming, several different analytical modifications of the Post-Newtonian series have been developed, trying to enhance their convergence even closer to the merger. In order to obtain the most accurate and complete waveforms many strategies have to be combined in joint efforts of Analytical and Numerical Relativity research communities. The Numerical INjection Analysis (NINJA) project blends AR and NR to achieve a smooth connection between two parts and thereby provide better templates for data analysis pipelines that are used to identify astrophysical events in the measurements of ground- and space-based detectors (most prominently LIGO and LISA) and enable the most accurate extraction of the physical parameters of the sources encoded in the signal. The application of those mixed models in analysis algorithms yet require an exhaustive error estimation.

7.2.1 Uncertainties in the modeling process

To access the accuracy requirements for detection and parameter estimation, we have to recall the basic strategy of matched-filtering (see chapter 3 Analysis).

Assuming a genuine detector signal is measured containing the waveform h_1 that has to be compared to a template $h_2(\theta)$ finding the maximum agreement depending on parameters θ . This can be achieved by evaluating the inner product (equation (3.3.1) in section Data Analysis)

$$\langle h_1 | h_2 \rangle \equiv 4\text{Re} \int_{f_1}^{f_2} \frac{\tilde{h}_1(f) \tilde{h}_2(f)^*}{S_n(f)} df \quad (7.2.1)$$

in the frequency $h(f)$ domain where S_n is the noise spectral density of the Gravitational Wave detector (adopting a stationary Gaussian noise with zero mean).

It is now possible to define the detection efficiency in terms of the norm $\|\cdot\|$ as

$$\mathcal{M} = 1 - \max_{\theta} \frac{\langle h_1, h_2(\theta) \rangle}{\|h_1\| \|h_2(\theta)\|}, \quad \|h_i\| = \sqrt{\langle h_i, h_i \rangle} \quad (7.2.2)$$

quantifying the loss in signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) due to an inexact model or fraction of missed signals in a matched-filter search.

If, instead of assessing a detector signal, two theoretical templates are compared, the mismatch between the waveforms that are supposed to be equivalent can be used to estimate the error of the modeling process. This can be performed either maximizing the agreement or minimizing the phase difference at the matching point (t_0, ϕ_0) that is found varying the parameters θ . A reasonable requirement to find the uncertainty of estimating parameters can be that the error of the waveform model is indistinguishable by the detector. Denoting two supposedly equivalent waveforms by h_1 and h_2 this can be mathematically formulated as

$$\|\delta h\| = \|h_1 - h_2\| < \varepsilon \quad (7.2.3)$$

or, under the assumption of equal norms $\|h_1\| = \|h_2\| = \|h\|$, in terms of the efficiency as

$$\mathcal{M} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\|\delta h\|^2}{\|h\|^2} < \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2\|h\|^2} \quad (7.2.4)$$

The fulfillment of the last two equivalent conditions is then the ultimate goal for an accurate waveform model. With this powerful tool, different types of uncertainties can be considered including errors in the NR regime, hybridization errors or interpolation errors.

Further reading: [Ohm12].

7.3 Effective One Body

The Effective One Body (EOB) approach is a bridge between post-Newtonian theory and Numerical Relativity while also taking into account Black Hole perturbation theory. As post-Newtonian waveforms fail to be accurate at a certain stage and Numerical Relativity simulations are expensive, it is the tool Gravitational Wave scientists must reach for when wanting to densely cover the parameterspace. The technique is often called 'analytic' even if we are dealing with Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs) that are solved numerically using standard Runge-Kutta integrations since this takes much less time than a full three-dimensional simulation. However, actual 'analytical' waveforms are produced as Reduced Order Modeling (ROM) interpolations (see next section) of the EOB results or Phenomenological model fits. As EOB calculations are tuned to NR simulations (calibration of free parameters), the comprehensive descriptions are often referred to as EOB/NR models.

7.3.1 EOB regimes

Figure 7.2 provides an overview on different validity ranges of the individual modeling approaches that try to capture the dynamics of a Binary Black Hole coalescence. There are mainly two variables that determine the scenario, the mass ratio and the separation of the Black Holes (here represented by the x - and y -axis of the plot). Numerical Relativity is applicable in the case of small mass ratio and binary separation where the simulations are computationally sustainable. Post-Newtonian theory fails at small distances (in the strong-field regime) but extends to higher mass ratio whereas for large mass ratio and small separation Perturbation theory and Self-force calculations are needed (see chapter 8 Perturbation and section Extreme Mass Ratio Inspiral of this chapter).

The Effective One Body approach now aims at including all scopes by bringing together results from the several different descriptions in a comprehensive model that performs fast when producing waveforms.

Figure 7.2: Regimes and approximation schemes for the relativistic two-body problem [BS15].

7.3.2 EOB formalism

The EOB model consists of three "rather separate ingredients" [Dam08]

- a description of the conservative (Hamiltonian) part of the dynamics of the Black Hole binary
- an expression for the radiation-reaction (flux) part of the dynamics
- a description of the GW waveform emitted by the coalescing Black Holes

All three ingredients are based on results from post-Newtonian expansions that have been prepared over many years of strong mathematical efforts by many researchers following an original groundwork paper [BD99] by Damour and Buonanno published in 1999. Among the contributors are Jaranowski, Schäfer, Iyer, Nagar, Barausse, Balmelli and Jetzer. Apart from the nonspinning EOB model, there are various extensions including spin (aligned or antialigned with the orbital plane) and precession that are continuously improving. The two main branches developing EOB expansions and codes are Buonanno's group at Albert-Einstein-Institut (AEI) in Potsdam / Hannover and Damour's group at Institut des Hautes Études Scientifiques (IHÉS) in Paris.

Hamiltonian and effective metric

Recall that the symmetric reduced mass ratio of a binary is $\nu = \mu/M = m_1 m_2 / M^2$ with the reduced mass $\mu = m_1 m_2 / (m_1 + m_2) = m_1 m_2 / M$ and the total mass $M = m_1 + m_2$. With R being the binary separation, a Post-Newtonian expansion parameter can be $\gamma = M/R$. The relative position of the Black Holes $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{q}_1 - \mathbf{q}_2$ and their linear momentum $\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{p}_1 = -\mathbf{p}_2$ then enters a conservative Hamiltonian

$$H(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) = H_0(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) + H_2(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) + H_4(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) \quad (7.3.1)$$

with a Newtonian part of the dynamics

$$H_0 = |\mathbf{p}|^2 / 2\mu + m\mu / |\mathbf{q}| \quad (7.3.2)$$

and the Post-Newtonian corrections $H_{2,4}$. The Hamiltonian can be used for calculations of the binary's energy and angular momentum as usual in the Hamiltonian formulation of classical mechanics.

The relativistic description enters with an EOB metric $g_{\mu\nu}^{\text{eff}}$ given by

$$ds^2 = g_{\mu\nu}^{\text{eff}} dx^\mu dx^\nu = -A(R)dt^2 + B(R)dR^2 + R^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2) \quad (7.3.3)$$

where

$$A(R) = 1 + \alpha_1(\nu)\gamma + \alpha_2(\nu)\gamma^2 + \dots \quad (7.3.4)$$

and

$$B(R) = 1 + \beta_1(\nu)\gamma + \beta_2(\nu)\gamma^2 + \dots \quad (7.3.5)$$

quantifying deviations from a Schwarzschild potential $A(R) = 1 + \gamma$.

The effective problem is the description of the motion of a test body in the spacetime (7.3.3) with the symmetric reduced mass ratio ν being a perturbation parameter. The coefficients α_i and β_i depend on ν and are "fixed by asserting a correspondence between certain action variables in the PN-framework" [Hug09]. In the limit of $\nu \rightarrow 0$ the problem obviously reduces to the Schwarzschild case.

Figure 7.3: EOB potential $A(R)$ as a function of the binary separation R . The Schwarzschild case (black dashes) is compared to EOB corrections where the recent model (red line) of Nagar et al. is "NR informed" (tuned to NR data). The solid dots mark the peaks of an effective "photon-potential" $A(R)/R^2$ where a light-ring around the effective Black Hole is apparent [Nag16].

Radiation reaction

The radiation-reaction part can be found using phase space variables r, p_r, ϕ, p_ϕ as (Newtonian) action principle

$$\frac{dp_\phi}{dt} = -\mathcal{F}_\phi \quad (7.3.6)$$

with the radiation reaction force given by

$$\mathcal{F}(v) = \frac{32}{5} \nu r^4 \Omega^5 F(v), \quad (7.3.7)$$

where $F(v)$ can be expanded in the (dimensionless) orbital velocity $\beta = v/c$ as

$$F(v) = 1 + \sum a_n \beta^{n/2} + \sum b_n \ln(\beta) \beta^{n/2}. \quad (7.3.8)$$

The coefficients a_n and b_n can be computed from comparing with PN results and perturbation theory up to certain orders in n . Damour et al. introduced a resummation of $F(v)$ by factoring out a pole at $v = \hat{v}$ that can be freely adjusted to NR simulations

$$F^{\text{res}}(v) = (1 - v/\hat{v})^{-1} P[(1 - v/\hat{v})F(v)], \quad (7.3.9)$$

where the remaining terms are reorganized using a Padé approximant P yielding

$$P \left[1 + \sum_{n=1}^N c_n \beta^n \right] = \frac{1 + \sum_{n=1}^{N/2} d_n \beta^n}{1 + \sum_{n=1}^{N/2} e_n \beta^n}. \quad (7.3.10)$$

This way, an N th order polynomial is converted into a ratio of $N/2$ th order polynomials that reproduce the original polynomial using the small expansion in v .

Further reading: [Hug09, Dam08].

Figure 7.4: Coalescence of two nonspinning Black Holes with a mass ratio $q = m_1/m_2 = 4$. The NR-EOB comparison is performed in a) amplitude, frequency and phase (left) and b) waveform of the dominant $l = m = 2$ mode (right) [Hug09].

7.3.3 EOB code (IHÉS)

As noted above in this section, there are mainly two groups developing an Effective One Body model or code. Buonanno's group at AEI and Damour's group at IHÉS. While the former does not release their code, the latter provides a public version¹ of a collection of MATLAB² scripts (C++ in progress) available under a GNU General Public License (GPL). The model incorporates Post-Newtonian expansions up to fifth order (5PN), the (2,2) - (2,1) - (3,3) mode and tidal effects for Neutron Star (NS) deformations. The nonspinning code was written by Alessandro Nagar and Thibault Damour while the tidal extension was developed by Sebastiano Bernuzzi. The EOB model and code are steadily improved by new implementations including more physics or higher expansion orders. One has to register before access to the download section is granted. A documentation generated with the Documentation System for MATLAB in HTML (M2HTML)³ can be found within the tarballs (file archives).

The following functions are most important

- EOBRun: main function
- Example_EOBRunq1: main example of EOB run
- compilemex: compiles EOB tails as mex-files

Running the code requires less than 10 seconds on an up-to-date standard PC for an equal-mass $q = 1$ binary (Example_EOBRunq1). Prior to use, however, one has to run a compilemex-script that includes lengthy Post-Newtonian expressions (tails) written in Fortran into the MATLAB scripts. The EOB potential, dynamics (orbit), and a waveform is plotted (see examples in figure 7.5).

Further reading: [EOB, Nag16].

Figure 7.5: EOB dynamics (above) and waveform (below) of an equal-mass non-spinning binary (own figure).

¹The 5PN (Tidal) Nospin EOB scripts are available under <https://eob.ihes.fr/>, a website hosted by the IHÉS.

²<https://de.mathworks.com/products/matlab.html>

³<http://www.artefact.tk/software/matlab/m2html/>

7.4 Reduced Order Modeling

Having Numerical Relativity (NR) simulation data or Effective One Body (EOB) code outputs at hand, there is another recently upcoming technique for obtaining fast and accurate waveforms: Surrogate models that perform a Reduced Order Modeling (ROM) as interpolation of the parameterspace. The method that was introduced by Field, Galley, Blackman et al. uses NR or EOB data to interpolate within the dimensions of the parameterspace (typically symmetric mass ratio and effective spin) to obtain an analytic waveform for any set of Binary Black Hole parameters. The final goal is to "build a model that is as good as NR and can be a substitute of NR simulations (surrogate)" [Ott15].

Figure 7.6: Reduced Order Modeling (ROM) of the parameterspace [Ott15].

Figure 7.6 illustrates the general procedure of building a ROM surrogate. Having N reduced basis waveforms (blue lines), the data is fit at N empirical time nodes (red lines) and using the known data (black dots), one can evaluate the fits at arbitrary parameters (cyan dots) and then use the empirical interpolant to uniquely determine new data (cyan line) [Ott15].

The surrogate model is trained on a dense set of waveforms (training set) and then checked using other data (test set), preferably from other simulation groups. The error is assessed by the deviations of the model from the test set, thus the reliability of the predictions with respect to NR results. Typically the errors are almost as small as the numerical error. As the ROM surrogate is based on NR data, it is restricted to the parameter ranges of the simulations (mass ratio, spins, orbits and spherical harmonic modes). Another possibility is to tune the model to EOB data that is generated beforehand, densely distributed over the parameterspace.

Figure 7.7: Comparison of the SXS $(l, m) = (2, 2)$ waveform with a ROM result [Bla15].

Figure 7.7 shows a comparison of the $(l, m) = (2, 2)$ waveform of a nonspinning simulation with mass ratio $q = 2$ with surrogates prediction. Both curves seem to agree astonishingly well, yet the spinning (aligned or antialigned) and precessing case is more complicated and subject to current ongoing research.

Instead of interpolating the parameterspace for surrogates (ROM), phenomenological models construct fits of NR data by minimizing the deviations (least-square) - they will be introduced in the next sections of this chapter.

Further reading: [Bla15].

7.5 Phenomenological Models

An useful alternative to the Effective One Body (EOB) model is to first construct a PN-NR hybrid that is phenomenologically fitted in a second step. The approach relies on including different Post-Newtonian expansions in the time or frequency domain, denoted as "Taylor Tn" or "Taylor Fn" where n is the version number.

The fits are usually done in the symmetric mass-ratio ν and an effective or total spin

$$\chi = \frac{m_1\chi_1 + m_2\chi_2}{m_1 + m_2} \quad (7.5.1)$$

yielding two-dimensional (surface) least-square regression.

7.5.1 PhenomD

If the frequency domain waveform $\tilde{h}(f)$ is modeled, it can be related to the time domain waveform $h(t)$ by the familiar Fourier transformation

$$\tilde{h}(f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(t)e^{-i2\pi ft} dt. \quad (7.5.2)$$

Especially interesting is the ringdown part that was found to comply with

$$h(t) = e^{2\pi(i f_{\text{RD}} t - f_{\text{damp}} |t|)}, \quad f_{\text{RD}}, f_{\text{damp}} \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (7.5.3)$$

where f_{RD} is the ringdown frequency and f_{damp} the damping or decay time of the Quasinormal Mode (QNM) that is excited. The remainder of this thesis will focus on ringdown fits and QNMs.

The frequency domain waveform can be fitted to the Lorentzian

$$\tilde{h}(f) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \frac{f_{\text{damp}}}{(f - f_{\text{RD}}) + f_{\text{damp}}^2}, \quad (7.5.4)$$

Husa et al. presented [Hus16] two-dimensional fits of the final mass (or radiated energy) and spin of the remnant Black Hole. The latter, for example, was found to be given by

$$\begin{aligned} a_f(\eta, S) = & S + 2\sqrt{3}\eta - 4.399\eta^2 + 9.397\eta^3 - 13.181\eta^4 \\ & + (-0.085S + 0.102S^2 - 1.355S^3 - 0.868S^4)\eta \\ & + (-5.837S - 2.097S^2 + 4.109S^3 + 2.064S^4)\eta^2 \end{aligned} \quad (7.5.5)$$

from a fit presented in figure 7.8 below.

Further reading: [Hus16].

Figure 7.8: Final Kerr spin parameter fitted according to equation (7.5.5) as a function of the symmetric mass-ratio η and an effective or total spin \hat{S} . Black dots represent data points with equal spins, grey dots unequal spins [Hus16].

There is also a version of a PhenomP model for generic configurations of spinning Black Hole binaries (through inspiral, merger and ringdown) including precession that was recently published [Han14] by Hannam et al.

7.6 Merger and Ringdown (own results)

This final section contains only own results, if not cited explicitly.

Having discussed some of the currently available waveform models, part of this thesis is to present a new phenomenological merger-ringdown model that is later visualized. The model was originally motivated by the need for a representation of the determining merger quantities amplitude ω , amplitude time derivative $d\omega/dt$, frequency ω and frequency time derivative $d\omega/dt$ over the parameterspace to use for calibration of the IHES Effective One Body (EOB) code.

Proposed by Alessandro Nagar (IHES) as aforementioned, analytical expressions for the above-named merger quantities have been found, fitted over the symmetric mass ratio $\nu = \mu/M = \frac{m_1 m_2}{(m_1 + m_2)^2} = \frac{q}{(q+1)^2}$ and the effective spin $S_{\text{eff}} = (m_1^2 \chi_{1z} + m_2^2 \chi_{2z}) / (m_1^2 + m_2^2)$. The polynomial dependency (suspected by common literature e.g. [Hus16]) has been confirmed. It turns out that second order polynomials in both ν and S_{eff} including mixing terms already describe the requested quantities to satisfying coefficients of determination $R^2 > 0.963$. The merger quantities have been fitted to a total of 141 nonprecessing simulations proposed by [Boh17] in Appendix C, individually discarding datapoints that break ranks. The two-dimensional surface fits are performed using the Polynomial Curve Fitting of MATLAB⁴.

7.6.1 Merger

Figure 7.9 indicates the position of the merger part of the Binary Black Hole waveform.

Figure 7.9: Merger part of the Binary Black Hole coalescence waveform indicated by a vertical black rectangle (edited from [BS10]).

On the following pages, the fit formulae with coefficients determined from the data are presented together with their respective coefficients of determination R^2 and figures with 3d-plots of the fitting surfaces on the data points (left hand sides) as well as the individual deviations (right hand sides). All merger quantities are extracted with a delay of $t/M = 2$ in order to obtain a feasible slope for the time derivatives. In the Effective One Body model this is called the "NonQuasiCircular functioning point" (NQCfp).

Jiménez-Forteza et al. proposed [Jim16] a hierarchical data-driven bottom-up approach to fitting the numerical data that is illustrated in figure 7.10. Motivated by the need to reduce the demands on the computational resources, they try to construct a phenomenological merger-model in both the effective spin parameter $S_{\text{eff}} = (m_1^2 \chi_{1z} + m_2^2 \chi_{2z}) / (m_1^2 + m_2^2)$ and a spin difference $\Delta\chi = \chi_1 - \chi_2$ instead of the original individual spins χ_1 and χ_2 , the original initial data parameters of the simulation. Moreover, the analytically available Extreme Mass Ratio limit is included.

⁴<https://de.mathworks.com/help/matlab/ref/polyfit.html> (23.2.2017)

Figure 7.10: Hierarchical step-by-step fitting of waveform (merger) quantities over the parameterspace that is spanned by the symmetric mass ratio ν and the two spins χ_1 and χ_2 that can be replaced by an effective spin S_{eff} and a spin difference $\Delta\chi$ [Jim16].

Amplitude and Derivative - Fit and Residuals

The amplitude at merger (NQC functioning point) was found to be

$$A(t_{\text{mrg}} + 2M) = 0.0011872S_{\text{eff}} + 0.015417\nu - 0.0012385\nu S_{\text{eff}} \\ + 0.027771\nu^2 - 0.00031086S_{\text{eff}}^2 + 0.0063024$$

with

$$R^2 = 0.963.$$

Its time derivative can be captured by

$$dA/dt(t_{\text{mrg}} + 2M) = 0.0019263S_{\text{eff}} + 0.019955\nu - 0.0042614\nu S_{\text{eff}} \\ + 0.010357\nu^2 - 0.00019718S_{\text{eff}}^2 + 0.0061834$$

with

$$R^2 = 0.976.$$

Figure 7.11: Fit of the gravitational wave amplitude A at merger t_{mrg} within the reduced two dimensional parameterspace spanned by the symmetric mass ratio ν and the effective spin S_{eff} . The left hand side shows the smooth surface that is least-square adapted to the data points obtained from the SXS simulations whereas the right hand side plots the deviations from the fit of the individual simulations.

Figure 7.12: Fit of the gravitational wave amplitude time derivative dA/dt at merger t_{mrg} within the reduced two dimensional parameterspace spanned by the symmetric mass ratio ν and the effective spin S_{eff} . The surface fit (left) is mapped together with the deviations of the individual simulations (right).

Frequency and Derivative - Fit and Residuals

The frequency at merger (NQC functioning point) was found to be

$$\begin{aligned}\omega(t_{\text{mrg}} + 2M) = & 0.00088998S_{\text{eff}} + 0.015153\nu - 0.00029933\nu S_{\text{eff}} \\ & + 0.029058\nu^2 - 0.00022244S_{\text{eff}}^2 + 0.0062474\end{aligned}$$

with

$$R^2 = 0.9887.$$

Its time derivative can be captured by

$$\begin{aligned}d\omega/dt(t_{\text{mrg}} + 2M) = & 0.0020809S_{\text{eff}} + 0.016133\nu - 0.0054203\nu S_{\text{eff}} \\ & + 0.024788\nu^2 + 9.9741 \cdot 10^{-5}S_{\text{eff}}^2 + 0.006222\end{aligned}$$

with

$$R^2 = 0.997.$$

Figure 7.13: Fit of the gravitational wave frequency ω at merger t_{mrg} within the reduced two dimensional parameterspace spanned by the symmetric mass ratio ν and the effective spin S_{eff} . The left hand side shows the smooth surface that is least-square adapted to the data points obtained from the SXS simulations whereas the right hand side plots the deviations from the fit of the individual simulations.

Figure 7.14: Fit of the gravitational wave frequency time derivative $d\omega/dt$ at merger t_{mrg} within the reduced two dimensional parameterspace spanned by the symmetric mass ratio ν and the effective spin S_{eff} . The surface fit (left) is mapped together with the deviations of the individual simulations (right).

Merger - Final mass and spin

The fitting results of the amplitude A_{mrg} and frequency ω_{mrg} along with their derivatives dA/dt_{mrg} and frequency $d\omega/dt_{\text{mrg}}$ at merger are already satisfying to some extent. Much more accurate however are the possible fits for the final mass m_f and the final spin j_f .

These are especially important in the remainder of this thesis, as the ringdown will be compared to Quasinormal Mode predictions (starting next chapter) where the calculations depend (solely) on these quantities. At least if the No-hair theorem is correct this should be the case, a fact that calls for experimental verification.

The final mass is connected to the radiated energy via

$$E_{\text{rad}} = M - m_f = 1 - m_f. \quad (7.6.1)$$

Taking all the initially nonspinning simulations one ends up with a polynomial formula in the symmetric mass ratio for the final mass

$$m_f(\nu) = -0.6802 \nu^2 - 0.0122 \nu + 0.9972$$

that yields very high coefficients of determination and residua

$$R^2 = 0.99991, \quad \max(\text{Res}) = 3.0120 \cdot 10^{-4}$$

Furthermore the final spin (that will be even more important in the next chapters) can be expressed as

$$j_f(\nu) = -3.7303 \nu^2 + 3.4264 \nu - 0.0017$$

with

$$R^2 = 0.999997, \quad \max(\text{Res}) = 5.2343 \cdot 10^{-4}$$

Figure 7.15 shows the quadratic fit functions together with the data points, each representing a value obtained from a SXS simulation whose individual Black Holes are initially nonspinning ($\chi_1 = \chi_2 = 0$).

Figure 7.15: Quadratic polynomial fits of the final mass (left) and spin (right) of all available initially nonspinning SXS simulations.

Figure 7.16: Ringdown part of the Binary Black Hole coalescence waveform indicated by a vertical black rectangle (edited from [BS10]).

7.6.2 Ringdown

With the merger quantities A_{mrg} , ω_{mrg} , dA/dt_{mrg} , $d\omega/dt_{\text{mrg}}$, m_f and j_f at hand, it is finally possible to construct a ringdown model that is later assessed in comparison with other models and calculations.

Figure 7.16 indicates the position of the ringdown part of the Binary Black Hole waveform.

A simple ansatz for the time evolution can be

$$\rho h_{rd} / M = A_{\text{mrg}} \exp\left(i(\omega_{\text{mrg}} + i/\tau_{\text{mrg}})t + i\phi_{\text{mrg}}(t=0)\right) \quad (7.6.2)$$

where in addition to the already discussed amplitude A_{mrg} and frequency ω_{mrg} at merger, a decay time τ_{mrg} and initial phase $\phi_{\text{mrg}}(t=0)$ have to be introduced. Note that the latter is not to be confused with the azimuthal variable φ of the spherical coordinate system that is often used in this work. The time derivatives dA/dt_{mrg} and $d\omega/dt_{\text{mrg}}$ needed for the Effective One Body tuning, are here not employed anymore - they could however still be utilized when a refinement of the model has to be done. The frequency ω_{mrg} and decay time τ_{mrg} will later be identified with the real and imaginary part of the complex Quasinormal Mode frequencies while the amplitude A_{mrg} is supposed to be the excitation coefficient of the damped harmonic mode.

To obtain the above expression fitted all over the parameterspace of the SXS simulation data, two individual fits have to be done, one exponential that captures the amplitude and decay time, and a linear one for the frequency (slope) and initial phase (intercept).

Ringdown - amplitude, phase and frequency

There are different ways to obtain the ringdown frequency and decay time from the available data. Besides being the slope of the phase in time, a numerical time derivative can be computed to directly capture the frequency. Thus one can get the ringdown frequency and decay time by

- Numerical derivative $\omega = \frac{d\phi}{dt}(t_{\text{mrg}})$ and approximation $\tau = t(A = A_{\text{mrg}}/e)$
- Difference quotient of phase evolution $\frac{\Delta\phi}{\Delta t}$ during linear ringdown

Figure 7.17 shows plots of the variation in time of the amplitude, phase and frequency of the 2,2 mode of BBH1 exemplarily.

While the amplitude seems to be quite smooth, there are some oscillations visible in the phase at the end of the linear increase before it gets constant with zero frequency. The oscillations are reflected in a two-sided resonance peak of the frequency. Because of these numerical artifacts it is more accurate to just approximate the frequency as the difference quotient of the phase evolution $\frac{\Delta\phi}{\Delta t}$ during linear ringdown which will be exclusively done in the following.

Figure 7.17: Exponentially decaying ringdown amplitude $A(t)$ (above left) and linearly increasing ringdown phase $\phi(t)$ (above right) of the 2,2-mode. The Ringdown frequency $\omega(t)$ (below) is obtained by a numerical derivative of the phase.

Fit comparison - amplitude and phase

In the construction of the phenomenological ringdown model, it is now due to fit the amplitude and phase. Starting with the amplitude, two possible formulas are tried. First a simple exponential decay

$$|h|(t) = A \cdot \exp(-t/\tau) \quad (7.6.3)$$

and secondly a double exponential decay

$$|\tilde{h}|(t) = A_1 \cdot \exp(-t/\tau_1) + A_2 \cdot \exp(-t/\tau_2) \quad (7.6.4)$$

The ringdown frequency and initial phase however can easily be obtained by

$$\phi(t) = \phi_0 + \bar{\omega}t$$

as motivated in the last section.

Figure 7.18 compares the two approaches for the exponential decay (above left) and the effect on the real part of the 2,2 waveform of BBH101 that is chosen as an example.

Figure 7.18: Exponential fit of the 2,2-mode ringdown waveform amplitude (above left) and linear fit of the phase (above right). Real part of the 2,2-mode ringdown waveform (below) where the SXS simulation (blue) is compared to a one-term exponential fit (green) and two-term exponential fit of the amplitude (red).

The real part of the waveform (plotted in figure 7.18 below) can be written as

$$\Re(h)(t) = |h|(t) \cdot \cos(\phi_0 + \omega_0 t) \quad (7.6.5)$$

It turns out that the double exponential fit of the amplitude performs much better. However it will be shown later that the Quasinormal Modes that are expected to be excited at merger and fade away during ringdown only allow for a single exponential according to Black Hole perturbation theory (see the next chapter 8 Perturbation).

Ringdown fitting - problems

So far only the 2,2-mode was considered because it is the dominant contribution as illustrated in the next section. Yet, the final aim is to perform a multimode comparison including all available 77 modes of the SXS data. Unfortunately there are several problems occurring in the analysis.

Most importantly, in many of the subdominant modes there is odd behaviour in either of both the amplitude and phase evolution. This mainly includes oscillations of the amplitude and phase that should not be present and pose unwanted deviations from the expected exponential decay and linear increase respectively. Figure 7.19 represents the broken modes by revealing the oscillations of the 3,1-mode of BBH101 with a medium final spin of $j_f = 0.5$.

Figure 7.19: Odd behavior of the 3,1-mode ringdown amplitude (above) and phase (below). The final spin of the remnant is $j_f = 0.5$, half its maximum.

Another fundamental issue is a vertical beam (figure 7.20 left) occurring in many subdominant modes as a relict of "junk radiation" produced by the initial data where the orbits have to become circularized by the emission of a first burst of Gravitational Waves before settling into the proper inspiral (see chapter 5 Simulation). Though this is a very important conceptual problem in the simulations, it is fortunately not affecting the ringdown fits as it can easily be cut off and is anyway only adhering the inspiral part that is not considered anymore in the remainder of this thesis.

Yet the most problematic issue seems to be rectangular oscillations occurring in the phase evolutions of some of the $m = 0$ modes, depicted in figure 7.20 (right). These modes cannot be fitted properly and have to be discarded.

Multimode comparison

At this point it is due to perform a comparison of the numerous Gravitational Wave modes available in the SXS data from $l = 2$ to $l = 8$ with all the corresponding values of $-l \leq m \leq l$.

The first discovery is that, as already mentioned, there are huge differences in the amplitude with differences up to a factor of 10^9 . This can simply be comprehended by looking at the plots in figure 7.22 above where the merger amplitude A_{\max} is diagrammed over the (spherical) multipole indexes l and m while the right hand side shows the fraction of the individual amplitudes related to the minimum.

The multimode comparison can also be performed including multiple layers in 3D (figure 7.21). It turns out that for the relevant merger quantities, the situation is symmetric in the multipole index m as illustrated for amplitude, frequency and decay time in figure 7.22.

Figure 7.20: Junk radiation caused by initial data (left) and step-oscillations of the ringdown phase (right).

Surprisingly the merger frequency can be fitted in the multipole indexes

$$\omega_{\text{mrg}}(l, m) = 0.23087 m - 0.0015754 l - 0.0031982 l m + 0.0029882 + 0.000111 l^2 - 7.783910^{-5} m^2 \quad (7.6.6)$$

with

$$R^2 = 0.9050 \quad (7.6.7)$$

which is unfortunately not possible for the other merger quantities, a fact that needs further explanation and investigation.

The so far only roughly conducted multimode comparison will be continued in chapter 9 Visualization with more powerful tools at hand and other data available that can be used for a graphical representation.

Figure 7.21: Multimode comparison (multiple layers) of the merger amplitude A_{max} by color code - the distribution is not changing significantly over the parameter space.

Figure 7.22: Multimode comparison (single layer) of the merger quantities A , ω and $1/\tau$ of the nonspinning BBH1 by color code. The amplitude distribution is symmetric in the multipole index m (above left). The dominant $(l, m) = (2, \pm 2)$ mode vastly exceeds the remaining modes by a factor of more than 10^8 (above right). The frequency distribution is also symmetric in the multipole index m , but with an opposite sign (middle left). The frequency at merger can surprisingly be fitted in the multipole indexes l and m (middle right) which is unfortunately not possible for the other merger quantities. The decay time shows no significant symmetry in m (below).

Chapter 8

Perturbation

Black Holes described as "gravitational atom" [RSF].

Long before Numerical Relativity simulations became feasible, there was a tool available to study perturbations of Black Holes that govern the ringdown part of the gravitational waveform where the remnant should be either a perturbed Schwarzschild or Kerr Black Hole. Obviously the first case (Schwarzschild perturbation) is expected to be the product of a head-on collision where no angular momentum is left such that the final Black Hole is nonspinning. The second (Kerr perturbation) has then to be evoked by a Binary Black Hole inspiral that is commonly simulated numerically because it is believed to be the prevalent scenario. Numerical simulations are obliged to agree with Black Hole perturbation theory, a formalism that linearizes Einstein's field equations around an exact solution such as the Minkowski (flat space), Schwarzschild (nonrotating Black Hole) or Kerr (rotating Black Hole) metric. This is important for the prediction of Gravitational Waves that are known to be perturbations of (or "ripples" in) the fabric of spacetime. Perturbation theory can be applied whenever the influence of an external process is small compared to the background spacetime or curvature produced by the presence of the Black Hole that is investigated. Perturbations of stars and Black Holes have been studied extensively several decades in the second half of the last century before finally numerical relativity was able to solve the full nonlinear problems. Regge and Wheeler [RW57] published a treatment of odd-parity Schwarzschild perturbations in 1957 even before Kerr [Ker63] discovered his solution in 1963 followed by Zerilli [Zer70] in 1970 who investigated the remaining even-parity perturbations. Later Teukolsky [Teu72] unified both to derive a master equation in 1972 that governs not only the different potentials depending on the parity but includes also a spin-weight distinguishing scalar, spinor, vector and tensor fields described by harmonic angular functions. The first kind (spin-weight zero) can, for example, model perturbations by spin-zero particles while spinor perturbations (spin-weight one half) capture neutrino interactions, vector (spin-weight one) perturbations correspond to electromagnetic reactions and finally we have the gravitational (spin-weight two) tensor perturbations governing Gravitational Waves. Teukolsky's master equation is a second order partial differential equation in spacetime (time, radius, angles) valid for a general spin-weighted field. As it has a form similar to Schrödinger's quantum mechanical wave equation, it is natural to apply certain boundary conditions in order to obtain discrete eigensolutions. Black Holes are assumed to allow only for purely ingoing waves at their horizon and purely outgoing waves at infinity. The resulting discrete frequencies are called Quasinormal Modes (QNMs) being complex due to the fact that the differential operator of the equation is not self-adjoint. Physically they can be interpreted as damped ("quasi") harmonic ("normal") oscillations of the spacetime where, in the gravitational case, the energy is lost due to the emission of Gravitational Waves. As astrophysically realistic encounters of Black Holes are expected to finally produce these Quasinormal Modes as perturbations of Schwarzschild or Kerr backgrounds, they are of great interest to Gravitational Wave modeling. They are also believed to be an important key to Quantum Gravity as quantizations of the complex frequencies have been discovered leading to a conjecture of a "Gravitational Atom" where Quasinormal Modes play the role of discrete "electron" energy levels. Consequently many Quantum Gravity investigations have been made, especially String Theory and Quantum Loop Gravity inspired approaches. In this chapter the task will be to extract the Quasinormal Modes from the ringdown part of the SXS waveforms in order to compare them to results of Black Hole perturbation theory. Further reading: [Zal14, Zim13].

8.1 Quasinormal Modes

Quasinormal Modes are exponentially decaying harmonic resonances of perturbed Black Holes. They were first discovered numerically [Vis70] by Vishveshwara in 1970 studying the scattering of Gravitational Waves by a Black Hole followed by numerous investigations and reviews published.

The resonant Quasinormal Mode perturbations are excited with the complex frequency

$$\tilde{\omega} = \omega_R + i\omega_I = \omega + i/\tau, \quad (8.1.1)$$

where ω is the actual real frequency and τ the decay time of the oscillation that is damped by the emission of Gravitational Waves. In the past, mostly linear perturbations were examined - however also nonlinear oscillations have to be considered, especially when dealing with parametric resonance and turbulent instabilities. As stated in the introduction above, it turns out that there are many similarities with the quantum mechanical atomic model that is described by Schrödinger's equation. In the Black Hole case, we are not only dealing with a Schrödinger-like wave equation, but also apply boundary solutions in order to obtain discrete (eigen-) frequencies with "quantum-like numbers" (n, l, m) which surprisingly even show an m -degeneracy (as in the quantum case) that is splitted by the Kerr rotation similar to the atomic Zeeman-effect¹. The next section reviews some of the quantum theoretical properties that can be compared to the Quasinormal Mode treatments.

Further reading: [Zal14].

8.1.1 Schrödinger's equation

Waves are excitations or perturbations of a background medium or spacetime metric. In quantum mechanics, subatomic particles are modeled by matter waves that mark regions of high probability to detect the particle². The wave equation governing quantum field interactions is Schrödinger's (nonrelativistic) equation

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \hat{H} \Psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (8.1.2)$$

with $\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ being the quantum probability wave function and \hat{H} the Hamilton (energy) operator that contains a kinetic and potential part

$$\hat{H} = \frac{-\hbar^2}{2\mu} \nabla^2 + V(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (8.1.3)$$

where $\nabla^2 = \partial_x^2 + \partial_y^2 + \partial_z^2$ is the Laplace operator.

Schrödinger's equation is separable in terms of time, radial and angular components.

Applying boundary conditions, the resulting standing waves are characterized by a discrete spectrum of eigenvalues of the Hamilton operator \hat{H} allowing for the decomposition

$$\Psi(r, \theta, \varphi, t) = \sum_{nlm} \psi_{nlm} \quad (8.1.4)$$

The angular part is given by the (scalar) spherical harmonics

$$Y_l^m(\theta, \varphi) = (-1)^m \sqrt{\frac{(2l+1)(l-m)!}{4\pi(l+m)!}} P_{lm}(\cos\theta) e^{im\varphi} \quad (8.1.5)$$

where $P_{lm}(\cos\theta)$ are the Associated Legendre polynomials (see chapter 6 Extraction).

The quantum numbers (n, l, m) describe degeneracy (same eigenvalue for different eigenfunctions) and can only take integer values while only m allows for negative numbers.

¹Splitting of the energy levels corresponding to a certain state in the atomic spectra by application of a magnetic field.

²Since the beginning of the 20th century, experiments have shown a manifest duality of matter and radiation both being particles and waves (or at least having respective attributes) depending on the particular experiment.

8.1.2 Spin-weighted definite parity perturbations

As mentioned in the introduction of this chapter, Regge, Wheeler, Zerilli and Teukolsky were surprised to find that perturbations of Schwarzschild and Kerr Black Holes exhibit very similar characteristics. There are Schrödinger-like wave equations, separable radial and angular parts of the waveforms and discrete spectra determined by indexes (n, l, m) . While Schrödinger's equation deals with massive particles that are supposed to be governed by a massless spin zero (Higgs) Boson, electromagnetic and gravitational interactions are vector (spin one) and tensor (spin two) field perturbations. To account for these different types, one can introduce a spin-weight s . Yet there is still another additional degeneracy, namely the parity of the perturbation (recall chapter Extraction) that is assumed to be definite.

Applying a spacial inversion, the angular part is transformed as

$$Y_l^m(\theta, \varphi) \rightarrow \tilde{Y}_l^m(\pi - \theta, \pi + \varphi) \quad (8.1.6)$$

while changing the sign according to the parity that is determined by l .

For even, polar, Zerilli or electric parity perturbations the resulting factor is

$$(-1)^l$$

whereas odd, axial, Regge-Wheeler or magnetic parity perturbations multiply by

$$(-1)^{l+1}$$

The terms "even" or "odd" are obviously misleading because the actual sign depends on l . In the following the two types will be referred to as either polar/axial or electric/magnetic parity perturbations (see also chapter 9 Visualization).

Restraining now to only the gravitational perturbations of a Black Hole metric, the spin-weight $|s| = 2$ can take two values. A positive $s = +2$ corresponds to

$$\psi_s = \psi_{+2} = \Psi_0 \quad (8.1.7)$$

determining the Newman-Penrose (see chapter 6 Extraction) scalar quantity

$$\Psi_0 = -C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} l^\alpha m^\beta l^\gamma m^\delta \quad (8.1.8)$$

that measures ingoing gravitational radiation. A negative $s = -2$ corresponds to

$$\psi_s = \psi_{-2} \sim r^4 \Psi_4 \quad (8.1.9)$$

determining the Newman-Penrose scalar quantity

$$\Psi_4 = -C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} n^\alpha m^{*\beta} n^\gamma m^{*\delta} \quad (8.1.10)$$

that is used to describe outgoing Gravitational Waves.

The Newman-Penrose null-tetrad

$$n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\hat{t} - \hat{r}), \quad l = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\hat{t} + \hat{r}), \quad m = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\hat{\varphi} - i\hat{\theta}) \quad (8.1.11)$$

is not to be confused with the discrete indexes n, l and m occurring in the spectral decomposition of the perturbation ψ . The next two sections will examine perturbations of the Schwarzschild and Kerr metric that are relevant to the extraction of Quasinormal Modes from Binary Black Hole coalescence ringdowns.

Both the Schwarzschild and Kerr perturbation equation, that will be presented in the following, allow for a separation of the perturbation scalar similar to the quantum mechanical case (??) as

$$\psi_{nlm}(t, r, \theta, \varphi) \sim h_{nlm}(t) R_{nlm}(r) S_{nlm}(\theta, \varphi) \quad (8.1.12)$$

where the time dependence

$$h_{nlm}(t) = A_{nlm} \exp\left(i(\omega_{nlm} + i/\tau_{nlm})t\right) \quad (8.1.13)$$

is determined by the Quasinormal Mode frequencies ω_{nlm} and decay times τ_{nlm} as well as the "excitation coefficients" A_{nlm} that can all be extracted as parameters of the ringdown signal of a Binary Black Hole coalescence.

For the radial part, the Euler ansatz

$$R_{nlm}(r) \sim (Ae^{ikr} + Be^{-ikr}) \quad (8.1.14)$$

can be made in order to identify the coefficients A and B from boundary conditions. The angular part is then given by the "spin-weighted spheroidal harmonics"

$${}_sS_{nlm}(\theta, \varphi, c) = e^{im\varphi} \exp\left(c_{lmn} \cos(\theta)\right) (1 + \cos(\theta))^{|m-s|/2} (1 - \cos(\theta))^{|m+s|/2} \sum_p a_p (1 + \cos(\theta))^p \quad (8.1.15)$$

including the oblateness parameter $c_{nlm} = a\tilde{\omega}_{nlm}$ setting the shape of a spheroid.

In this sense, the (spin-weighted) spherical harmonics

$${}_sY_{lm}(\theta, \varphi) = {}_sS_{nlm}(\theta, \varphi, c = 0) \quad (8.1.16)$$

are a special case of the more general (spin-weighted) spheroidal harmonics in the non oblate, spherical limit where $c \rightarrow 0$. Both angular distributions will be discussed in more depth in the last chapter 9 on Visualization.

Further reading: [Zal14].

8.1.3 Schwarzschild perturbations

Recall the Schwarzschild metric for a nonrotating Black Hole

$$ds^2 = -\alpha^2 dt^2 + \frac{dr^2}{\alpha^2} + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2) + h_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu \quad (8.1.17)$$

now expanded by a small (Gravitational Wave) perturbation $h_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu$ while the factor

$$\alpha^2 = 1 - r_s/r = 1 - 2M/r \quad (8.1.18)$$

still includes the event horizon r_s of the Black Hole with mass M .

The perturbation ψ is then governed by the partial differential equation

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial r_*^2} + V_l(r)\psi = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2} + \omega^2 \psi = V_l(r)\psi \quad (8.1.19)$$

with the tortoise coordinate introduced in section Black Holes of chapter 2 Basics obeying

$$dr_* = \frac{dr}{\alpha^2} \quad r_* = r + 2M \ln(\alpha^2 r/2M). \quad (8.1.20)$$

The emerging potential $V_l(r)$ is depending on the type (parity) of the perturbation. For axial (or magnetic) perturbations the expression was found [RW57] by Regge and Wheeler to be

$$V_l^{\text{mag}}(r) = \alpha^2 \left(\frac{l(l+1)}{r^2} - \frac{6M}{r^3} \right) \quad (8.1.21)$$

whereas Zerilli discovered the polar (or electric) potential

$$V_l^{\text{el}}(r) = \alpha^2 \left[\frac{2\lambda^2(\lambda+1)r^3 + 6\lambda^2 Mr^2 + 18\lambda M^2 r + 18M^3}{r^3(\lambda r + 3M)^2} \right] \quad (8.1.22)$$

with

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{2}(l-1)(l+2). \quad (8.1.23)$$

Further reading: [Zal14].

8.1.4 Kerr perturbations

As the majority of the Black Holes occurring in the universe are in general expected to rotate, the Kerr solution for axially symmetric spinning point masses is considered to be the astrophysically most relevant solution.

Recall the line element (2.3.18) in Boyer-Lindquist coordinates (t, r, θ, φ) given by

$$ds^2 = - \left(1 - \frac{r_s r}{\Sigma}\right) dt^2 - \frac{2r_s a r \sin^2 \theta}{\Sigma} dt d\varphi + \frac{\Sigma}{\Delta} dr^2 + \Sigma d\theta^2 + \left(r^2 + a^2 + \frac{r_s a^2 r \sin^2 \theta}{\Sigma}\right) \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2 \quad (8.1.24)$$

with $\Sigma = r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta$, $\Delta = r^2 - r_s r + a^2$ and $r_s = 2GM/c^2$ where $a = J/M$ is the dimensionless spin parameter of the Black Hole.

Making use of the Newman-Penrose formalism, Teukolsky presented [Teu72] a single equation that governs several kinds of perturbations ${}_s\psi$ of different spin-weight s .

The "Teukolsky master equation" (Δ^{-s} is the generalized Laplace operator)

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{(r^2 + a^2)^2}{\Delta} - a^2 \sin^2 \theta \right] \frac{\partial^2 {}_s\psi}{\partial t^2} + \frac{4Mar}{\Delta} \frac{\partial^2 {}_s\psi}{\partial t \partial \phi} + \left[\frac{a^2}{\Delta} - \frac{1}{\sin^2 \theta} \right] \frac{\partial^2 {}_s\psi}{\partial \phi^2} \\ & - \Delta^{-s} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\Delta^{s+1} \frac{\partial {}_s\psi}{\partial r} \right) - \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial {}_s\psi}{\partial \theta} \right) - 2s \left[\frac{a(r-M)}{\Delta} + \frac{i \cos \theta}{\sin^2 \theta} \right] \frac{\partial {}_s\psi}{\partial \phi} \\ & - 2s \left[\frac{M(r^2 - a^2)}{\Delta} - r - ia \cos \theta \right] \frac{\partial {}_s\psi}{\partial t} + (s^2 \cot^2 \theta - s) {}_s\psi = 4\pi \Sigma T \end{aligned} \quad (8.1.25)$$

is rather lengthy and even includes an inhomogeneous matter source term $4\pi\Sigma T$ where T is the trace of the energy-momentum tensor that can be set to zero for vacuum Black Holes, allowing for the separation

$${}_s\psi(t, r, \theta, \phi) = e^{-i\omega t} e^{im\phi} S(\theta) R(r). \quad (8.1.26)$$

Note again that here scalar fields are represented by $s = 0$, spinor fields by $s = \pm 1/2$, electromagnetic fields by $s = \pm 1$, and gravitational perturbations by $s = \pm 2$ where the signs depend on the direction of the interaction (outgoing -, ingoing +). Removing the almost trivial time and azimuthal dependence, the factors $e^{-i\omega t}$ and $e^{im\phi}$, one is left with the radial part $R(r)$ and polar expression $S(\theta) = {}_s S_{lm}(x, c)$ with $x = \cos \theta$ and the oblateness parameter $c = aw$

The spin-weighted spheroidal function ${}_s S_{lm}(\theta, c)$ (without the azimuthal dependence)³ is then satisfying

$$\partial_x \left[(1 - x^2) \partial_x [{}_s S_{lm}] \right] + \left[(cx)^2 - 2csx + s + {}_s A_{lm} c - \frac{(m + sx)^2}{1 - x^2} \right] {}_s S_{lm} = 0 \quad (8.1.27)$$

where m is the azimuthal and ${}_s A_{lm}(c)$ the angular separation constant.

The radial function $R(r)$ is satisfying

$$\Delta^{-s} \frac{d}{dr} \left[\Delta^{s+1} \frac{dR(r)}{dr} \right] + \left[\frac{K^2 - 2is(r-M)K}{\Delta} + 4is\omega r - \lambda \right] R(r) = 0 \quad (8.1.28)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} K &\equiv (r^2 + a^2)\omega - am, \\ \lambda &\equiv {}_s A_{lm} a\omega + a^2\omega^2 - 2am\omega \end{aligned} \quad (8.1.29)$$

while the solution can be expressed as

$$R(r) = e^{i\omega r} (r - r_-)^{-1-s+2iM\omega+i\sigma} (r - r_+)^{-s-i\sigma} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n \left(\frac{r - r_+}{r - r_-} \right)^n \quad (8.1.30)$$

where

$$\sigma \equiv \frac{2\omega r_+ - ma}{r_+ - r_-} \quad (8.1.31)$$

and

$$r_{\pm} = M \pm \sqrt{M^2 - a^2} \quad (8.1.32)$$

are the roots of the quadratic equation $\Delta = r^2 + a^2 - 2Mr$ corresponding to event horizon and ergosphere of the Kerr Black Hole respectively (see chapter 2 Basics).

Further reading: [Zal14].

³It is called "harmonic" when depending on both θ and φ while only "function" if the φ dependence is discarded.

8.2 Numerical Calculation

Many methods have been developed for the calculation of Quasinormal Mode frequencies and expansion coefficients over the last decades. Three of the most important ones are briefly presented in the following. The techniques mainly differ in their accuracy, stability and applicability to certain spacetimes (Schwarzschild, Reisner-Nordström, Kerr, Kerr Newman) and regimes (low or high damping).

8.2.1 WKB method

The first approach uses the analogy of Quasinormal Modes with Quantum Mechanics with respect to the wave equations (see first section of this chapter) to justify the use of the well-known Quantum mechanical WKB⁴ expansions adapted to the Quasinormal Mode case. The Bohr-Sommerfeld rule

$$\int_{r_A}^{r_B} (\omega^2 - V(r))^{1/2} dr = (n + 1/2)\pi \quad (8.2.1)$$

can then be applied to determine the lowest order frequencies. Here r_A and r_B are the two roots (turning points) of $\omega^2 - V(r) = 0$.

The method is increasingly successful for high frequency contributions corresponding to large l numbers. In the limit where $l \gg 1$, an "eikonal" expansion can be used where the waves propagate along null geodesics in the background metric. As this geometric optics correspondence holds, the WKB technique can be extended to higher-order perturbations that are interpreted as dispersion of the waves that are partially bound to the Black Hole such that the signal can oscillate.

Originally developed for Quantum mechanical perturbation theory, the WKB method has been adjusted to various Black Hole spacetimes. Unfortunately the treatment of a Kerr Black Hole is not very simple (complex potential) and accurate (fails at high damping). In this case, the angular eigenvalue problem is coupled to the radial eigenvalue problem as the spherical symmetry is lost.

Further reading: [BCS09, Zim13].

8.2.2 Continued fraction

Another method to calculate the Quasinormal Mode is purely numerical. In contrast to the previously introduced WKB method, it does not provide much intuition about the properties of the Quasinormal Mode spectrum. Leaver used the analogy of Quasinormal Modes with Quantum mechanics in order to build his method [Lea85] that identifies the perturbation wave equations as special cases of Teukolsky's generalized spheroidal wave equation. With a clever series expansion and the appropriate boundary conditions (purely incoming waves at the horizon and purely outgoing at infinity) Leaver could derive recursion relations and examine their convergence properties. The intricate solution of partial differential equations is this way reduced to the numerical solution of continued fraction relation involving only elementary algebraic operations. The technique is found to be very accurate and reliable due to the fact that it scarcely depends on the form of the perturbative potential. It is also quite fast, avoiding the numerical integration of the wave equations. Again one has to methodologically distinguish the two important cases of uncharged Black Holes: nonrotating Schwarzschild and rotating Kerr solutions.

Further reading: [KS99, BCS09].

Schwarzschild modes

In the Schwarzschild case, one can separate the angular part of the wavefunction as just being the spin-weighted spherical harmonics ${}_s Y_{lm}$ while the radial part can be expressed as a power series expansion

$$R(r) = \frac{r^{2i\omega}}{(r-1)^{i\omega}} e^{i\omega(r-1)} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n \left(\frac{r-1}{r} \right)^n \quad (8.2.2)$$

that was found by Leaver who consequently derived a three-term recurrence relation for the expansion coefficients a_n ($n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$)

⁴The method was developed by Wentzel, Kramers, and Brillouin in 1926.

$$\begin{aligned}
\alpha_0 a_1 + \beta_0 a_0 &= 0, \\
\alpha_n a_{n+1} + \beta_n a_n + \gamma_n a_{n-1} &= 0, \\
a_{-1} &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{8.2.3}$$

that determine the (complex) Quasinormal Mode frequencies ω for spin-weight s overtone n multipole l modes via

$$\begin{aligned}
\alpha_n &= n^2 - 2n(i\omega - 1) - 2i\omega + 1, \\
\beta_n &= -2n^2 + 2n(4i\omega - 1) + 8\omega^2 + 4i\omega - l(l+1) + s^2 - 1, \\
\gamma_n &= n^2 - 4i\omega n - 4\omega^2 - s^2.
\end{aligned} \tag{8.2.4}$$

Note that the azimuthal m multipole index does not appear in the Schwarzschild case due to its spherical symmetry. Leaver's method has its name from the fact that the coefficients follow from an infinite continued-fraction equation

$$\frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} = \frac{-\gamma_{n+1}}{\beta_{n+1} - \frac{\alpha_{n+1}\gamma_{n+2}}{\beta_{n+2} - \frac{\alpha_{n+2}\gamma_{n+3}}{\beta_{n+3} - \dots}}} \tag{8.2.5}$$

or in a more compact notation

$$\frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} = \frac{-\gamma_{n+1}}{\beta_{n+1} - \frac{\alpha_{n+1}\gamma_{n+2}}{\beta_{n+2} - \frac{\alpha_{n+2}\gamma_{n+3}}{\beta_{n+3} - \dots}}} \tag{8.2.6}$$

The infinite roots of this equation are distinguished by the "overtone number" n . When calculating the modes ω_{nl} (the solution is degenerate in m that is missing as an index) there are two groups, one ω_{nl} with positive real part (frequency) and the modes ω'_{nl} with negative real part. Fortunately, there are the symmetries

$$\text{Re}(\omega'_{nl}) = -\text{Re}(\omega_{nl}), \quad \text{Im}(\omega'_{nl}) = \text{Im}(\omega_{nl}) \tag{8.2.7}$$

that reduce the necessary calculations by half.

The continued fraction equation can be inverted finding the n -th inversion as

$$\beta_n - \frac{\alpha_{n-1}\gamma_n}{\beta_{n-1} - \frac{\alpha_{n-2}\gamma_{n-1}}{\beta_{n-2} - \dots \frac{\alpha_0\gamma_1}{\beta_0}}} = \frac{\alpha_n\gamma_{n+1}}{\beta_{n+1} - \frac{\alpha_{n+1}\gamma_{n+2}}{\beta_{n+2} - \dots}} \tag{8.2.8}$$

whose root can be calculated numerically using Newton's two-dimensional methods with appropriate initial guesses. The bottom-up evaluation makes it challenging to estimate the number of levels the continued fraction should include. There are several ways to control the number of terms with varying accuracy. However, calculating the Schwarzschild modes is in general no challenging task anymore. Dealing with perturbations of the Kerr metric on the other hand is more intricate.

Kerr modes

As stated before, perturbations of the Kerr metric can be split into an angular part that is the spheroidal harmonic expansion

$${}_s S_{lm}(\theta, \varphi) = e^{im\varphi} \exp\left(a\omega_{lmn} \cos(\theta)\right) (1 + \cos(\theta))^{|m-s|/2} (1 - \cos(\theta))^{|m+s|/2} \sum_p a_p (1 + \cos(\theta))^p \tag{8.2.9}$$

and a radial part given by

$$R(r) = e^{i\omega r} (r - r_-)^{-1-s+2iM\omega+i\sigma} (r - r_+)^{-s-i\sigma} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{r - r_+}{r - r_-}\right)^n \tag{8.2.10}$$

As opposed to the Schwarzschild case, the equations are still coupled by the m value whose degeneracy is gradually lifted as the Black Hole's dimensionless spin $a = j_f/M$ increases towards its maximum of $a = 1$.

Again one has to (numerically) determine the expansion coefficients a_n that are found to still satisfy the three-term recurrence relation (8.2.3), in this case with

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha_n &= n^2 + (D_0 + 1)n + D_0, \\ \beta_n &= -2n^2 + (D_1 + 2)n + D_3, \\ \gamma_n &= n^2 + (D_2 - 3)n + D_4 - D_2 + 2\end{aligned}\tag{8.2.11}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}D_0 &= 1 - s - 2i\sigma_+, \\ D_1 &= 4[i(\sigma_+ + \omega) - 1] + 2i(r_+ - r_-)\omega, \\ D_2 &= 3 + s - 2i(\sigma_+ + 2\omega), \\ D_3 &= (4r_+ - a^2)\omega^2 + 2\omega[(r_+ - r_-)\sigma_+ + 4\sigma_+ + ir_+] + 2i\sigma_+ - (1 + s) - A_{lm}, \\ D_4 &= (1 - 4i\omega)(1 + s - 2i\sigma_+)\end{aligned}\tag{8.2.12}$$

depend in turn on the spin-weight s , the Quasinormal Mode frequency ω , the event horizon r_+ and the ergosphere boundary r_- . In addition there is an "angular separation constant" occurring which should not be confused with the Quasinormal Mode excitation coefficients A_{nlm} that correspond to the ringdown amplitude of a Binary Black Hole merger (see end of chapter 7 Modeling).

Further reading: [Zal14].

8.2.3 Spectral decomposition

Cook and Zalutskiy found another approach that in their opinion "has much better convergence than the continued fraction method, and it seems more stable, although that was not rigorously investigated" [Zal14]. Spectral methods for evolving Gravitational Waves from Kerr Black Holes were already introduced [Hug00] in 2000 by Hughes and notably are the numerical technique chosen in the Spectral Einstein Code (SpEC) that was described in chapter 5 Simulation and is the code producing the SXS simulations used in this work. Cook and Zalutskiy state that they "were not aware of Hughes's works [and] derived it independently". Their method is able of numerically computing both the Kerr Quasinormal Modes and the spin-weighted *spheroidal* harmonics that, in contrast to the spin-weighted *spherical* harmonics, do not have an analytic representation.

Starting with an expansion of the spin-weighted spheroidal functions in terms of the spin-weighted spherical functions

$${}_sS_{lm}(x; c) = \sum_{l'=l_{\min}}^{\infty} C_{l'lm}(c) {}_sS_{l'm}(x; 0)\tag{8.2.13}$$

with $l_{\min} \equiv \max(|m|, |s|)$ and, as before, $x = \cos \theta$ it is possible to express the "Sturm-Liouville" eigenvalue problem of the angular equation (8.1.27) as a matrix eigenvalue equation

$$MC_{lm}(c) = {}_sA_{lm}C_{lm}(c)\tag{8.2.14}$$

where the spheroidal expansion coefficients C_{lm} depend on the oblateness parameter $c = a\omega$ and the angular separation constants ${}_sA_{lm}$ have to be determined as eigenvalues of the diagonal matrix M that depends on expansion coefficients occurring when (8.2.13) is substituted into (8.1.27).

Cook and Zalutskiy use the Mathematica eigensystem solver to determine ${}_sA_{lm}$ from M . The calculation by Leaver's method relies on Newton's method having a quadratic convergence and being sensitive to initial guesses. However the spectral eigenvalue calculation feature an exponential convergence. A comparison for the $l = m = 2$ mode is shown in figure 8.1.

Further reading: [Zal14].

Figure 8.1: Convergence of the Cook's spectral method (green triangles) versus Leaver's continued fraction method (blue dots). Exemplified is the accuracy ΔA_{22} of the $l = m = 2$ angular separation constant, logarithmically plotted against the number of terms N in the expansion (8.2.13) for a Kerr Black Hole of nearly-extremal dimensionless spin $a = 0.995$ [Za114].

8.3 Berti data

Quasinormal Mode data computed with Leaver's method is available on the homepage⁵ of E. Berti. It was used to compare the $s = -2$ gravitational spectrum with the results obtained from fitting the ringdown part of the SXS waveforms. Figure 8.2 shows the format of the available data that includes multipoles from $l = 2$ to $l = 7$ while the individual files contain the Kerr parameter a , the real and imaginary part of the Quasinormal Mode frequency ω_R and ω_L as well as the complex angular separation constant A_{lm} . The details of the calculations can be found in [BCS09] and [BCW06].

Emanuele Berti
Associate Professor,
University of Mississippi

✉ Email
f Facebook
g+ Google+

Description	Reference(s)	Download
Schwarzschild QNM frequencies	arXiv:0905.2975	$s = \ell = 2$
Data format:	gr-qc/0512160	$s = \ell = 1$
$2M\omega_R, 2M\omega_I, \text{error}, n$		$s = \ell = 0$
Kerr QNM frequencies ($s = -2$)	arXiv:0905.2975	$\ell = 2$
Data format:	gr-qc/0512160	$\ell = 3$
$a/M, M\omega_R, M\omega_I, \text{Re}(A_{\ell m}), \text{Im}(A_{\ell m})$		$\ell = 4$
		$\ell = 5$
		$\ell = 6$
		$\ell = 7$
Kerr QNM frequencies ($s = -1$)	arXiv:0905.2975	$\ell = 1$
Data format:	gr-qc/0512160	$\ell = 2$
$a/M, M\omega_R, M\omega_I, \text{Re}(A_{\ell m}), \text{Im}(A_{\ell m})$		$\ell = 3$
		$\ell = 4$
		$\ell = 5$
		$\ell = 6$
		$\ell = 7$
Kerr QNM frequencies ($s = 0$)	arXiv:0905.2975	$\ell = 0$
Data format:	gr-qc/0512160	$\ell = 1$
$a/M, M\omega_R, M\omega_I, \text{Re}(A_{\ell m}), \text{Im}(A_{\ell m})$		$\ell = 2$
		$\ell = 3$
		$\ell = 4$
		$\ell = 5$
		$\ell = 6$

Figure 8.2: Quasinormal Mode data available at [BD]. Here only the $s = -2$ data (framed by the red rectangle) is used to compare with the ringdown fits extracted from the SXS data [SDB].

⁵<http://www.phy.olemiss.edu/~berti/ringdown> (6.4.2017)

8.4 Cook data

8.4.1 Degeneracy

Cook and Zalutskiy published [CZ14] their QNM data obtained by their spectral codes, a *KerrQNM package* and Polynomial roots calculator (*PolyRoots*)⁶ visualized as curves (parametrized by the Kerr spin parameter) in the complex QNM frequency plane where the frequency constitutes the x -axis and the inverse decay time the y -axis (shown in figure 8.2 below).

Figure 8.3: QNM data obtained by Cook and Zalutsky with their spectral *KerrQNM package* and Polynomial roots calculator (*PolyRoots*) [Zal14].

One can see how the degeneracy in the spherical harmonic multipole index m is increasingly lifted as the Kerr parameter approaches its maximum value of $a = 1$ where the situation is plotted. For each spherical harmonic multipole index l , the Schwarzschild modes lie on black dashed lines from which the colored curves originate. Each color corresponds to a different overtone index n that varies the damping or inverse decay time. While the real ω -axis is bound by the index l , the imaginary $1/\tau$ -axis is in general unbound as the damping is not constrained.

8.4.2 Purely imaginary frequencies

Besides the Kerr QNM boundary condition where the waves are purely ingoing at the Black Hole horizon and outgoing at infinity, there are other possible configurations where the waves travel in only one direction, either from the left or the right. Figure 8.4 sketches the three different boundary condition scenarios. Chandrasekhar was the first to notice that these purely outgoing or ingoing modes are "algebraically special" in the sense that they belong to a special class of solutions.

Figure 8.4: Three different boundary conditions in the Kerr perturbation problem. Total Transmission Mode Left (TTM_L), Quasi Normal Mode (QNM) and Total Transmission Mode Right (TTM_R) with waves differing in direction with respect to the Black Hole event horizon and infinity [Zal14].

⁶The package is available at <https://github.com/patim/Poly> (6.4.2017).

8.5 Comparison (own results)

This final section contains only own results.

8.5.1 SXS-Berti

The fundamental question to pose is "which Quasinormal Modes are excited at the end of a Binary Black Hole coalescence simulated by Numerical Relativity?" To examine this, 258 nonbroken SXS simulations are used to extract the ringdown fits (composing the phenomenological model presented in chapter 7 Modeling) from all 77 available modes yielding a total of 19866 individual fits. The complex frequencies (frequency ω and decay time τ of the ringdown) are then compared to the Berti data that was calculated by Leaver's continued fraction method.

Figure 8.5 shows both plotted together in the complex plane. It is apparent that mainly the fundamental mode (lowermost row) is excited. The plot below focuses on a specific SXS final spin $j_f = 0.5$, revealing that the dominant $(l, m) = (2, \pm 2)$ spherical SXS mode corresponds to the fundamental $(n, l, m) = (1, 2, 2)$ and $(n, l, m) = (1, 2, 0)$ spheroidal Quasinormal Berti mode as the darkest blue dots overlap with the appropriate red dots. Furthermore, the Quasinormal Modes with purely imaginary frequencies are obviously excited (see previous section).

The upper plot shows how the m -degeneracy is lifted with increasing spin as there are clusters splitting up. In the lower plot, groups of three dots are split, representing individual m -values.

Figure 8.5: Comparison of the QNMs extracted from the SXS simulations with Berti's data. All accessible SXS-QNMs are shown above, whereas the plot below focuses on a specific simulation with final spin $j_f = 0.5$.

In a next step, only the dominant $(l, m) = (2, 2)$ mode is analyzed depending on the final spin j_f . The Berti data can be fitted, yielding the QNM frequency

$$\Re(\sigma)(j_f) = \omega(j_f) = 1.1647j_f + 8.912810^{-5} - 0.92785j_f^2$$

with

$$R^2 = 0.9774$$

and the QNM decay time

$$\Im(\sigma)(j_f) = -1/\tau(j_f) = -0.21548j_f - 1.357910^{-5} + 0.23001j_f^2$$

with

$$R^2 = 0.9712.$$

Figure 8.6 shows a comparison of the $(l, m) = (2, 2)$ mode SXS ringdown frequency and decay time with the $(n, l, m) = (1, 2, 2)$ QNM Berti data. The course of the curves seems to be similar, but shifted in y direction indicating that the SXS spherical $(l, m) = (2, 2)$ mode does not exactly correspond to the Berti spheroidal $(n, l, m) = (1, 2, 2)$ mode it is compared to. It is however the closest match.

Figure 8.6: Comparison of the 2,2-mode QNM frequency (above) and decay time (below) extracted from the SXS simulations with Berti's data.

Figure 8.7 illustrates the increase in (real) ringdown frequency with the spherical multipole index l as predicted by Perturbation theory. Each differently colored cluster represents a specific $l = m \geq 2$ mode where all accessible SXS simulations are included varying in the final spin j_f . The fundamental QNM mode (lowermost row) is still predominantly excited, but with increasing l , there are more and more points reaching into the higher overtones that decay faster as their damping $1/\tau$ is higher.

Figure 8.7: QNMs from SXS modes $l = 2$ to $l = 6$ compared to Berti QNMs with varying final spin $j_f \in [0, 1]$.

Chapter 9

Visualization

Spheroidal isosurfaces [Fal01] (left) and Kerr tendexes [Zim12] (right).

The visualization of gravitational waves was in the past mostly concerned with the wave propagation and the effects on testparticles when the spacetime is stretched or squeezed by the wave. The spacetime is usually represented by the well known two-dimensional fabric, a grid that shows geodesics to demonstrate how spacial distances change in the presence of matter (and energy). By integrating the geodesic equation one obtains the path of particles or light rays that can be used for four-dimensional ray-tracing visualizations. Recently, new tools for visualizing the spacetime curvature have been developed by Kip Thorne's group [Owe11, Nic12, Zha12, Zim12, PBN13].

The tendex/vortex formalism uses tidal tendexes and frame-drag vortexes to visualize how spacetime is deformed by static and rotating Black Holes. This can be especially useful when the large data of compact binary coalescence simulations is examined and physically interpreted. The method also allows to uncover dualities looking at gravitational waves and quasinormal modes. Tidal tendexes and frame-drag vortexes are constructed by contractions of the Weyl curvature tensor, the traceless part of the Riemann tensor that is the remaining nonzero part in vacuum describing the propagation of gravitational waves.

The tendex and vortex fields are analogous to electromagnetic fields - the former field can be regarded as the electric, the latter as the magnetic part of the Weyl tensor and there even are Maxwell-like equations that govern the static and dynamic behavior of the gravitational fields. Price, Belcher and Nichols recently wrote a didactical treatment on a comparison of electromagnetic and gravitational radiation [PBN13]. Moreover, as the gravitational wave content of the numerical simulations is usually decomposed into spin-weighted spherical harmonics while the quasinormal mode data is given in spin-weighted spheroidal harmonics, there is more in the context of gravitational waves that needs better visualization tools. Before reviewing some of the most important results and functionality of the techniques just mentioned, this chapter begins by looking at the different pictures that can be used to describe the mediation of gravitational information. Just as in the electromagnetic case light can be regarded in the wave particle duality, as rays captured by geometric optics and radiation examined by multipole calculations, similar considerations can be done in the gravitational case.

The visualization of Binary Black Hole coalescence dynamics has recently improved by various features. Horizon tendexes and vortexes projected on an event or apparent horizon help in understanding the merger processes. Among the discoveries are that Black Holes colliding head-on have their horizon vorticities (positive and negative) oscillate between two sides of the remnant Black Hole vanishing eventually by the Quasinormal Mode radiation. The visualization of the simulation data can also show how the shape of the horizons is developing at merger by illustrating the tidal effects. Last but not least, as mentioned in a previous chapter, the SXS horizon data includes orbital trajectories and the time evolution of the spins of the individual Black Holes and a common apparent horizon that can be visualized together with the dimensionless Ricci scalar plotted on the spheres representing the Black Holes. This is especially useful for examinations of the chaotic behavior of precessing binaries.

9.1 Raytracing

Raytracing is a method in computer graphics to realistically display virtual objects in a scene. This is done by calculating the two-dimensional projection of a three-dimensional scene where virtual light rays are cast from an imaginary camera or eye and traced to the objects. The computer algorithm is determining intersection points of the light rays with light sources (self-luminous) or objects (lighted by a light source or another reflecting object)¹. If a ray (primary ray, camera or eye ray) hits an object, it can be absorbed, reflected or refracted. In case of reflection, the direction of a new ray (secondary ray, object ray) has to be identified considering geometrical criteria (primary ray's angle of impact) or physical criteria (surface quality of the material). Moreover it is possible to include rare cases of fluorescence where the surface of an object has absorbed a certain part of the light and re-emits it with a larger wavelength (less energy) in a random direction. In order to minimize computing time, it is important to avoid tracing unnecessary rays which do not have an impact on the image. The procedure can work backwardly (eye-based) or forwardly (light-based) depending on whether the rays are cast starting from the camera or light source. In addition, a bidirectional raytracing can be performed where rays are calculated from both sides and brought together by a connecting ray. The raytracing method is capable of simulating optical effects such as reflection, refraction, dispersion etc. Using the approximation of geometric (ray) optics all wave phenomena are neglected. Compared to other techniques of computer graphics, the ray tracing method is able to yield a higher degree of photorealism. Unfortunately this is at the cost of increased computing time making ray tracing predominantly interesting for applications where pre-rendering (computation prior to playing the film) is possible such as special effects in movies and television. Real-time computations used in computer games and interactive applications require fast and efficient algorithms at the expense of photo quality. The use of raytracing is further enhanced by the increase of computational power. If sufficient processing capacity is available, the raytracing algorithm is even able to include external model data from photography or material properties of the objects that are represented.

Figure 9.1: Visualization of a light ray around a Black Hole (left) and Gravitational Waves passing through matter (right) [Mül06, Mun10].

The relativistic raytracing has to take into account that spacetime is curved and intertwined. While in the classic case, differences in the light transit times can be neglected, in the relativistic scenario, the rays take diverse amounts of time to reach the individual objects and consequently have to be transferred into the appropriate coordinate (rest) system accounting for their proper time. Mappings become distorted due to relativistic (Lorentz) contractions occurring when objects are moved with speeds close to the speed of light. Additionally, the colors change as an effect of redshifts caused by the relative movement of camera and objects. Besides its application in research where astrophysical models are visually examined, the relativistic raytracing can be deployed in space-simulations produced for movies and computer games.

The next section presents an alternative method to visualize the spacetime curvature that relies on tensor field visualization.

¹The scene is comprised of all light sources and objects, yet excluding observer or camera.

9.2 Tensor Field Visualization

In Quantum Mechanics, we are dealing with wavefunctions $\Psi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ that represent the probability Ψ of finding matter or energy (a particle or field) at a particular moment of time t at a particular position in space \mathbf{x} . The problem can be represented by a **scalar field**. In Electrodynamics, the electric and magnetic fields are **vector fields** $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ that assign each point in time and space to a vector whose direction and magnitude are the field properties. In General Relativity, gravitational fields are described in terms of higher order (or rank) tensors such as the Riemann or Ricci curvature tensors (equation(2.1.62) and (2.1.64) in chapter 2 Basics). Visualizing **tensor fields** is in general a challenging task. A second-rank tensor, represented by a matrix, can be visualized by its eigenvectors and eigenvalues. If the matrix is symmetric, the eigenvalues are real and the corresponding eigenvectors orthogonal. Together they contain the full information of the tensor.

Among the methods available to visualize tensor fields are

- tensor field streamlines (integral curves along the direction of the eigenvectors)
- tensor field hyperstreamlines (colored tubes with elliptic cross section)
- tensor field topology (classifying types of degenerate points with infinitely many directions of the eigenvectors)
- tensor glyphs (visualizing degrees of freedom and their anisotropy)

9.2.1 Tensor Glyphs

Symmetric three-dimensional matrices can be visualized using ellipsoids where the three principal axes run along the directions of the orthogonal eigenvectors with the corresponding eigenvalues $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \lambda_3$ determining the anisotropy with measures (where $\lambda_{tot} = (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3)$)

$$c_l = (\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)/\lambda_{tot}, \quad c_p = 2(\lambda_2 - \lambda_3)/\lambda_{tot}, \quad c_s = 3\lambda_3/\lambda_{tot} \tag{9.2.1}$$

that can be visualized using cuboid, cylinder or superquadratic glyphs (see figure 9.2 below). Further reading: [Pei09, Schu10].

Figure 9.2: Different types of glyphs. The superquadratics (below) smoothen the discontinuity at $c_l = c_p$ and artificial orientation at $c_s = 1$ of the cylinder glyphs (above right) and avoid overemphasizing small differences in eigenvalues as the cuboid glyphs (above left) do [Pei09, Schu10].

9.3 Tidal tendexes and frame-drag vortexes

As mentioned in the introduction of this chapter, the visualization of nonlinear dynamics of curved spacetime has recently been advanced by a formalism that extracts tidal and frame-drag information out of the Weyl conformal curvature tensor. In vacuum (Black Holes without sources in the metric) the rank-4 Weyl tensor $C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$ is identical to the rank-4 Riemann tensor $R_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$ containing all the information about the curvature of spacetime. The static part of the Riemann tensor is absorbed in its trace, the rank-2 Ricci tensor $R_{\alpha\beta}$, while the dynamic part (containing gravitational wave content) forms the traceless Weyl tensor [Gou07]

$$C^\gamma{}_{\delta\alpha\beta} = R^\gamma{}_{\delta\alpha\beta} - \frac{1}{2} \left(R^\gamma{}_{\alpha} g_{\delta\beta} - R^\gamma{}_{\beta} g_{\delta\alpha} + R_{\delta\beta} \delta^\gamma{}_{\alpha} - R_{\delta\alpha} \delta^\gamma{}_{\beta} \right) - \frac{1}{6} R \left(g_{\delta\alpha} \delta^\gamma{}_{\beta} - g_{\delta\beta} \delta^\gamma{}_{\alpha} \right) \quad (9.3.1)$$

with $R = g^{ij} R_{ij} = R^j{}_j$ being the rank-0 Ricci curvature scalar, a further contraction of the Ricci tensor. From the above definition follows that

$$C^\mu{}_{\alpha\mu\beta} = 0 \quad (9.3.2)$$

and by applying the symmetry properties of the Riemann tensor one can derive the tracelessness of the Weyl tensor that is the only nonzero part of the Riemann tensor in free space.

By symmetry, the $4^4 = 256$ components of the Riemann tensor reduce to 20 where 10 enter the Ricci tensor and are fixed by Einstein's field equations. The other 10 are allocated to the Weyl tensor and can be interpreted in terms of tidal and frame-drag effects in spacetime. In numerical relativity simulations (e.g. Binary Black Hole coalescence), spacetime is split into space and time - as described in chapter 5 Simulation. When applying this 3+1 Decomposition to construct spacial hypersurfaces (foliations) that evolve in time, the Weyl tensor splits into two spatial components (irreducible parts)

$$\mathcal{E}_{jk} = C_{\hat{0}j\hat{0}k} \quad (9.3.3)$$

describing tidal gravity and

$$\mathcal{B}_{jk} = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{jpk} C^{pq}{}_{\hat{0}\hat{0}} \quad (9.3.4)$$

describing differential dragging of inertial frames.

The indices correspond to an "orthonormal observer" reference frame moving perpendicularly to the spacial slices. $\hat{0}$ is their time component and ϵ_{jpk} the spatial Levi-Civita tensor. In analogy to electromagnetism they are often referred to as "electric" and "magnetic" part of the Weyl tensor. An important difference is that the electromagnetic field is described by rank-1 vectors E_i and B_i , whereas the gravitational field is thus described by rank-2 tensors (matrices) with 9 entries in 3D space. Due to symmetry and tracelessness, the number of components is reduced to 5 and this way, 5 of the 10 independent Weyl tensor components can enter its electric and 5 the magnetic part.

Having constructed \mathcal{E}_{jk} and \mathcal{B}_{jk} by contracting $C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$, the tangential integral curves (eigenlines) along the three eigenvectors of the electric part \mathcal{E}_{jk} are interpreted as paths along which stretching or squeezing of spacetime occurs - they are called tendex lines (from the Latin "tendere" = "to stretch"). Similarly, the three eigenvectors of the magnetic part \mathcal{B}_{jk} are interpreted as paths along which clockwise or counterclockwise twisting occurs - they are called vortex lines (from the Latin "vertere" = "to rotate"). The corresponding eigenvalues of the electric and magnetic tensor are called tendicity and vorticity, being a measure of the strenghts of the stretching (negative), squeezing (positive), counterclockwise (negative) or clockwise rotation (positive). Regions of large tendicity or vorticity (each positive or negative) can be graphically marked as tendexes or vortexes (each positive or negative).

If two orthogonal observers are separated by a tiny spatial vector ξ , the relative acceleration (as a result of tidal forces)

$$\Delta a_j = -\mathcal{E}_{jk} \xi^k \quad (9.3.5)$$

is captured by the electric field tensor that can be regarded as the tidal field.

A gyroscope at the tip of ξ precesses (as a result of frame-dragging) relative to an inertial frame at the tail with an angular velocity

$$\Delta\Omega_j = \mathcal{B}_{jk}\xi^k \tag{9.3.6}$$

captured by the magnetic field tensor that can be regarded as the frame-drag field. Further reading: [Owe11].

Invariants of Tendex and Vortex Fields

The tidal tendex and frame-drag vortex fields are coordinate-dependent. In order to obtain them, the Weyl-tensor has to be contracted with a tetrad (four-dimensional coordinate basis). However it is possible to find invariants - this will be a first glimpse of the analogies between gravitation and electromagnetism that will be discussed in the next section.

In Maxwell's **electromagnetism**, the quantities

$$\mathcal{I}_1^{\text{EM}} \equiv E^2 - B^2, \quad \mathcal{I}_2^{\text{EM}} \equiv EB \cos\theta_{\perp EB} \tag{9.3.7}$$

constructed from the electric field \mathbf{E} and magnetic field \mathbf{B} vectors are invariant under a special relativistic coordinate transformation.

In Einstein's **gravitation**, the quantities

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I} &\equiv \frac{1}{2}(\mathcal{E}_{ij}\mathcal{E}^{ij} - \mathcal{B}_{ij}\mathcal{B}^{ij}) + i\mathcal{E}_{ij}\mathcal{B}^{ij} \\ \mathcal{J} &\equiv \left(-\frac{1}{6}\mathcal{E}^i{}_j\mathcal{E}^j{}_k\mathcal{E}^k{}_i + \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{E}^i{}_j\mathcal{B}^j{}_k\mathcal{B}^k{}_i\right) + i\left(\frac{1}{6}\mathcal{B}^i{}_j\mathcal{B}^j{}_k\mathcal{B}^k{}_i - \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{B}^i{}_j\mathcal{E}^j{}_k\mathcal{E}^k{}_i\right) \end{aligned} \tag{9.3.8}$$

constructed from the tidal field \mathcal{E} and frame-drag field \mathcal{B} tensors are invariant under a general relativistic coordinate transformation.

The invariants of electromagnetism and gravitation are especially useful to check calculations where the coordinate transformations (change of the observer position) have to preserve them.

Further reading: [DB12].

Figure 9.3: Tendex lines outside a spherically symmetric nonrotating mass (left) and vortex lines around a spherically symmetric nonrotating mass (right) together with their effect on observers. Blue lines have positive tendicity or vorticity and squeeze or produce a clockwise differential precession of gyroscopes while red lines have negative tendicity or vorticity and stretch or produce a counterclockwise differential precession of gyroscopes [Nic12].

9.3.1 Electromagnetic vs. gravitational radiation

The tendex/vortex formalism can be useful for a comparison of electromagnetic and gravitational radiation. This is the first application presented here based on the didactical treatment of Price, Belcher and Nichols [PBN13]. The nature of electromagnetic and gravitational fields (in linearized General Relativity) is compared both mathematically and visually by transferring the powerful tool of lines of force / fields from the former to the latter. The gravitational "lines of fields" can be adopted by the tendex/vortex (eigen)lines, the integral curves along the eigenvectors $\mathcal{E}_{jk}v^k = \lambda v^k$ and $\mathcal{B}_{jk}v^k = \lambda v^k$ of the electric and magnetic field tensor. As for gravitational radiation there is no monopole or dipole contribution (lack of mass and momentum conservation in contrast to the electromagnetic case), the first multipole moment that can be compared between the two types of radiation is the quadrupolar. Therefore, the fields of static and dynamic (oscillating) electromagnetic and gravitational point quadrupoles are computed. Recall that radiation is evoked by time varying sources of charge (electromagnetic) and mass (gravitational). While similar behavior in both the near and the far fields is observed, there are some differences in the meaning of field line motion and the flow of energy.

Acceleration of charge and mass A starting point for finding a way to compare electromagnetic and gravitational fields can be to consider the forces due to accelerations of charges and masses that are exposed to the fields.

In the electromagnetic case, it is the well known Lorentz force coming along with an acceleration acting on a point particle of mass m and charge q

$$\mathbf{a} = \frac{q}{m} (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}), \quad (9.3.9)$$

where \mathbf{v} is the velocity and \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} are the electric and magnetic field vectors.

In index notation, this can be written in terms of the permutation (Levi-Civita) tensor ϵ_{ijk}

$$a^j = \frac{q}{m} (E^j + \epsilon_{jkp} v^k B^p). \quad (9.3.10)$$

In the gravitational case, astonishingly, a similar expression can be found for two point particles separated by a small displacement \mathbf{s} , moving with a relative velocity \mathbf{v}

$$\frac{d^2 s^j}{dt^2} = a^j = -\mathcal{E}_{jk} s^k - 2\epsilon_{jkp} \mathcal{B}_{pm} v^k s^m \quad (9.3.11)$$

in terms of the gravitational field tensors \mathcal{E}_{ij} and \mathcal{B}_{ij} .

Maxwell's equations and Maxwell-like relations Next thing is to note that there is also a formal similarity in the static and dynamic field equations for the electromagnetic field vectors (\mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B}) and the gravitational field tensors (\mathcal{E}_{ij} and \mathcal{B}_{ij}). The well-known electromagnetic Maxwell equations are

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} &= 0, & \nabla \times \mathbf{E} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} &= 0, \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{B} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} &= 0, & \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9.3.12)$$

and in index notation, again using the Levi-Civita permutation tensor ϵ_{ijk}

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial E_j}{\partial x^j} &= 0, & \epsilon_{ijk} \frac{\partial E_k}{\partial x^j} + \frac{\partial B_i}{\partial t} &= 0, \\ \epsilon_{ijk} \frac{\partial B_k}{\partial x^j} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial E_i}{\partial t} &= 0, & \frac{\partial B_j}{\partial x^j} &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (9.3.13)$$

Again, surprisingly, similar expressions for the gravitational fields have been found arising from the Bianchi identities for the Riemann tensor [BS10]

$$\nabla_e R_{abcd} + \nabla_d R_{abec} + \nabla_c R_{abde} = 0 \quad (9.3.14)$$

relying on the fact that the gravitational field tensors are symmetric and traceless (outside sources)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_{jk} &= \mathcal{E}_{kj}, & \mathcal{B}_{jk} &= \mathcal{B}_{kj}, \\ \mathcal{E}_{kk} &= 0, & \mathcal{B}_{kk} &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (9.3.15)$$

leading to the Maxwell-like relations

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{E}_{jk}}{\partial x^j} &= 0, & \frac{1}{2} \left(\epsilon_{pjk} \frac{\partial \mathcal{E}_{qk}}{\partial x^j} + \epsilon_{qjk} \frac{\partial \mathcal{E}_{pk}}{\partial x^j} \right) + \frac{\partial \mathcal{B}_{pq}}{\partial t} &= 0, \\ \frac{1}{2} \left(\epsilon_{pjk} \frac{\partial \mathcal{B}_{qk}}{\partial x^j} + \epsilon_{qjk} \frac{\partial \mathcal{B}_{pk}}{\partial x^j} \right) - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \mathcal{E}_{pq}}{\partial t} &= 0, & \frac{\partial \mathcal{B}_{jk}}{\partial x^j} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9.3.16)$$

which can also be expressed in terms of a special divergence ∇ and curl \times

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \mathcal{E} &= 0 & \nabla \times \mathcal{E} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{B}}{\partial t} &= 0 \\ \nabla \times \mathcal{B} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \mathcal{E}}{\partial t} &= 0 & \nabla \cdot \mathcal{B} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9.3.17)$$

that takes into account the additional dimension due to the tensorial nature of the fields.

Electromagnetic and gravitational point quadrupole Figure 9.4 sketches the scenario of an electromagnetic and gravitational quadrupole. In the following, expressions for the static and dynamic electromagnetic and gravitational fields will be presented - in the electromagnetic case as components of the electric E and magnetic B field vectors and in the gravitational case as components of the "electric" \mathcal{E} and "magnetic" \mathcal{B} parts of the Weyl curvature tensor. The electromagnetic field lines or gravitational eigenlines are visualized using the Line Integral Convolution (LIC) method of Cabral and Leedom [CL93] where the "brightness or darkness of pixels is correlated along field lines" [PBN13] and its extension as Dynamic Line Integral Convolution (DLIC) developed by Sunquist [Sun03].

Figure 9.4: Electromagnetic (left) and gravitational (right) quadrupole where charges or masses are placed along a z -axis [PBN13].

Static electromagnetic fields generated by a static electric quadrupole can be expressed in spherical coordinates (r, θ, φ) as

$$E_r = \frac{6Q}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r^4} \left(\frac{3}{2} \cos^2 \theta - \frac{1}{2} \right), \quad E_\theta = \frac{6Q}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r^4} \cos \theta \sin \theta \quad (9.3.18)$$

corresponding to the electrostatic potential

$$\Phi_e = \frac{Q}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r^3} (3 \cos^2 \theta - 1). \quad (9.3.19)$$

Static gravitational fields generated by a static gravitational quadrupole are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{E}_{rr} &= -\frac{12GQ}{r^5}(3\cos^2\theta - 1), \\ \mathcal{E}_{r\theta} &= -\frac{24GQ}{r^5}\sin\theta\cos\theta, \\ \mathcal{E}_{\phi\phi} - \mathcal{E}_{\theta\theta} &= \frac{6GQ}{r^5}\sin^2\theta,\end{aligned}\tag{9.3.20}$$

corresponding to the gravitational potential

$$\Phi_g = -\frac{GQ}{r^3}(3\cos^2\theta - 1)\tag{9.3.21}$$

Dynamic electromagnetic fields generated by an oscillating electric quadrupole can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}E_r &= -\frac{Qk^2}{2\pi\epsilon_0 r^2} \left[\cos(kr - \omega t) \left(1 - \frac{3}{k^2 r^2} \right) - \frac{3}{kr} \sin(kr - \omega t) \right] \left(\frac{3}{2} \cos^2\theta - \frac{1}{2} \right), \\ E_\theta &= -\frac{Qk^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r^2} \left[\sin(kr - \omega t) \left(kr - \frac{6}{kr} \right) + \left(3 - \frac{6}{k^2 r^2} \right) \cos(kr - \omega t) \right] \cos\theta \sin\theta, \\ B_\phi &= -\frac{Qk^3}{4\pi\epsilon_0 cr} \left[\sin(kr - \omega t) \left(1 - \frac{1}{3k^2 r^2} \right) + \frac{3}{kr} \cos(kr - \omega t) \right] \cos\theta \sin\theta,\end{aligned}\tag{9.3.22}$$

where k is the spatial frequency given by the dispersion relation $k = \omega/c$. The fields are produced by the time variation of the quadrupole moment

$$Q(t) = qd_0^2 + 2qd_0\Delta d \cos\omega t + q(\Delta d \cos\omega t)^2\tag{9.3.23}$$

while the distances of the charge oscillate as

$$d(t) = d_0 + \Delta d \cos\omega t.\tag{9.3.24}$$

Dynamic gravitational fields generated by an oscillating gravitational quadrupole are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{E}_{rr} &= -\frac{4GQk^2}{r^3} \left[\left(-1 + \frac{3}{k^2 r^2} \right) \cos(kr - \omega t) + \frac{3\sin(kr - \omega t)}{kr} \right] (3\cos^2\theta - 1), \\ \mathcal{E}_{r\theta} &= -\frac{4GQk^2}{r^3} \left[\left(\frac{6}{(kr)^2} - 3 \right) \cos(kr - \omega t) - \left(kr - \frac{6}{kr} \right) \sin(kr - \omega t) \right] \sin\theta \cos\theta, \\ \mathcal{B}_{r\phi} &= -\frac{4GQk^2}{r^3} \left[-3\cos(kr - \omega t) - \left(kr - \frac{3}{kr} \right) \sin(kr - \omega t) \right] \sin\theta \cos\theta, \\ \mathcal{E}_{\phi\phi} - \mathcal{E}_{\theta\theta} &= -\frac{2GQk^2}{r^3} \left[\left(-\frac{3}{(kr)^2} + 3 - (kr)^2 \right) \cos(kr - \omega t) - \left(\frac{3}{kr} - 2kr \right) \sin(kr - \omega t) \right] \sin^2\theta, \\ \mathcal{B}_{\theta\phi} &= -\frac{GQk^2}{cr^3} \left[(-3 + (kr)^2) \cos(kr - \omega t) - \left(-\frac{3}{kr} + 2kr \right) \sin(kr - \omega t) \right] \sin^2\theta.\end{aligned}\tag{9.3.25}$$

Figures 9.5 and 9.6 present visualizations using LIC or DLIC. The dynamic visualization is just a snapshot at $t = 0$. A whole radiation period is available online² as a movie sequence together with the static pictures.

Further reading: [PBN13].

The remainder of this thesis will treat implementations of the tendex/vortex formalism for Gravitational Waves around static and dynamic Black Holes in the Schwarzschild and Kerr metric as well as their applications to the visualization of the SXS simulation data. Furthermore, the ringdown radiation and Quasinormal Mode angular distribution will be discussed comparing spherical with spheroidal harmonics.

²The material can be found at <http://web.mit.edu/viz/gravrad/index.html> (10.4.2017).

Figure 9.5: Static (left) and dynamic (right) electromagnetic quadrupole field lines visualized using [Dynamic] Line Integral Convolution ([D]LIC) [PBN13].

Figure 9.6: Static (above) and dynamic (below) gravitational quadrupole eigenlines visualized using [Dynamic] Line Integral Convolution ([D]LIC) [PBN13].

9.3.2 Gravitational Waves

A plane Gravitational Wave can be described using linearized gravity. In an asymptotically flat Minkowski background metric, the "electric" (tidal) and "magnetic" (frame-drag) part of the Weyl tensor can be expressed using the transverse-traceless (TT) gauge as

$$\mathcal{E}_{ij} = -\frac{1}{2}\partial_0^2 h_{ij}, \quad \mathcal{B}_{ij} = -\frac{1}{2}\epsilon_i^{pq} n_p \partial_0^2 h_{qj} \quad (9.3.26)$$

in terms of the general polarization tensor h_{ij} and normal vector n_p of the Gravitational Wave or directly in terms of the two Gravitational Wave polarization mode tensors e_{ij}^+ and e_{ij}^\times as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_{ij} &= -\frac{1}{2}(\ddot{h}_+ e_{ij}^+ + \ddot{h}_\times e_{ij}^\times), \\ \mathcal{B}_{ij} &= -\frac{1}{2}(\ddot{h}_+ e_{ij}^\times - \ddot{h}_\times e_{ij}^+), \end{aligned} \quad (9.3.27)$$

where h_+ and h_\times are the usual polarization amplitudes.

In a spatial orthonormal basis (e_1, e_2, e_3), the tensor can be conveniently expressed in the simple matrix form

$$\mathcal{E} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\begin{array}{c|cc} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \hline 0 & -\ddot{h}_+ & -\ddot{h}_\times \\ 0 & -\ddot{h}_\times & \ddot{h}_+ \end{array} \right) \quad (9.3.28a)$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\begin{array}{c|cc} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \hline 0 & \ddot{h}_\times & -\ddot{h}_+ \\ 0 & -\ddot{h}_+ & -\ddot{h}_\times \end{array} \right) \quad (9.3.28b)$$

Furthermore, using the Newman-Penrose formalism (see chapter 6 Extraction), one can construct a (complex) null tetrad

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{l} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\mathbf{e}_0 + \mathbf{e}_1), & \mathbf{n} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\mathbf{e}_0 - \mathbf{e}_1), \\ \mathbf{m} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\mathbf{e}_2 + i\mathbf{e}_3), & \mathbf{m}^* &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\mathbf{e}_2 - i\mathbf{e}_3) \end{aligned} \quad (9.3.29)$$

where \mathbf{l} is along the propagation direction of the Gravitational Wave. This allows for computing the NP curvature scalar that describes outgoing gravitational radiation

$$\Psi_4 = C_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} n^\mu m^{*\nu} n^\rho m^{*\sigma} = -\ddot{h}_+ + i\ddot{h}_\times \quad (9.3.30)$$

and rewriting the matrix in terms of Ψ_4 as

$$\mathcal{E} + i\mathcal{B} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\begin{array}{c|cc} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \hline 0 & \Psi_4 & i\Psi_4 \\ 0 & i\Psi_4 & -\Psi_4 \end{array} \right). \quad (9.3.31)$$

The eigenvalues of both the tidal field \mathcal{E} and frame-drag field \mathcal{B} , the "tendicity" and "vorticity", can then simply be expressed as

$$\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\ddot{h}_+^2 + \ddot{h}_\times^2} = \frac{1}{2}|\Psi_4| \quad (9.3.32)$$

in analogy to plane electromagnetic waves, where the magnitudes of the electric and magnetic field vectors

$$|\mathbf{E}| = |\mathbf{B}| = \sqrt{h_a^2 + h_b^2} \quad (9.3.33)$$

are similarly given in terms of the electromagnetic polarization amplitudes h_a and h_b . Finally, the two transverse eigenvector meshes of \mathcal{E} and \mathcal{B} show a $\pi/4$ angle, just as the directions of the Gravitational plus and cross mode (see chapter 2 Basics).

Figure 9.7 and 9.8 illustrate the geometry of the tendex and vortex lines of a plane Gravitational Wave and the gravitational radiation projected on a sphere as expected to be generated by a merger of two Black Hole colliding head-on along the z -axis.

Further reading: [Nic12].

Figure 9.7: Gravitational Wave tendex lines (left) and vortex lines (right) projected on a plane. The blue (dashed) lines represent positive tendicity or vorticity (squeezing or clockwise precession) while the red (solid) lines correspond to negative tendicity or vorticity (stretching or counterclockwise precession). The wave is traveling along the z direction (out of the plane). The two scenarios can be identified with the two different polarization modes (plus or cross) and it is shown that the sign (blue or red) is changed together with the mode [Nic12].

Figure 9.8: Gravitational Wave tendex lines (left) and vortex lines (right) projected on a sphere as expected to be produced by a merger of two Black Hole colliding head-on along the z -axis. While the colors are the same as in figure 9.7, their intensity is proportional to the strength of the corresponding tendicity or vorticity that varies over the sphere depending on the dominant spin-weighted spherical harmonic mode ${}_{-2}Y_{2,0}(\theta, \varphi) \propto \sin^2 \theta$ and is obviously small at the poles [Nic12].

9.3.3 Stationary Black Holes

The next section presents expressions for the tidal and frame-drag fields of static Schwarzschild and rotating Kerr Black Holes that can be visualized using tendicity/vorticity (eigenvalues) or tendex/vortex lines (eigenvectors).

Horizon tendicity and vorticity

In Black Hole perturbation theory (BHPT) and Numerical Relativity (NR), we are often only interested in the Black Hole exterior. In many simulations, as for example those performed by the Spectral Einstein Code (SpEC) available in the SXS database (see chapter 5 Simulation), the region inside the event horizon is "excised" from the computational and solution domain.

Yet, it is instructive to examine the region close to the Black Hole by defining a spacelike surface penetrating the horizon that provides information in terms of quasilocal quantities describing the tendicity and vorticity of the excised interior. This leads to the definition of the "horizon tendicity" and "horizon vorticity"

$$\mathcal{E}_{NN} = \mathcal{E}_{ij}N^iN^j, \quad \mathcal{B}_{NN} = \mathcal{B}_{ij}N^iN^j \quad (9.3.34)$$

that depend on a hypersurface-normal observer, moving with four-velocity \mathbf{u} through the event horizon with inward pointing normal vector \mathbf{N} orthogonal to \mathbf{u} and two other orthonormal basis vectors \mathbf{e}_2 and \mathbf{e}_3 . All four vectors together form an orthonormal tetrad $(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{N}, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3)$ from which the Newman-Penrose null tetrad

$$\mathbf{l} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{N}), \quad \mathbf{n} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{N}), \quad \mathbf{m} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\mathbf{e}_2 + i\mathbf{e}_3) \quad (9.3.35)$$

can be constructed that enables a contraction to the Weyl scalar

$$\Psi_2 = C_{lmm^*n} = (\mathcal{E}_{NN} + i\mathcal{E}_{NN})/2. \quad (9.3.36)$$

Penrose and Rindler [PR84] defined a complex curvature of a two-surface as

$$\mathcal{K} = \frac{1}{4}(\mathcal{R} + i\mathcal{X}) = -\Psi_2 + \mu\rho - \lambda\sigma, \quad (9.3.37)$$

in terms of the spin coefficients $\lambda, \mu, \rho, \sigma$.

The horizon tendicity and vorticity can then be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_{NN} &= -\mathcal{R}/2 + 2\Re(\mu\rho - \lambda\sigma), \\ \mathcal{B}_{NN} &= -\mathcal{X}/2 + 2\Im(\mu\rho - \lambda\sigma). \end{aligned} \quad (9.3.38)$$

For a stationary Black Hole, two of the spin coefficients $\rho = \sigma = 0$ vanish, and we are left with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_{NN} &= -\mathcal{R}/2, \\ \mathcal{B}_{NN} &= -\mathcal{X}/2. \end{aligned} \quad (9.3.39)$$

Schwarzschild Black Hole

Recall the Schwarzschild metric line element in Eddington-Finkelstein (EF) coordinates

$$ds^2 = -\left(1 - \frac{2M}{r}\right) d\tilde{t}^2 + \frac{4M}{r} d\tilde{t}dr + \left(1 + \frac{2M}{r}\right) dr^2 + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2 \quad (9.3.40)$$

with the ingoing EF-time

$$\tilde{t} = t + 2M \ln|r/2M - 1| \quad (9.3.41)$$

which is constant for the simplest horizon penetrating slices that can be a condition for the lapse and shift in Numerical Relativity simulations.

An observer measuring the tidal and frame-drag fields lying on a slice of constant \tilde{t} has a four-velocity

$$\mathbf{u} = -\alpha_{\text{EF}} \nabla \tilde{t}, \quad \alpha_{\text{EF}} = 1/\sqrt{1 + 2M/r} \quad (9.3.42)$$

with the "normalizing lapse function" α_{EF} .

The observer then carries the tetrad

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + 2M/r}} \left[\left(1 + \frac{2M}{r}\right) \partial_{\tilde{t}} - \frac{2M}{r} \partial_r \right], \\ \mathbf{e}_{\hat{r}} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + 2M/r}} \partial_r, \quad \mathbf{e}_{\hat{\theta}} = \frac{1}{r} \partial_{\theta}, \quad \mathbf{e}_{\hat{\varphi}} = \frac{1}{r \sin \theta} \partial_{\varphi} \end{aligned} \quad (9.3.43)$$

and the nonzero components of the tidal field can be computed as

$$\mathcal{E}_{\hat{r}\hat{r}} = -\frac{2M}{r^3}, \quad \mathcal{E}_{\hat{\theta}\hat{\theta}} = \mathcal{E}_{\hat{\varphi}\hat{\varphi}} = \frac{M}{r^3}. \quad (9.3.44)$$

Since the tidal field is diagonal in this tetrad, the eigenvectors and eigenvalues are simply

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{V}_r^{\mathcal{E}} &= \mathbf{e}_{\hat{r}}, \quad \lambda_r = -\frac{2M}{r^3}, \\ \mathbf{V}_{\theta}^{\mathcal{E}} &= \mathbf{e}_{\hat{\theta}}, \quad \lambda_{\theta} = \frac{M}{r^3}, \\ \mathbf{V}_{\varphi}^{\mathcal{E}} &= \mathbf{e}_{\hat{\varphi}}, \quad \lambda_{\varphi} = \frac{M}{r^3}. \end{aligned} \quad (9.3.45)$$

Figure 9.10 (left) visualizes them as tendex lines around the nonrotating Schwarzschild Black Hole that are tangential to the orthonormal basis vectors $\mathbf{e}_{\hat{r}}$, $\mathbf{e}_{\hat{\theta}}$ and $\mathbf{e}_{\hat{\varphi}}$. While the radial eigenvalues (tendicities) are negative and correspond to stretching, the angular eigenvalues (tendicities) are positive and correspond to squeezing.

Slowly rotating Kerr Black Hole

When the Black Hole gains a small spin, characterized by the dimensionless parameter $a = J/M$, the metric obtains an additional off-diagonal term $g_{t\varphi}$ due to inertial frame-dragging effects, leading to the "Slow Kerr metric"

$$ds^2 = -\left(1 - \frac{2M}{r}\right) d\tilde{t}^2 + \frac{4M}{r} d\tilde{t}dr + \left(1 + \frac{2M}{r}\right) dr^2 + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\tilde{\varphi}^2 - \frac{4aM}{r} \sin^2 \theta d\tilde{t}d\tilde{\varphi} - 2a\sqrt{1 + 2M/r} \sin^2 \theta \quad (9.3.46)$$

where the coordinate transformation

$$\tilde{\varphi} = \varphi + (a/2M) \ln |1 - 2M/r| \quad (9.3.47)$$

has fixed the singularity of the Schwarzschild coordinate φ caused by the frame-dragging.

The observer moving orthogonally to the slices of constant \tilde{t} carries almost that same tetrad as in the Schwarzschild case (9.3.43) with the exception of $e_{\tilde{r}}$ being changed to

$$e_{\tilde{r}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + 2M/r}} \left[\partial_r + \frac{a}{r^2} (1 + 2M/r) \partial_{\tilde{\varphi}} \right]. \quad (9.3.48)$$

The slow rotation produces a frame-drag field

$$\mathcal{B}_{\tilde{r}\tilde{r}} = \frac{-6aM \cos \theta}{r^4}, \quad \mathcal{B}_{\tilde{r}\tilde{\theta}} = \mathcal{B}_{\tilde{\theta}\tilde{r}} = \frac{-3aM \sin \theta}{r^4 \sqrt{1 + 2M/r}}, \quad \mathcal{B}_{\tilde{\theta}\tilde{\theta}} = \mathcal{B}_{\tilde{\varphi}\tilde{\varphi}} = \frac{3aM \cos \theta}{r^4} \quad (9.3.49)$$

while the horizon vorticity is given by the radial component

$$\mathcal{B}_{NN} = \mathcal{B}_{\tilde{r}\tilde{r}} = \frac{-6aM \cos \theta}{r^4} \quad (9.3.50)$$

being negative in the north polar regions and positive in the south polar regions.

Furthermore, the eigenvectors (tendex lines) of the tidal field change to

$$\mathbf{V}_r^\mathcal{E} = e_{\tilde{r}} - \frac{2Ma \sin \theta}{r^2 \sqrt{1 + 2M/r}} e_{\tilde{\varphi}}, \quad \mathbf{V}_{\tilde{\varphi}}^\mathcal{E} = e_{\tilde{\varphi}} + \frac{2Ma \sin \theta}{r^2 \sqrt{1 + 2M/r}} e_{\tilde{r}}, \quad \mathbf{V}_{\tilde{\theta}}^\mathcal{E} = e_{\tilde{\theta}} \quad (9.3.51)$$

leaving the eigenvalues (tendicities) unchanged

$$\lambda_r = -\frac{2M}{r^3}, \quad \lambda_\theta = \frac{M}{r^3}, \quad \lambda_\varphi = \frac{M}{r^3}. \quad (9.3.52)$$

The Slow Kerr tendex and vortex lines are depicted in figure 9.9 below.

Figure 9.9: Tendex lines (left) and vortex lines (right) of a slowly spinning Kerr Black Hole [Zha12].

Rapidly rotating Kerr Black Hole

Recall that the Kerr metric in Boyer-Lindquist (BL) coordinates

$$ds^2 = - \left(1 - \frac{2Mr}{\Sigma} \right) dt^2 + \frac{\Sigma}{\Delta} dr^2 + \Sigma d\theta^2 + \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{\Sigma} A d\varphi^2 - \frac{4Mar \sin^2 \theta}{\Sigma} dt d\varphi \quad (9.3.53)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma &= r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta, \\ \Delta &= r^2 - 2Mr + a^2, \\ A &= (r^2 + a^2)^2 - a^2 \Delta \sin^2 \theta \end{aligned} \quad (9.3.54)$$

describes a rapidly rotating Black Hole with spin $a = J/M$.

There are four sets of spacetime coordinates that are frequently used in literature

- **Boyer-Lindquist coordinates** $\{t, r, \theta, \varphi\}$
(see section Black Holes in chapter 2 Basics).
- **Ingoing-Kerr coordinates** $\{\tilde{t}, r, \theta, \tilde{\varphi}\}$
as described in the previous Slow Kerr case.
Often \tilde{t} is replaced by the null coordinate $v = \tilde{t} + r$.
Curves of constant $v =$, $\theta =$ and $\tilde{\varphi}$ are ingoing null geodesics.
- **Quasi-Cartesian Kerr-Schild coordinates** $\{\tilde{t}, x, y, z\}$ and their cylindrical variant $\{\tilde{t}, \varpi, z, \varphi\}$ with

$$\begin{aligned} x + iy &= (r + ia)e^{i\tilde{\varphi}} \sin \theta, & z &= r \cos \theta, \\ \varpi &= \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} = \sqrt{r^2 + a^2} \sin^2 \theta, \\ \varphi &= \arctan(y/x) = \tilde{\varphi} + \arctan(a/r). \end{aligned} \quad (9.3.55)$$

- **Cook-Scheel harmonic coordinates** $\{\bar{r}t, \bar{r}x, \bar{y}, \bar{r}z\}$ with the Cook-Scheel time coordinate $\bar{r}t$ given by

$$\bar{r}t = \tilde{t} + 2M \ln \left| \frac{2M}{r - r_-} \right| \quad (9.3.56)$$

with the known expression for the horizons (event horizon r_+ and ergosphere r_-). The spatial coordinates are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} r x + i \bar{r} y &= [r - M + ia] e^{i\tilde{\varphi}} \sin(\theta), \\ r z &= [r - M] \cos(\theta). \end{aligned} \quad (9.3.57)$$

These various coordinates can be used in NR simulations where a numerical integrator generates the vortex lines, visualized in figure 9.10 (right). Further reading: [Zha12].

Figure 9.10: Tendex lines of a nonrotating Schwarzschild Black Hole (left) and vortex lines of a rotating Kerr Black Hole (right) with colors as in figure 9.7. The surface of the sphere, representing the Black Hole event horizon, is shaded according to its horizon vorticity \mathcal{B}_{NN} [Zha12].

9.3.4 Quasinormal Pulsations of Schwarzschild and Kerr Black Holes

Finally, the tendex-vortex formalism can be employed to visualize the spacetime curvature effects of Black Hole Quasinormal Modes (QNMs) as they have been described in chapter 8 Perturbation. Recall that the QNMs are classified by a radial quantum number n , spheroidal harmonic orders (l, m) and parity that is "even", "polar" or "electric" if a space inversion yields a perturbation factor of $(-1)^l$, or "odd", "axial" or "magnetic" if the factor is $(-1)^{l+1}$. The visualization of electric and magnetic parity perturbation reveals that there is a near duality (the upper two panels in figure 9.11 look almost the same) between modes of the same (n, l, m) . The tendex and vortex structures of electric modes are interchanged with vortex and tendex structures of magnetic modes. The duality is perfect for the complex eigenfrequencies and on the horizon and slightly broken in the equatorial plane of a nonspinning Black Hole. The breaking is increasing off-plane and as the spin gets larger, but surprisingly good even out of the plane for fast spinning Black Holes (the lower two panels in figure 9.11 look still very similar). Nichols et al. even showed [Zim12] that the visualization does not depend on the numerical slicing if they are produced by simulations. Unfortunately, the announced following paper on the actual implementation, that is simulating Quasinormal Mode tendexes and vortexes numerically or extracting full three-dimensional data from SXS simulations, is still missing up to date. The output of SXS simulations is still restrained to include³ only information about the horizon tendicity \mathcal{E}_{NN} and vorticity \mathcal{B}_{NN} that were introduced at the beginning of the last section. Luckily there are analytic expressions available for the dominant fundamental $(n, l, m) = (1, 2, 2)$ mode that will be presented at this point, prior to some possible visualizations.

The components of the **Electric-parity (2,2) mode tidal field** are

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{E}_{rr} &= \text{Re} [E_{1(e)} e^{-i\omega t} Y^{22}], \\ \mathcal{E}_{rA} &= \text{Re} [E_{2(e)} e^{-i\omega t} Y_A^{22}], \\ \mathcal{E}_{AB} &= \text{Re} \left[\left(-\frac{1}{2} E_{1(e)} \delta_{AB} Y^{22} + E_{3(e)} Y_{AB}^{22} \right) e^{-i\omega t} \right],\end{aligned}\tag{9.3.58}$$

where the angular indexes are $A, B \in \{\theta, \varphi\}$. The expression involves the scalar spherical harmonics Y^{lm} , vector spherical harmonics Y_A^{lm} , tensor spherical harmonics Y_{AB}^{lm} , the Kronecker delta δ_{AB} and the coefficients

$$\begin{aligned}E_{1(e)}(r) &= -\frac{3\mathcal{Z}}{2r^3}, \\ E_{2(e)}(r) &= \frac{[3M\alpha^2 - 2iM\omega(2r + 3M)] Z - \alpha^2 r(2r + 3M)Z'}{2r^4\alpha^2\sqrt{1 + 2M/r}}, \\ E_{3(e)}(r) &= \frac{1}{2r^4\alpha^4(r + 2M)} \left(\left[-\frac{3\alpha^2(3M^3 + 6M^2r + 4Mr^2 + 4r^3)(4M + r\alpha^2)}{(2r + 3M)^2} + \frac{4iM\omega r(3M^2 + 6Mr - 2r^2)}{(2r + 3M)} \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + \omega^2 r^3(4M + r\alpha^4) \right] Z + \alpha^2 r \left[\frac{(3M^2 + 6Mr - 2r^2)(4M + r\alpha^2)}{2r + 3M} - 4iM\omega r^2 \right] Z' \right),\end{aligned}\tag{9.3.59}$$

where a prime ' denotes a derivative with respect to r and

$$\mathcal{Z} = \left[\frac{\lambda^2(\lambda + 1)}{3M} + \frac{3M\alpha^2}{r(\lambda r + 3M)} \right] Z - \frac{Z_{,r^*}}{\lambda}\tag{9.3.60}$$

with

$$\alpha^2 = 1 - 2M/r, \quad \lambda = \frac{1}{2}(l - 1)(l + 2).\tag{9.3.61}$$

The Zerilli function Z can be derived from the eigenequation

$$\frac{d^2 Z}{dr_*^2} + \omega^2 Z = \mathcal{V}_z(r) Z\tag{9.3.62}$$

containing a second derivative with respect to the radial tortoise coordinate

$$r_* = r + 2M \ln(\alpha^2 r / 2M)\tag{9.3.63}$$

and the potential

$$\mathcal{V}_Z(r) = \alpha^2 \left[\frac{2\lambda^2(\lambda + 1)r^3 + 6\lambda^2 M r^2 + 18\lambda M^2 r + 18M^3}{r^3(\lambda r + 3M)^2} \right].\tag{9.3.64}$$

³The number of SXS simulations were a `HorizonsDump.h5` file is available is currently exceeding 100 and constantly increasing.

The components of the *Electric-parity (2,2) mode frame-drag field* are

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{B}_{rr} &= 0, \\ \mathcal{B}_{rA} &= \text{Re} [B_{1(e)} e^{-i\omega t} X_A^{22}], \\ \mathcal{B}_{AB} &= \text{Re} [B_{2(e)} e^{-i\omega t} X_{AB}^{22}]\end{aligned}\tag{9.3.65}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}B_{1(e)} &= \frac{[6M^2\alpha^2 - i\omega r^2(2r + 3M)] Z - 2Mr\alpha^2(2r + 3M)Z'}{2r^5\alpha^2\sqrt{1 + 2M/r}}, \\ B_{2(e)} &= \frac{1}{2r^4\alpha^4(2r + 3M)(r + 2M)} \left([-12M\alpha^2(M^2 + 4r\beta_1) - i\omega(r^2 + 4M^2)\beta_2 + 4M\omega^2r^3(2r + 3M)] Z \right. \\ &\quad \left. - r\alpha^2 [4M\beta_2 + i\omega r(2r + 3M)(r^2 + 4M^2)] Z' \right).\end{aligned}\tag{9.3.66}$$

The simplifying factors are defined by

$$\beta_1 = \frac{r^2 + Mr + M^2}{2r + 3M}, \quad \beta_2 = (2r^2 - 6Mr - 3M^2).\tag{9.3.67}$$

Similar expressions can be found for the magnetic-parity modes.

The **magnetic-parity vector and tensor harmonics** can be related to the spin-weighted spherical harmonics ${}_sY_{lm}$ by

$$\begin{aligned}X_A^{lm} &= -i\sqrt{\frac{l(l+1)}{2}}(-{}_1Y_{lm}m_A + {}_1Y_{lm}m_A^*), \\ X_{AB}^{lm} &= -i\frac{\sqrt{D}}{2}(-{}_2Y_{lm}m_Am_B - {}_2Y_{lm}m_A^*m_B^*),\end{aligned}\tag{9.3.68}$$

while for the **electric-parity vector and tensor harmonics** it holds that

$$\begin{aligned}Y_A^{lm} &= \sqrt{\frac{l(l+1)}{2}}(-{}_1Y_{lm}m_A - {}_1Y_{lm}m_A^*), \\ Y_{AB}^{lm} &= \frac{\sqrt{D}}{2}(-{}_2Y_{lm}m_Am_B + {}_2Y_{lm}m_A^*m_B^*).\end{aligned}\tag{9.3.69}$$

Here, the Teukolsky-Starobinsky constant for spin-weighted spherical harmonics is

$$D = (l+2)!/(l-2)!.\tag{9.3.70}$$

The Newman-Penrose tetrad vector is given by

$$\mathbf{m} = 2^{-1/2}(\mathbf{e}_\theta + i\mathbf{e}_\varphi), \quad \mathbf{m}^* = 2^{-1/2}(\mathbf{e}_\theta - i\mathbf{e}_\varphi)\tag{9.3.71}$$

meaning that

$$\begin{aligned}m_\theta &= 2^{-1/2}, & m_\varphi &= 2^{-1/2}i, \\ m_\theta^* &= 2^{-1/2}, & m_\varphi^* &= -2^{-1/2}i\end{aligned}\tag{9.3.72}$$

Figure 9.11, 9.12 and 9.13 show visualizations of the tendexes, vortexes as well as the horizon tendicity and vorticity of the (2,2) Quasinormal Mode.

Further reading: [Zim12].

Figure 9.11: Vortexes (left panels) and tendexes (right panels) of a nonrotating Schwarzschild Black Hole (upper panels) and rotating Kerr Black Hole (lower panels) with colors defined as for the lines in figure 9.7. The Black Hole metric is affected in the electric ($\delta\mathcal{B}$) or magnetic ($\delta\mathcal{E}$) part of the Weyl curvature tensor by a magnetic $(-1)^{l+1}$ or electric $(-1)^l$ parity perturbation in the dominant (2,2) mode. An almost perfect duality between magnetic parity vortex and electric parity tendex perturbations is revealed [Zim12].

Figure 9.12: Three-dimensional vortexes and tendexes caused by magnetic and electric parity perturbations of a Schwarzschild and Kerr Black Hole metric with formal properties as in figure 9.11. The off-white regions mark surfaces where the magnitudes have dropped to a specific percentages that is denoted [Zim12].

Figure 9.13: Perturbative Horizon tendencies ($\delta\mathcal{E}_{NN}$) and vorticities ($\delta\mathcal{B}_{NN}$) projected on a sphere for a dominant (2,2) Quasinormal Mode with electric and magnetic parity (see labels on the top) in a Schwarzschild (upper panels) and Kerr (lower panels) Black Hole background. The colors are defined as in figure 9.7 while the intensity is proportional to the strength of the tendency or vorticity [Zim12].

9.4 Quasinormal Modes (own results)

The final sections contain only own results, if not cited explicitly.

This section is concerned with the visualization of Quasinormal modes using spin-weighted spherical and spheroidal harmonics.

9.4.1 Spherical and Spheroidal Harmonics

While the SXS simulation output consists of waveforms that are provided in a gravitational ($s = -2$) spin-weighted *spherical* harmonic decomposition with $2 \leq l \leq 8$ and $-l \leq m \leq +l$, the Berti QNMs are given in a $s = -2$ (gravitational) spin-weighted *spheroidal* harmonic decomposition where $1 \leq n \leq 8$ and $2 \leq l \leq 7$ with $-l \leq m \leq +l$.

Gravitational Waves

As shown in the previous chapter 8 Perturbation, the ringdown part of a Binary Black Hole coalescence waveform can be written as an exponential decay (damped harmonic)

$$\psi_{lm}(t, \rho, \theta, \varphi) = M \frac{1}{\rho} A_{lm} \exp\left(i(\omega_{lm} + i/\tau_{lm})t + i\phi_{lm}(t=0)\right) {}_{-2}Y_{lm}(\vartheta, \varphi) \quad (9.4.1)$$

where ρ is the extraction radius of the Gravitational Wave, A_{lm} the merger amplitude, $\omega_{lm} + i/\tau_{lm}$ the complex frequency and $\phi_{lm}(t=0)$ the initial phase.

The angular dependence is incorporated within the gravitational ($s = -2$) spin-weighted spherical harmonics ${}_{-2}Y_{lm}(\vartheta, \varphi)$. Goldberg et al. found [Gol67] an explicit formula for an arbitrary spin-weight s

$${}_sY_{lm}(\theta, \varphi) = (-1)^m \sqrt{\frac{(l+m)!(l-m)!(2l+1)}{4\pi(l+s)!(l-s)!}} \sin^{2l}(\theta/2) \sum_{r=0}^{l-s} \binom{l-s}{r} \binom{l+s}{r+s-m} (-1)^{l-r-s} e^{im\varphi} \cot^{2r+s-m}(\theta/2) \quad (9.4.2)$$

that allows an easy computation with a Mathematica notebook available on the SXS page <http://www.black-holes.org/SpinWeightedSphericalHarmonics.nb> (24.4.2017).

Quasinormal Modes

Quasinormal Modes can be separated in their dependence on time t , extraction radius ρ and observer angles θ, φ decomposed in (n, l, m) as

$$\psi_{nlm}(t, \rho, \theta, \varphi) \sim h_{nlm}(t) R_{nlm}(\rho) S_{lm}(\theta, \varphi). \quad (9.4.3)$$

The time-dependence can be associated with the Binary Black Hole coalescence ringdown

$$h_{nlm}(t) = A_{nlm} \exp\left(i(\omega_{nlm} + i/\tau_{nlm})t\right) \quad (9.4.4)$$

while the radial solution (see chapter 8 Perturbation) yields

$$R_{nlm}(\rho) \sim (Ae^{ik\rho} + Be^{-ik\rho}). \quad (9.4.5)$$

Finally, the spin-weighted spheroidal harmonics were found [Lea85] by Leaver to be

$${}_sS_{lm}(\theta, \varphi) = e^{im\varphi} \exp\left(a\omega_{lmn} \cos(\theta)\right) (1 + \cos(\theta))^{|m-s|/2} (1 - \cos(\theta))^{|m+s|/2} \sum_p a_p (1 + \cos(\theta))^p \quad (9.4.6)$$

were the coefficients a_p can be obtained from his continued fraction approach that was introduced as a numerical method for QNM calculation in the previous chapter.

In the following, visualizations of the spin-weighted spherical and spheroidal harmonics will be presented. Recall that compared to the spin-weighted spherical harmonics with multipole indexes l and m , the spheroidal harmonics have an additional parameter, the oblateness parameter c .

Spherical harmonics

The most important Gravitational Wave (-2) spin-weighted spherical multimodes are

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}_{-2}Y_{22} &= \sqrt{\frac{5}{64\pi}} (1 + \cos \theta)^2 e^{2i\varphi}, \\
 {}_{-2}Y_{21} &= \sqrt{\frac{5}{16\pi}} \sin \theta (1 + \cos \theta)^2 e^{i\varphi}, \\
 {}_{-2}Y_{20} &= \sqrt{\frac{15}{32\pi}} \sin^2 \theta, \\
 {}_{-2}Y_{2-1} &= \sqrt{\frac{5}{16\pi}} \sin \theta (1 - \cos \theta)^2 e^{-i\varphi}, \\
 {}_{-2}Y_{2-2} &= \sqrt{\frac{5}{64\pi}} (1 - \cos \theta)^2 e^{-2i\varphi},
 \end{aligned} \tag{9.4.7}$$

with an angular dependence that is plotted in plan view on a sphere in figure 9.15.

Spheroidal harmonics

The spin-weighted spheroidal harmonics (SWSdH) ${}_sS_{lm}(\theta, \varphi, c)$ are generalizations of the spin-weighted spherical harmonics (SWSH) ${}_sY_{lm}(\theta, \varphi)$ with vanishing oblateness parameter c , that is

$${}_sY_{lm}(\theta, \varphi) = {}_sS_{lm}(\theta, \varphi, 0). \tag{9.4.8}$$

The SWSdH separate in their angular dependence as

$${}_sS_{lm}(\theta, \varphi, c) = \frac{1}{2\pi} {}_sS_{lm}(x; c) e^{im\varphi} \tag{9.4.9}$$

being solutions of the differential equation

$$\partial_x \left[(1 - x^2) \partial_x [{}_sS_{lm}(x; c)] \right] + \left[(cx)^2 - 2csx + s + {}_sA_{lm}(c) - \frac{(m + sx)^2}{1 - x^2} \right] {}_sS_{lm}(x; c) = 0 \tag{9.4.10}$$

where ${}_sA_{lm}(c)$ is the separation constant.

Further reading: [Zal14].

Figure 9.14 reveals the spheroidal isosurfaces of constant angles θ , φ and oblateness parameter c .

The plots in figure 9.16, 9.17, 9.18 and 9.19 illustrate demonstrative parameter variations of the multipole indexes (l, m) and the oblateness parameter c shown from two different views (plan and axial). With each multipole index l , there is an additional band of high intensity. If the oblateness is increasing, the bands get shifted towards the poles.

Figure 9.14: Spheroidal isosurfaces of constant angles θ , φ and oblateness c [Fal01].

Figure 9.15: Spherical harmonic distribution with $(s, l, m) = (-2, 2, m)$.

Figure 9.16: Spheroidal harmonic distribution $(s, n, c) = (-2, 1, 1)$ with varying multiple indexes $(l, m) \in \{2, 4, 8\}$.

Figure 9.17: Spheroidal harmonic distribution $(s, n, c) = (-2, 1, 1)$ with varying multiple indexes $(l, m) \in \{3, 6, 9\}$.

Figure 9.18: Spheroidal harmonic distribution $(s, n, l, m) = (-2, 1, 2, 0)$ with varying oblateness $c \in \{1, 2, 3\}$.

Figure 9.19: Spheroidal harmonic distribution $(s, n, l, m) = (-2, 1, 2, 0)$ with varying oblateness $c \in \{3, 9, 18\}$.

9.4.2 SXS ringdown and Berti QNMs

Figure 9.20 presents the angular distribution of both the SXS-ringdown data of all available multipoles ($l \in [2, 8]$) and the Berti QNMs of the fundamental mode ($n = 1$) and available multipoles ($l \in [2, 7]$).

Figure 9.20: SXS-ringdown and Berti-QNM (fundamental mode) comparison.

As the angular distribution looks very similar it could be inferred that almost all *fundamental* Quasinormal Modes are excited when Black Holes collide while the quadrupolar $l = 2$ mode is dominant as expected.

9.5 SXS Initial Data (own results)

Animations of the angular distribution of the merger amplitude show that it is almost perfectly independent of the initial data (most importantly the mass ratio q and effective spin S_{eff}) or the final spin j_f . In the movies, the parameters are varied over the parameterspace. The mass ratio is increased from 1 to 10 in steps of 1, the effective spin is increased from 0.1 to 1.0 in steps of 0.1 and the same applies to the final spin. As, due to the almost negligible changes, it is not reasonable to print the movies in their full length as a sequence on paper, only the first and the last frame is plotted in figure 9.22 and 9.21. The movie files can be found on the CD that is attached.

Figure 9.21: Independence of the angular distribution from the resulting final spin j_f .

With increasing final or effective spin, the intensity maxima within the bands get slightly shifted towards the poles, as it is expected due to the resulting increase in the oblateness parameter

$$c = \omega j_f. \tag{9.5.1}$$

Figure 7.13 shows that with the effective spin, the merger frequency ω is increased, which in turn raises the oblateness.

Figure 9.22: Independence of the angular distribution from the initial data, that is the mass ratio q (first row) or effective spin S_{eff} (second row).

Chapter 10

Summary and Outlook

In this thesis, various issues in the theory of Gravitational Waves from Binary Black Hole systems as well as Black Hole Quasinormal Modes have been examined.

In chapter 2 Basics, the fundamental aspects of the theory of Special and General Relativity were presented followed by a review of Gravitational Wave properties and Black Hole spacetimes. Finally, Binary Black Holes were introduced together with the Gravitational Wave signal that is expected to be produced when two Black Holes collide and merge (coalescence).

In chapter 3 Analysis, the most important facts about ground- and space-based Gravitational Wave detectors were outlined along with a survey of their technical properties, setup and sensitivity (curves). The issue of detector noise was discussed, leading to data analysis tools such as "matched-filtering".

In chapter 4 Approximation, the description of Binary Black Hole inspiral dynamics and the involved Gravitational Wave polarization modes in Newtonian and Post-Newtonian theory was summarized and illustrated by plots of the waveforms, its phase and frequency as well as the orbital decay.

In chapter 5 Simulation, the constitutive theory of Numerical Relativity was worked out, starting with the 3+1 Decomposition of spacetime which enables bringing the general relativistic description of astrophysical processes into a form that can be treated as an initial value (or Cauchy) problem, allowing for computer simulations of the strong-field regime of Black Holes. The historical ADM formulation and some improved versions, the BSSN equations and Generalized Harmonic coordinates, were discussed, followed by a brief review of Black Hole Initial Data, the numerical treatment of Black Hole singularities and fundamental numerical approaches such as spectral methods. Finally, the Spectral Einstein Code (SpEC) was presented together with the SXS waveform catalog of Binary Black Hole coalescence simulations. The parameterspace was examined with respect to available mass ratios, spins, orbital frequencies, simulated orbits and eccentricity. The chapter closed with an investigation of the Black Hole spin precession that is included in the catalog.

Chapter 6 Extraction reviewed the two basic methods to obtain the Gravitational Wave content from a Numerical Relativity simulation, the gauge-invariant Regge-Wheeler-Zerilli approach and the tetrad-based Newman-Penrose formalism.

Chapter 7 Modeling compared different approaches that were motivated by the fact that Numerical Relativity simulations often require a lot of computation time and are difficult to perform for high mass ratios and extremal spins, leading to a sparse coverage of the parameterspace. The Effective One Body code that provides fast waveforms with a dense parameterspace coverage was described and performed. Notably, a phenomenological model was constructed for the merger and ringdown part of the Binary Black Hole coalescence waveform that contains the constitutive merger and ringdown quantities fitted over the whole parameterspace and all multipole modes of the examined waveforms from the available SXS simulations.

Chapter 8 Perturbation presented the fundamental theory of Quasinormal Mode (QNM) excitations of the perturbed Black Hole Schwarzschild and Kerr metric. Two different approaches for the numerical calculation of QNMs were presented: Leaver's continued-fraction method and Cook's spectral method and afterwards compared in their performance that is the convergence. Subsequently, available datasets were exemplified and compared to the ringdown frequency and decay times of the Numerical Relativity waveforms in order to find out that the fundamental QNM is predominantly excited when two Black Holes collide.

Chapter 9 Visualization completed the thesis with methods to illustrate the spacetime curvature, especially in the nonlinear strong-field regime of Black Holes. After a review of the basic properties of the recently developed tendex/vortex formalism, some applications to Gravitational Waves and Black Holes were discussed, showing that static (nonrotating Schwarzschild) and dynamic (rotating Kerr) Black Holes produce regions of strong stretching, squeezing or whirling that propagate as Gravitational Waves. Subsequently, the Quasinormal Modes were visualized using the tendex/vortex formalism as well as projections on a sphere to show the angular distribution of the spin-weighted spheroidal harmonics along with variations of the different parameters. Finally, the angular distribution of the Gravitational Waves at merger was monitored over the SXS parameterspace in movies which suggest that the radiation spreading is almost perfectly independent of the initial data of the Binary Black Hole coalescence simulation.

Concluding this thesis, some future directions of Gravitational Wave research are highlighted.

Detectors are expected to steadily improve in sensitivity. The first detection of GW150914 has opened a new window for the exploration of the gravitating universe: Gravitational Wave astronomy enabling observations of the dark universe that refuses to emit detectable electromagnetic radiation. Combining the measurements of both gravitational and electromagnetic waves, it will be possible to extend the cosmic distance ladder and verify former results of Radio astronomy.

Simulation tools for Binary Black Hole coalescence applications will be constantly enhanced. Increasing computer power, more stable algorithms and codes as well as amended mathematical methods will help achieving higher accuracy, a larger parameterspace coverage, extremal spins and additional precessing simulations. Apart from Black Holes, also Neutron Stars are of strong interest, requiring relativistic hydrodynamics dealing with tidal disruptions and magnetic fields.

Modeling of analytic waveforms will remain a very important task due to the requirements of the ongoing experimental detector data analysis. Effective One Body models will increase in accuracy and overlap with numerical simulations, especially being more successful in the case of precessing binaries. Surrogate (Reduced Order) and Phenomenological models will profit from additional simulation data and output of the EOB codes. All these steps will lead a way towards high accurate and fast waveform templates that will be tested by future ground- and space-based detectors.

Perturbation theory will continue to play an essential role for the description of Quasinormal Modes from Black Holes and Neutron Stars. A comparison with simulation results will serve as a cross-check helping to a more accurate parameter estimation of the binary. Second order QNMs will aid accessing the errors in the perturbation calculations and are necessary to examine nonlinear mode coupling and parametric resonance or instabilities of Black Holes. Recently, also a fluid-gravity duality has been discovered revealing gravitational turbulence. Most importantly, General Relativity needs to be affirmed or disproved along with the No-hair theorem of Black Holes.

Visualization of Gravitational Waves in Black Hole spacetimes has made a huge advance with the development of the tendex/vortex tools to illustrate the spacetime curvature effects (stretching or squeezing and twisting). Hopefully, the formalism will be prospectively applied to an increasing number of additional scenarios, particularly in the context of numerical simulations. The visualization of Quasinormal Modes is an interesting topic that so far has not received much attention. Hopefully, it will be explored in greater depth along with new results from perturbation theory, Numerical Relativity and Quantum Gravity. Finally, a didactic treatment of QNMs would be desirable to attract public attention in popular scientific journals, movies and documentaries, at planetaria, universities or schools.

Further reading: [KS99, BCS09, Zim16].

Cover picture showing an artwork of a Binary Black Hole coalescence with the emitted Gravitational Waves [APS].

Chapter 11

Codes and Literature

This appendix exemplifies some selected codes that were written to process the data and generate the named figures shown in the indicated chapters. More than 100 additional MATLAB scripts can be found on a CD that is attached.

11.1 Chapter Simulation

PlotPrecession.m producing figure 5.20.

```
%%analyse amplitude modulation from spin precession
%%author: Philipp Scharpf, version: 16.05.17

%SXS parameters
BBHparams = importdata('BBHdata/BBHparams.dat');
%specify BBHs to be processed
%BBHnrs = importdata('BBHnrs-rhOverM.dat');

%extraction order
N = 3;
%mode
l = 2;
m = 2;

%iterate over BBHs specified
stop = size(BBHnrs);
for i=1:stop(l)
    BBHnr = BBHnrs(i);

%display BBHnr currently processed
disp(['BBH' mat2str(BBHnr)])

%read in waveform
WF = readWF(BBHnr,N,l,m);

%find properties of requested waveform
index = find(BBHparams(:,1)==BBHnr);
q = BBHparams(index,2);
chi1 = BBHparams(index,3);
chi2 = BBHparams(index,4);

%get and plot amplitude (modulation)
cWF = complex(WF(2,:),WF(3,:));
ampl = abs(cWF);
t = WF(1,:);

figure
plot(t,ampl);
xlim([0 3000]);
title(['q = ' mat2str(round(q,2)) ' ', '\chi_1 = ' mat2str(round(chi1,2)) ' ', '\chi_2 = '
mat2str(round(chi2,2))]);
xlabel('t/M', 'FontSize', 20);
ylabel('A_{22}/M', 'FontSize', 20);
set(gca, 'FontSize', 20);

%get and plot spin (precession)
Spin = getSpin(BBHnr,'A');
Spinx = Spin(2,:);
Spiny = Spin(2,:);
Spinz = Spin(2,:);
t = Spin(1,:);

figure
plot(t,Spiny)
hold on

Spin = getSpin(BBHnr,'B');
Spinx = Spin(2,:);
Spiny = Spin(2,:);
Spinz = Spin(2,:);
t = Spin(1,:);

plot(t,Spiny)

title(['q = ' mat2str(round(q,2)) ' ', '\chi_1 = ' mat2str(round(chi1,2)) ' ', '\chi_2 = '
mat2str(round(chi2,2))]);
xlabel('t/M', 'FontSize', 20);
ylabel('\chi_x', 'FontSize', 20);
set(gca, 'FontSize', 20);

end
```

11.2 Chapter Modeling

findModeRelevance.m producing figure 7.21.

```

%%%find relevance of individual modes (l,m)
%%%author: Philipp Scharpf, version: 16.05.17

BBHnrs = importdata('BBHdata/BBHnrs-nonprocessing.dat');
%BBHnrs = [1]';
%extraction order
N = 3;

%iterate over BBHnrs
stop1 = size(BBHnrs);
for j=1:stop1(1)

BBHnr = BBHnrs(j);

%display BBHnr currently processed
disp(['BBH' mat2str(BBHnr)])

%find properties of requested waveform
index = find(BBHparams(:,1)==BBHnr);
q = BBHparams(index,2);
chi1 = BBHparams(index,3);
chi2 = BBHparams(index,4);
chi1x = BBHparams(index,5);
chi1y = BBHparams(index,6);
chi1z = BBHparams(index,7);
chi2x = BBHparams(index,8);
chi2y = BBHparams(index,9);
chi2z = BBHparams(index,10);
Ecc = BBHparams(index,11);
Momg = BBHparams(index,12);
orbits = BBHparams(index,13);

%compute symmetric mass ratio
nu = q/(1+q)^2;

%compute Seff from masses
[m1 m2] = extract_m1m2(BBHnr);
S = m1^2*chi1 + m2^2*chi2;
Seff = S/(m1^2+m2^2);

%get RM mass and spin

modes = importdata('BBHdata/modes2.dat');

%iterate over modes
stop2 = size(modes);
for i=1:stop2(1)

l = modes(i,1);
m = modes(i,2);

%display current mode
%disp(['l = ' mat2str(l) ', ' 'm = ' mat2str(m)]);

%read in waveform
WF = readWF(BBHnr,N,l,m);

k = i+(j-1)*stop2(1);
%display progress
%disp([mat2str(round(k/stop1(1)/stop2(1)*100,2)) ' %']);

%construct complex waveform with time
%cut junk radiation at the first half
tlength = size(WF(1,:));
thalf = round(tlength(2)/2);
h = complex(WF(2,thalf:end),WF(3,thalf:end));
t = WF(1,thalf:end);

%save basic properties
output.BBHnr(k) = BBHnr;
output.l(k) = l;
output.m(k) = m;

```

```

%compute A
output.A(k) = max(abs(h));

%compute mrg
A = abs(h);
A_mrg = max(A);
index_mrg = find(A==A_mrg);
t_mrg = t(index_mrg);

%compute omg
phi = -unwrap(angle(h));
omg = Deriv4(phi,t,4)';
output.omg(k) = omg(index_mrg);
%output.omg(k) = (phi(index_mrg+index_tau)-phi(index_mrg))/(t(index_tau) - t_mrg);

%compute tau
A_postmrg = A(index_mrg:end);
t = t(index_mrg:end);
index_tau = find(A_postmrg<=A_mrg/exp(1),1);
output.tau(k) = t(index_tau) - t_mrg;

%compute phi
output.phi(k) = phi(index_mrg);

end

end

%plot results
scatter3(output.l,output.m,output.omg,20,'filled')
scatter3(output.l,output.m,output.BBHnr,20,output.A,'filled')
c = colorbar;
xlabel('l')
ylabel('m')
zlabel('\omega_{mrg}')
zlabel('BBHnr')
ylabel(c,'\omega_{mrg}','FontSize',15)
title(['BBH' mat2str(BBHnr) ' - ' 'multimode comparison'])

```

11.3 Chapter Perturbation

fitRD.m to obtain fits from SXS data for figure 8.5, 8.6 and 8.7.

```

%%fit and save all properties of the ringdown
%%author: Philipp Scharpf, version: 16.05.17

%SXS parameters
BBHparams = importdata('BBHdata/BBHparams.dat');
BBHnrs = importdata('BBHdata/BBHnrs-rhOverM-cut.dat');
%extraction order
N = 3;
%mode
l = 2;
m = 2;

%%iterate over BBHs specified
stop = size(BBHnrs);
for i=1:stop(1)
    BBHnr = BBHnrs(i);

%display BBHnr currently processed
disp(['BBH' mat2str(BBHnr)])

%read in waveform
Cache = readWF(BBHnr,N,l,m);

%find properties of requested waveform
index = find(BBHparams(:,1)==BBHnr);
q = BBHparams(index,2);
chilz = BBHparams(index,7);
chi2z = BBHparams(index,10);

%compute symmetric mass ratio
RD.nu(i) = q/(1+q)^2;

%compute Seff from masses
[m1 m2] = extract_m1m2(BBHnr);
S = m1^2*chilz + m2^2*chi2z;
RD.Seff(i) = S/(m1^2+m2^2);

%read in waveform
WF = readWF(BBHnr,N,l,m);

%construct complex waveform with time
%cut junk radiation at the first half
tlength = size(WF(1,:));
thalf = round(tlength(2)/2);
h = complex(WF(2,thalf:end),WF(3,thalf:end));
t = WF(1,thalf:end);

%determine merger and cut off ringdown
amp = abs(h);
amp_mrg = max(amp);
index_mrg = find(amp==amp_mrg);
index_end = find(amp < 0.01*amp_mrg,1);
h = h(index_mrg:index_end);
t = t(index_mrg:index_end) - t(index_mrg);

%get amplitude
amp = abs(h);
A = max(amp);

%get decay time
index_tau = find(amp<amp_mrg/exp(1),1);
tau = t(index_tau);

%get phase
%phi = mod(-unwrap(angle(h)),2*pi);
phi = -unwrap(angle(h));
phi0 = phi(1);
index_max = find(phi==max(phi),1);

%get frequency
%omg = (max(phi) - phi(1))/(t(index_max) - t(1));
omg = (max(phi) - phi(1))/(t(end) - t(1));

RD.A(i) = A;
RD.tau(i) = tau;
RD.phi0(i) = phi0;
RD.omg(i) = omg;

end

```

11.4 Chapter Visualization

PlotSphereBerti.m producing figure 9.20.

```

%%%Plot angular distribution of Berti data
%%%author: Philipp Scharpf, version: 16.05.17

%construct angular grid
Phi = 0:0.1:2*pi;
Theta = 0:0.05*pi;
[phi,theta] = meshgrid(Phi,Theta);

%spherical/spheroidal harmonic formula

s = -2;
n = 1;

O = 0;
for n = 1 : 1
for l = 2 : 7
    for m = 0 : 2

        %disp(['(' mat2str(l) ', ' mat2str(m) ')'])

        index = find(Berti.n==n & Berti.l==l & Berti.m==m);
        c = Berti.jf(index(1))*Berti.omg(index(1));

        O = O + sS(s,n,l,m,c,theta,phi);

    end
end
end

%normalize
peaks = max(real(O));
peakvalue = peaks(1,1);

%plot angular dependence
figure
[x,y,z] = sphere(62);
surf(x,y,z,real(O)/peakvalue)
view(2)
cb = colorbar;
xlabel('x')
ylabel('y')
zlabel('z')
ylabel(cb,'_s S_{nlm}(c)')
title('Berti QNMs - angular distribution l \in [2,7], n = 1')

```

sS.m called by PlotSphereBerti.m

```

%%%Calculate s-weighted spheroidal harmonics
%%%author: Philipp Scharpf, version: 26.04.17

function S = sS(s,n,l,m,c,theta,phi)

%spheroidal harmonic formula

S1 = exp(i*m*phi);
S2 = exp(c*cos(theta));
S3 = (1+cos(theta)).^(abs(m-s)/2) .* (1-cos(theta)).^(abs(m+s)/2);
% S4 = sum_p a_p (1+cos(theta)).^p;

S = S1.*S2.*S3;

end

```

PlotSphereSXSloop.m producing figure 9.21 and 9.22.

```

%%Plot angular distribution of SXS data in q, Seff, jf or BBH loop
%%author: Philipp Scharpf, version: 11.05.17

%construct angular grid

Phi = 0:0.1:2*pi;
Theta = 0:0.05*pi;
[phi,theta] = meshgrid(Phi,Theta);

%set global parameters

s = -2;
lmin = 2;
lmax = 8;

%set loop parameter

for BBHnr = 1 : 324
%for q = 1 : 10
%for Seff = 1 : 10
%for jf = 1 : 10

    try

% spherical/spheroidal harmonic formula

O = 0;
for l = lmin : lmax
    for mm = 0 : 2*l

        m = -l+mm;

        %disp(['(' mat2str(l) ', ' mat2str(m) ')'])

        index = find(SXS.BBHnr == BBHnr & SXS.l==l & SXS.m==m);
        %index = find(SXS.q > q-0.01 & SXS.q < q+0.01 & SXS.l==l & SXS.m==m);
        %index = find(SXS.Seff > Seff*0.08 & SXS.Seff < Seff*0.12 & SXS.l==l & SXS.m==m);
        %index = find(SXS.jf > jf*0.08 & SXS.jf < jf*0.12 & SXS.l==l & SXS.m==m);
        %index = index(1);

        O = O + SXS.A(index)*sS(s,l,l,m,SXS.jf(index)*SXS.omg(index),theta,phi);%

    end
end

%normalize

peaks = max(real(O));
peakvalue = peaks(1,1);

%plot angular dependence

[x,y,z] = sphere(62);
surf(x,y,z,real(O)/peakvalue)
%view(2)
cb = colorbar;
xlabel('x')
ylabel('y')
zlabel('z')
ylabel(cb,'A_{mrg}','FontSize',15)
title(['BBH' mat2str(BBHnr) ' ringdown - angular distribution 1 \in [' mat2str(lmin) ', ' mat2str(lmax)
'],''],'FontSize',14)
%title(['q = ' mat2str(q) ' ringdown - angular distribution 1 \in [' mat2str(lmin) ', ' mat2str(lmax) ']])
%title(['S_{eff} = ' mat2str(Seff*0.1) ' ringdown - angular distribution 1 \in [' mat2str(lmin) ', '
mat2str(lmax) ']])
%title(['j_f = ' mat2str(jf*0.1) ' ringdown - angular distribution 1 \in [' mat2str(lmin) ', ' mat2str(lmax)
'']'])

%save figures for movie

F(BBHnr) = getframe(gcf);

    catch warning('broken data'); end

end

movie2avi(F,'Movies/SXSloop.avi','compression','None');
```

List of Figures

1.1	Historical stages	2
1.2	Gravitational Waves Science	3
2.1	Minkowski and Penrose diagram	10
2.2	Gravitational Wave polarization modes	17
2.3	Free mass elongation	18
2.4	Gravitational Wave lensing	19
2.5	Orbit inclination	21
2.6	No-hair theorem	23
2.7	Wormhole solution	25
2.8	Event horizon and ergosphere	27
2.9	Schwarzschild and Kerr	27
2.10	Stages of coalescence	28
3.1	Sensitivity curve	30
3.2	Pulsar	31
3.3	LIGO setup	31
3.4	LIGO results	32
3.5	LISA's stages	33
4.1	Newtonian waveform (in Geometric and SI-Units)	38
4.2	Newtonian frequency (in Geometric and SI-Units)	39
4.3	Newtonian phase	40
4.4	Newtonian orbit	40
5.1	Foliations of spacetime	46
5.2	Extrinsic curvature	47
5.3	Triangle on cylinder or sphere	47
5.4	Lapse scalar and shift vector	48
5.5	Moving puncture method	53
5.6	Event and Apparent Horizon	53
5.7	Excision method	53
5.8	NR codes and SpEC	55
5.9	SXS Gravitational Waveform Database	56
5.10	SXS Parameterspace 3D/2D	59
5.11	SXS Parameterspace: frequency and orbits	60
5.12	SXS Parameterspace: eccentricity and precession	60
5.13	SXS waveforms	61
5.14	BBH1 orbits	62
5.15	Orbital decay BBH1	62
5.16	SXS orbit and spin	63
5.17	SXS precession and nutation	63
5.18	SXS orbit and spin of BBH165	64
5.19	Precessing Binary Black Hole system	65
5.20	SXS precession and modulation	65
5.21	Apostolatos Precession	65
7.1	Modeling approaches	74
7.2	Regimes and approximation schemes	76
7.3	EOB potential	77
7.4	Comparison NR-EOB	78
7.5	EOB dynamics and waveform	79
7.6	ROM procedure	80
7.7	SXS-ROM	80
7.8	Kerr spin fit	81
7.9	Merger part of the waveform	82
7.10	Hierarchical fit	83
7.11	Fit of amplitude at merger	84

7.12	Fit of amplitude time derivative at merger	84
7.13	Fit of frequency at merger	85
7.14	Fit of frequency time derivative at merger	85
7.15	Fits of final mass and spin	86
7.16	Ringdown part of the waveform	87
7.17	Ringdown amplitude, phase and frequency	88
7.18	Fits of ringdown waveform	89
7.19	Broken ringdown amplitude and phase	90
7.20	Junk radiation and step-oscillations	91
7.21	Multimode comparison (multiple layers) BBH1-3/100	91
7.22	Multimode comparison of the BBH1 merger quantities	92
8.1	Convergence Leaver vs. Cook	101
8.2	Berti data	101
8.3	Cook data	102
8.4	TTM and QNM boundary conditions	102
8.5	QNM comparison	103
8.6	QNM frequency and decay time of 2,2-mode	104
8.7	QNMs $l = 2$ to $l = 6$	105
9.1	Visualization of BH and GW	108
9.2	Cuboid, cylinder and superquadratic glyphs	109
9.3	Tendex and vortex lines	111
9.4	Electromagnetic and gravitational quadrupole	113
9.5	Static and dynamic electromagnetic quadrupole field lines	115
9.6	Static and dynamic gravitational quadrupole eigenlines	115
9.7	GW tendex and vortex lines in plane	117
9.8	GW tendex and vortex lines on sphere	117
9.9	Slow Spin Kerr tendex and vortex lines	119
9.10	Schwarzschild and Kerr BH tendex and vortex lines	120
9.11	BH tendexes and vortexes in plane	123
9.12	BH tendexes and vortexes on cylinder	123
9.13	BH horizon tendicities and vorticities on sphere	123
9.14	Spheroidal isosurfaces	125
9.15	Spherical distribution $(s, l, m) = (-2, 2, m)$	126
9.16	Spheroidal distribution $(s, n, c) = (-2, 1, 1)$ with $(l, m) \in \{2, 4, 8\}$	127
9.17	Spheroidal distribution $(s, n, c) = (-2, 1, 1)$ with $(l, m) \in \{3, 6, 9\}$	128
9.18	Spheroidal distribution $(s, n, l, m) = (-2, 1, 2, 0)$ with $c \in \{1, 2, 3\}$	129
9.19	Spheroidal distribution $(s, n, l, m) = (-2, 1, 2, 0)$ with $c \in \{3, 9, 18\}$	130
9.20	SXS-Berti angular distribution	131
9.21	SXS final spin angular dependence	131
9.22	SXS initial data angular dependence	132

Bibliography

Textbooks

- [Goe04] Gönner, H. *Spezielle Relativitätstheorie (und die klassische Feldtheorie)*. 1. Auflage. Springer Spektrum (2004)
- [Fli12] Fließbach, T. *Allgemeine Relativitätstheorie*. 6. Auflage. Springer Spektrum (2012)
- [Rin01] W. Rindler. *Relativity - Special, General and Cosmology*. Oxford University Press (2001)
- [BMW] Boblest, S. Müller, T. Wunner, G. *Spezielle und allgemeine Relativitätstheorie*. Springer Spektrum (2016)
- [Mag07] Maggiore, M. *Gravitational Waves. Volume 1: Theory and Experiments*. Oxford University Press (2007)
- [BS10] Baumgarte, T. Shapiro, S. *Numerical Relativity. Solving Einstein's Equations on the Computer*. Cambridge University Press (2010)
- [BPL05] Bona, C. Palenzuela-Luque, C. *Elements of Numerical Relativity*. Springer-Verlag (2005)
- [RZ13] Rezolla, L. Zanotti, O. *Relativistic Hydrodynamics*. Oxford University Press (2013)
- [Gou07] Gourgoulhon, E. *3+1 Formalism and Bases of Numerical Relativity*. Spinger (2012)
- [PR84] Penrose, R. Rindler, W. *Spinors and Space-Time: Volume 1, Two-Spinor Calculus and Relativistic Fields*. Cambridge Monographs on Mathematical Physics (1984)
- [Gal13] Galilei, G. *Discorsi e dimostrazioni matematiche*. Verlag Elsevier (2013)
- [BS15] Buonanno, A. Sathyaprakash, B.S. *General Relativity and Gravitation: A Centennial Perspective*. Cambridge University Press (2015)

Thesis

- [Mas14] Masterson, A. *Evolution and Regularisation of Vacuum Brill Gravitational Waves in Spherical Polar Coordinates*. PhD thesis. University of Calgary (18.11.2014). <http://theses.ucalgary.ca/handle/11023/1804> (30.10.2016)
- [Boy09] Boyle, M. *Accurate gravitational waveforms from binary black-hole systems*. PhD thesis. California Institute of Technology (6.2.2009). <http://thesis.library.caltech.edu/143/> (8.10.2016)
- [Zal14] Zalutskiy, M. *Efficient iterative algorithm for computing quasinormal modes of black holes and information extraction from black hole ringdown signal*. Master's thesis. Wake Forest University Graduate School of Arts and Sciences. (May 2014) <https://wakespace.lib.wfu.edu/handle/10339/39254> (23.2.2017)
- [Zim13] Zimmerman, A. *Topics in Black Hole Perturbation Theory and the Visualization of Curved Spacetime*. PhD thesis. California Institute of Technology. (15.4.2013) <http://thesis.library.caltech.edu/7713/> (3.3.2017)
- [Fal01] Falloon, P. *Theory and Computation of Spheroidal Harmonics with General Arguments*. Master's thesis. University of Western Australia (Sept. 2001). ftp://www.biophysics.uwa.edu.au/pub/Theses/MSc/Falloon/Masters_Thesis.pdf (23.2.2017)
- [Mül06] Müller, T. *Visualisierung in der Relativitätstheorie*. PhD thesis. Universität Tübingen (2006)
- [Mun10] Munz, H. *Visualisierung von Gravitationswellen in der allgemeinen Relativitätstheorie*. Diploma thesis. Universität Stuttgart (2010)

Papers

- [Abb16] Abbott, B. et al. (LIGO Scientific Collaboration and Virgo Collaboration) *Observation of Gravitational Waves from a Binary Black Hole Merger*. Phys. Rev. Lett. 116, 061102 (11.2.2016)
- [KPJ16] Kausar, R. Philippoz, L. Jetzer, P. *Gravitational wave polarization modes in $f(R)$ theories*. Phys. Rev. D 93, 124071 (2016)
- [Sch16] Schwarzschild, K. *Über das Gravitationsfeld eines Massenpunkts nach der Einsteinschen Theorie*. Sitz. Akad. Wiss. p. 189–196 (1916)
- [MT88] Morris, M. Thorne, K. Yurtsever, U. *Wormholes, Time Machines, and the Weak Energy Condition*. Phys. Rev. Lett. 61, 1446 (1988)
- [HH17] Hernandez-Pastora, J. Herrera, L. *Interior solution for the Kerr metric*. Phys. Rev. D 95, 024003 (4.1.2017)
- [Ker63] Kerr, R. *Gravitational Field of a Spinning Mass as an Example of Algebraically Special Metrics*. Phys. Rev. Lett. 11, 237 (1.9.1963)
- [Tho74] Thorne, K. *Disk-Accretion onto a Black Hole. II. Evolution of the Hole*. Astrophysical Journal, Vol. 191, pp. 507-520 (15.7.1974)
- [MCB14] Moore, C. Cole, R. Berry, C. *Gravitational-wave sensitivity curves*. IOP Publishing Ltd, Classical and Quantum Gravity, Volume 32, Number 1, 015014 (8.10.2015)
- [Hug09] Hughes, S. *Gravitational Waves from Merging Compact Binaries*. Annu. Rev. Astron. Astrophys. 2009. Vol. 47: 107-157
- [CB10] Centrella, J. Baker, J. et al. *Black-hole binaries, gravitational waves, and numerical relativity*. Rev. Mod. Phys. 82, 3069 (16.11.2010)
- [ADM59] Arnowitt, R. Deser, S. Misner, C. *Dynamical Structure and Definition of Energy in General Relativity*. Phys. Rev. 116, 1322 (1.12.1959)
- [Pre05a] Pretorius, F. *Evolution of Binary Black-Hole Spacetimes*. Phys. Rev. Lett. 95, 121101 (14.9.2005)
- [Pre05b] Pretorius, F. *Numerical relativity using a generalized harmonic decomposition*. IOP Publishing Ltd, Classical and Quantum Gravity, Volume 22, Number 2, 425–451 (3.1.2005)
- [SN95] Shibata, M. Nakamura, T. *Evolution of three- dimensional gravitational waves: Harmonic slicing case*. Phys. Rev. D 52, 5428–5444 (1995)
- [BS98] Baumgarte, T. Shapiro, S. *Numerical integration of Einstein's field equations*. Phys. Rev. D 59, 024007 (1998)
- [Mro13] Mroué et al. *Catalog of 174 Binary Black Hole Simulations for Gravitational Wave Astronomy*. Phys. Rev. Lett. 111, 241104 (11.12.2010)
- [Aji12] Ajith, P. Boyle, M. et al. *The NINJA-2 catalog of hybrid post-Newtonian/numerical-relativity waveforms for non-precessing black-hole binaries*. IOP Publishing Ltd. Classical and Quantum Gravity, Volume 29, Number 12, 124001 (1.6.2012)
- [Hin13] Hinder, I. et al. *Error-analysis and comparison to analytical models of numerical waveforms produced by the NRAR Collaboration*. IOP Publishing Ltd. Classical and Quantum Gravity, Volume 31, Number 2, 025012 (5.12.2013)
- [Apo94] Apostolatos, T. Cutler, C. Sussman, G. and Thorne, K. *Spin-induced orbital precession and its modulation of the gravitational waveforms from merging binaries*. Phys. Rev. D 49, 6274 (15.6.1994)
- [Ohm12] Ohme, F. *Analytical meets numerical relativity: status of complete gravitational waveform models for binary black holes*. Class. Quantum Grav. 29, 124002 (1.6.2012)
- [Hue16] Huerta, E. *A complete waveform model for compact binaries on eccentric orbits*. Phys. Rev. D 95, 024038 (31.1.2017)
- [Hin10] Hinder, I. *Comparisons of eccentric binary black hole simulations with post-Newtonian models*. Phys. Rev. D 82, 024033 (27.7.2010)

- [Boh17] Bohé et al. *Improved effective-one-body model of spinning, nonprecessing binary black holes for the era of gravitational-wave astrophysics with advanced detectors*. Phys. Rev. D 95, 044028 (17.2.2017)
- [BD99] Buonanno, A. Damour, T. *Effective one-body approach to general relativistic two-body dynamics*. Phys. Rev. D 59, 084006 (8.3.1999)
- [Dam08] Damour, T. *Introductory lectures on the Effective One Body formalism*. Int. J. Mod. Phys. A 23, 1130 (30.3.2008)
- [Nag16] *Energetics and phasing of nonprecessing spinning coalescing black hole binaries*. Nagar, A. Damour, T. et al. Phys. Rev. D 93, 044046 (17.2.2016)
- [Bla15] Blackman, J. et al. *Fast and Accurate Prediction of Numerical Relativity Waveforms from Binary Black Hole Coalescences Using Surrogate Models*. Phys. Rev. Lett. 115, 121102 (18.9.2015)
- [Hus16] Husa, S. et al. *Frequency-domain gravitational waves from nonprecessing black-hole binaries. I. New numerical waveforms and anatomy of the signal*. Phys. Rev. D 93, 044006 (3.2.2016)
- [Han14] Hannam, M. et al. *Simple Model of Complete Precessing Black-Hole-Binary Gravitational Waveforms*. Phys. Rev. Lett. 113, 151101 (7.10.2014)
- [RW57] Regge, T. Wheeler, J. *Stability of a Schwarzschild Singularity*. Phys. Rev. 108, 1063 (15.11.1957)
- [Zer70] Zerilli, F. *Effective Potential for Even-Parity Regge-Wheeler Gravitational Perturbation Equations*. Phys. Rev. Lett. 24, 737 (30.3.1970)
- [NP62] Newman, E. Penrose, R. *An Approach to Gravitational Radiation by a Method of Spin Coefficients*. Journal of Mathematical Physics 3, 566 (1962)
- [Teu72] Teukolsky, S. *Rotating Black Holes: Separable Wave Equations for Gravitational and Electromagnetic Perturbations*. Phys. Rev. Lett. 29, 1114 (16.10.1972)
- [Vis70] Vishveshwara, C. *Scattering of Gravitational Radiation by a Schwarzschild Black-hole*. Nature Letters 227, 936 - 938 (29.8.1970)
- [Jim16] Jiménez-Forteza, X. et al. *Hierarchical data-driven approach to fitting numerical relativity data for nonprecessing binary black holes with an application to final spin and radiated energy*. Phys. Rev. D 95, 064024 (15.3.2017)
- [Hug00] Hughes, S. *Evolution of circular, nonequatorial orbits of Kerr black holes due to gravitational-wave emission*. Phys. Rev. D 61, 084004 (15.3.2000)
- [BCS09] Berti, E. Cardoso, V. Starinets, A. *Quasinormal modes of black holes and black branes*. IOP Publishing Ltd, Classical and Quantum Gravity, Volume 26, Number 16, 163001 (24.7.2009)
- [BCW06] Berti, E. Cardoso, V. Will, C. *On gravitational-wave spectroscopy of massive black holes with the space interferometer LISA*. Phys. Rev. D 73, 064030 (24.3.2006)
- [CZ14] Cook, G. Zalutskiy, M. *Gravitational perturbations of the Kerr geometry: High-accuracy study*. Phys. Rev. D 90, 124021 (5.12.2015)
- [Schu10] Schultz, T. Kindlemann, G. *Superquadric glyphs for symmetric second-order tensors*. IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics. Volume 16, Issue 6, 1595-1604 (Nov. 2010)
- [Owe11] Owen, R. et al. *Frame-Dragging Vortexes and Tidal Tendexes Attached to Colliding Black Holes: Visualizing the Curvature of Spacetime*. Phys. Rev. Lett. 106, 151101 (11.4.2011)
- [Nic12] Nichols, D. et al. *Visualizing Spacetime Curvature via Frame-Drag Vortexes and Tidal Tendexes I. General Theory and Weak-Gravity Applications*. Phys. Rev. D 84, 124014 (6.12.2011)
- [Zha12] Zhang, F. et al. *Visualizing spacetime curvature via frame-drag vortexes and tidal tendexes. II. Stationary black holes*. Phys. Rev. D 86, 084049 (26.10.2012)
- [Zim12] Zimmerman, A. et al. *Visualizing spacetime curvature via frame-drag vortexes and tidal tendexes. III. Quasi-normal pulsations of Schwarzschild and Kerr black holes*. Phys. Rev. D 86, 104028 (12.11.2012)
- [PBN13] Price, R. Belcher, J. Nichols, D. *Comparison of electromagnetic and gravitational radiation: What we can learn about each from the other*. American Journal of Physics 81, 575 (July 2013)

- [CL93] Cabral, B. Leedom, L. *Imaging Vector Fields Using Line Integral Convolution*. Proc. SIGGRAPH 93, 263-270 (1993). Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory. <http://cs.brown.edu/courses/csci2370/2000/1999/cabral.pdf> (10.4.2017)
- [Sun03] Sunquist, A. *Dynamic line integral convolution for visualizing streamline evolution*. IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics. Volume 9, Issue 3, 273-282 (July-Sept. 2003)
- [DB12] Dennison, K. Baumgarte, T. *Invariants for tendex and vortex fields*. Phys. Rev. D 86, 107503 (8.11.2012)
- [Gol67] Goldberg, J. et al. *Spin-s Spherical Harmonics and δ* . AIP Journal of Mathematical Physics 8, 2155 (1967)
- [Lea85] Leaver, E. *An Analytic Representation for the Quasi-Normal Modes of Kerr Black Holes*. Proc. Roy. Soc. Lond. A402, 285 (1985)
- [KS99] Kokkotas, K. Schmidt, B. *Quasi-Normal Modes of Stars and Black Holes*. Living Reviews in Relativity 2.1, p. 2 (1999)

Codes

- [ET] GW150914. <http://einstein toolkit.org/about/gallery/gw150914/> (8.10.2016)
- [SpEC] SpEC. <http://www.black-holes.org/SpEC.html>
- [EOB] EOB-IHES. <https://eob.ihes.fr/>

Catalogs

- [CoS] Müller, T. Grave, F. Catalogue of Spacetimes. arXiv (2009) letzte Version Mai 2014: <http://go.visus.uni-stuttgart.de/CoS> (2.4.2016)
- [SDB] SXS Waveform Database. <http://www.black-holes.org/waveforms/catalog.php> (8.10.2016)
- [GTD] Georgia Tech Catalog. <http://www.einstein.gatech.edu/catalog/> (8.10.2016)
- [BD] Berti, E. Ringdown data <http://www.phy.olemiss.edu/~berti/ringdown> (16.3.2017)

Web pages

- [LIGO] LIGO collaboration. www.ligo.org (18.3.2017)
- [LOSC] LIGO Open Science Center. <https://losc.ligo.org> (18.3.2017)
- [LISA] LISA Science. <https://www.elisascience.org/> (23.3.2017)
- [SXS] SXS collaboration. <http://www.black-holes.org> (4.11.2016)
- [HDF] HDF Group. <https://www.hdfgroup.org> (20.2.2017)
- [SA] Horgan, J. *Pioneering Physicist John Wheeler Dies at 96*. Scientific American (1991) <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/pioneering-physicist-john-wheeler-dies> (27.2.2017)
- [Mue] Müller, A. *Lexikon der Astrophysik*. <http://www.spektrum.de/astrowissen/lexdt.html> (27.2.2017)
- [Mue2] Müller, A. LSW Heidelberg. <http://www.lsw.uni-heidelberg.de/users/amueller> (28.2.2017)
- [Spek] Spektrum der Wissenschaft. *Lexikon der Astronomie*. <http://www.spektrum.de/lexikon/astronomie> (1.3.2017)

Images

- [APS] APS Physics. https://physics.aps.org/assets/f91c3735-0779-443e-9a74-449ac4df8c39/e68_1.png (4.11.2016)
- [phys] phys.org. <http://phys.org/news/2016-02-gravitational-black-hole.html> (4.11.2016)
- [Nor] John D. Norton http://www.pitt.edu/~jdnorton/teaching/HPS_0410/chapters/black_holes_picture/
- [NASA] NASA. <http://science.gsfc.nasa.gov/663/images/gravity/GWspec.jpg> (11.10.2016)
- [Quora] Quora. <https://www.quora.com/If-universe-is-spherical-why-do-physicists-explain-wormhole-using-a-sheet-of-paper> (1.3.2017)
- [LE] LIGO Education. <https://www.ligo.caltech.edu/> (21.3.2017)
- [UB] Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin. <https://www.physics.hu-berlin.de/en/qom/research/freqref/lisa> (21.3.2017)
- [OTTE] Onward To The Edge <https://onwardtotheedge.wordpress.com/2013/01/14/neutron-stars/> (22.3.2017)
- [RLC] Read Letter Christians. <https://www.redletterchristians.org/beautiful-minds-newton-einstein-think-gravity-god/> (2.2.2017)
- [GCS] Gauss Centre for Supercomputing. http://www.gauss-centre.eu/ gauss-centre/EN/Projects/Astrophysics/2014/husa_grav_wave_signals.html?nn=1345700 (4.11.2016)
- [GCS2] Gauss Centre for Supercomputing. http://www.gauss-centre.eu/ gauss-centre/EN/Projects/Astrophysics/2014/rezzolla_bin_black_hole.html?nn=1345700 (3.4.2017)
- [ctc] Stephen Hawking Centre for Theoretical Cosmology News. http://www.ctc.cam.ac.uk/news/150330_newsitem.php or if missing https://web-beta.archive.org/web/20150906145525/http://www.ctc.cam.ac.uk/news/150330_newsitem.php (23.2.2017)
- [NASA2] NASA. <https://www.elisascience.org/multimedia/image/emri-image> (4.11.2016)
- [eLISA] eLISA. <https://www.elisascience.org/files/imagecache/fullview/images/LISA-orbit.jpg> (4.11.2016)
- [Alc] Alchetron. Tullio Regge <https://alchetron.com/Tullio-Regge-994167-W> (7.3.2017)
- [SH] Today in Science History. John Wheeler https://todayinsci.com/W/Wheeler_John/WheelerJohn-Quotations.htm (7.3.2017)
- [MP] Math Pubs. Frank Zerilli <http://www.mathpubs.com/author/Frank+Zerilli> (7.3.2017)
- [RSF] Resonance Science Foundation. <http://resonance.is/black-holes-described-gravitational-atom/> (2.3.2017)
- [Wiki] Wikipedia. https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Henri_Poincar%C3%A9 (2.3.2017)
- [Phyx] PHYSIKALISCHE SOIREE Knowledge Base . <https://www.phyx.at/warum-ist-albert-einstein-bedeutend/> (2.3.2017)
- [APS2] APS Physics. https://www.aps.org/programs/honors/prizes/prizerecipient.cfm?last_nm=Pretorius&first_nm=Frans&year=2003 (2.3.2017)
- [PSUCI] School of Physical Sciences. <https://ps.uci.edu/news/48962> (2.3.2017)
- [Wiki2] Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ADM_formalism (2.3.2017)
- [EinOn] Einstein Online. http://www.einstein-online.info/vertiefung/aLIGO@set_language=de.html (2.3.2017)
- [SymMag] Symmetry Magazine. <https://www.symmetrymagazine.org/article/gravitational-waves-and-where-to-find-them> (2.3.2017)

[Wiki3] Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Laser_Interferometer_Space_Antenna (2.3.2017)

[SSA] Science in Society Archive http://www.i-sis.org.uk/Gravitational_Waves_Exist_but_Colliding_Black_Holes.php (2.3.2017)

Presentations

[Sch13] Scheel, M. *Numerical relativity: Triumphs and challenges of binary black hole simulations*. California Institute of Technology (6.6.2013). http://www.tapir.caltech.edu/~rom-gr/slides/Mark_Scheel.pdf (13.2.2017)

[Ott15] Ott, C. *Simulation and Modeling of Gravitational Wave Sources*. TAPIR, Caltech - SXS Collaboration. https://indico.cern.ch/event/462448/contributions/1979211/attachments/1204237/1754156/Ott_COFI_20151205.pdf (21.3.2017)

[Pei09] Peikert, R. *Tensor Field Visualization*. SciVis (2007) https://graphics.ethz.ch/teaching/former/scivis_07/Notes/Slides/09-tensorField.pdf (18.4.2017)

[Zim16] Zimmerman, A. *Black Hole Ringdown and Quasinormal Modes*. Perimeter Institute for Theoretical Physics (2016) <https://www.perimeterinstitute.ca/videos/black-hole-ringdown-and-quasinormal-modes> (25.4.2017)